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RESEARCH REGARDING ON THE INFLUENCE OF CROP ROTATION AND NUTRITION REGIME ON THE GROWTH PROGRESS OF BIOMASS AND PRODUCTION IN WINTER WHEAT CULTIVATED ON LUVOSOILS

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Abstract

The paper is based on the research carried out during 2018-2020 in a long term trial placed in 2001 on the luvisol from Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea. The crop rotation and nutrition regime influence on the biomass and yield were studied in the following device: factor A- crop rotation (a_1 = winter wheat, monocrop; a_2 = winter wheat-maize; a_3 = pea-winter wheat-maize a_4 = pea-winter wheat-maize-maize) factor B- nutrition regime (b_1 = N0P0; b_2 = $N_{120}P_{80}$; b_3 = $N_{120}P_{80}$ +manure 10 t/ha (applied for every crop). The biggest quantity of total biomass was determined in the crop rotation pea-winter wheat-maize-maize and the smallest quantity was registered in the winter wheat monocrop in all stages of the vegetation period. The difference between these variants were of 128% at the beginning of the vegetation, of 39% at the first internod formation, of 22% at straw elongation, of 25% at spike formation, of 26% at the beginning of the seed formation, of 21% at early ripening, of 23% at incomplete ripening and of 29% at complete ripening; the nutrition regime had a great influence, too, on the total dry biomass. The highest values were registered in the variant fertilized with $N_{120}P_{80}$ +manure 10 t/ha and the smallest in the variant N0P0. Between these variants, the following differences were determined: of 64% at the beginning of the vegetation, of 48% at the formation of the first internod, of 53% at straw elongation; at 38% at the formation of spike; of 32% at the beginning of seeds formation, of 39% at early ripening, of 41% at incomplete ripening and of 24% at complete ripening; in the total biomass, the grain mass represented 35%-43%, straw mass 22%-42%, chaff mass 4%-14%, foliar mass 5%-10% and root mass represented 4-9%; the crop rotation influenced the yield level. The smallest yield was obtained in winter wheat monocrop, 2920 kg/ha. In the other variants, the yields obtained were bigger; the differences were of 21% in winter wheat-maize, of 56% in pea-winter wheat-maize and of 57% in pea-winter wheat-maize-maize; the nutrition regime influenced very much (2610 kg/ha) the yield level, in comparison with the variant N0P0, the winter wheat yield obtained in the variant with $N_{120}P_{80}$ increased with 69% and in the variant $N_{120}P_{80}$ +manure 10 t/ha with 80%.

Key words: winter wheat, crop rotation, fertilization level, phenophase, biomass wheat components

INTRODUCTION

The biomass accumulation, as well as a large yield of a superior quality, is conditioned by a series of factors as the intensity, quality and duration of illumination, atmospheric air warmth and soil temperature, water content of soil, plant water content, precipitations, atmospheric humidity, chemical composition of soil, fertility, crop rotation and fertilization (Bingham, 1980, Soltner, 1990, Salisbury, 1995).

The crop rotation together with other appropriate agricultural practices contribute to the favourableness of growth and development conditions of wheat root system, to an improved synthesis of specific organic compounds and their improved translocation to plant's organs (Ionescu, 1985, Ardelean, 2009, 2013).

At the low temperature during winter, the process of photosynthesis does not stop, but the content of chlorophyll decreases, the content of ascorbic acid increases, the concentration of the cellular juice increases, the percent of dry substance increases, which points out a better adaptation to the conditions during winter (Austin, 1978, Schmidt, 1980,).

The intensity of the growth of wheat plants in spring stands under the influence of the moisture and temperature conditions, important differences in the quantity of dry substance accumulated by the wheat plants being determined by the mineral and organic-mineral nutrition factors. (Bandici, et. al., 2003).

Plant growth is fundamental in obtaining yield and it is related to vegetation and technological factors, the level of yield being reflected in the intensity of biomass accumulation. In the majority of cases, total growth of green mass is considered on the assumption that a maximum yield is obtained by increasing total dry weight biomass production and by a favourable repartition of it among plant's organs (Dincă, 1982).

However, as a known fact roots are not only absorbing water and nutrients from soil but play a key role in plant's general metabolism. Roots harbour the biosynthesis of some essential compounds for the rest of the plant to which they send the biosynthetic products (Lazany, 2000).

The conclusions that were reached with regard to a normal development of plants, point the importance of a balanced NP fertilisation. This ensures the avoidance of disturbances caused by drought during the vegetation period which decrease plant's resistance. Also, a balanced fertilisation promotes a corresponding passage over each growth stage in order to equilibrate the other vital process, the development and finally to reach corresponding productions (Lazany, 2003).

Most of the research was centred on the influence of crop rotation on the yields, namely on the biomass accumulation. The crop rotations with regard to wheat was very satisfactory in this order as forerunner plant: pea, beans, winter rape, linseed, soy, red clover, potato, sugar beet, sunflower, corn etc. (Muntean L.S., et al., Domuța, Bandici, 2007).

After long tests it was demonstrated the importance of crop rotation on wheat yields on brown-red soils in Romanian Plain. On clay-illuvial podzols, the introduction of ameliorative plants, such as red clover represented an element of utmost importance for the increase of the wheat yield (Bîlteanu, 1993, Ardelean, 2006).

It is demonstrated that after 10 years monocrop, wheat yield decreases continuously in comparative with rotations. It fluctuates as a consequence of changing climatic conditions. Under such circumstances, fertilization does not induce a significant yield increase. A particularly important problem is linked to wheat crop increase, which must fit the rising consumption needs of world population (Domuta, et., al., 2007, 2008, Bandici, Guş, 2001).

Advances in biomass accumulation dynamics in winter wheat in the pedo-climatic conditions of Western Plain of Romania were made (Zăhan, 1989a) during their studies on Transylvanian wheat race.

The influence of fertilization on biomass accumulation in winter wheat was studied. Frequent research put in a direct relationship the phytomass accumulation with the fertilizers that were utilized (Zăhan, 1989b).

The dynamics of the phenomena dealing with winter wheat growth made the object of field research (Domuța, 2012).

The forerunner plant is a decisive factor influencing growth and development of wheat. The role of forerunner plant on wheat growth and development is stressed out by: Zăhan (Zăhan, 1989a).

Forerunner plant together with other appropriate agricultural practices contribute to the favourableness of growth and development conditions of wheat root system, to an improved synthesis of specific organic compounds and their improved translocation to plant's organs (Lazany, 2000; 2003). Finally, all the enumerated conditions lead to improved efficiency per area unit. Plant growth is fundamental in obtaining yield and is related to vegetation and technological factors, the level of yield being reflected in the intensity of production (Dincă, 1971; Bîlteanu, 1993)

In the majority of cases, total growth of green mass is considered on the assumption that a maximum yield is obtained by increasing total production and by a favourable distribution of it among plant's organs (Zăhan, Zăhan, 1989b, Bandici, 1997; 2001). However, roots are not only absorbing water and nutrients from soil but play a key role in plant's general metabolism. Roots harbour the biosynthesis of some essential compounds for the rest of the plant to which they send the biosynthetic products (Zamfirescu, 1977).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research were carried out during 2018-2020 in a long trial placed in 2001 at Agricultural Research and Development Station Oradea. The soil from the research field is a luvosoils characterized by macroaggregates hydrostability of 46.7%, a clay content of 31.5% in Ap

horizon and of 39.8% in Bt horizon; field capacity on watering depth of the winter wheat is of 24.0% (178.7 mm), wilting point is of 9.7% (72.0 mm) and easily available water content is of 19.2% (143.1 mm); on the same depth, the value of the bulk density (1.49 g/cm^3) indicates a low settling, total porosity (49%) is median and hydraulic conductivity is of 12.0 mm/hour.

The presence of the Bt horizon determines the successive appearance of the water excess in the cold season and the first part of the warm season and of the water deficit in the second part of the summer.

Chemical parameters indicate a soil with pH of 6.8, humus content of 1.75%, mobile phosphorus of 22.0 ppm and mobile potassium of 140.4 ppm on the ploughed depth (0-20 cm).

The following device of the experiment was studied.

Factor A: crop rotation:

a₁= winter wheat, monocrop;

a₂= winter wheat-maize;

a₃= pea-winter wheat-maize

a₄= pea-winter wheat-maize-maize

Factor B: nutrition regime:

b₁= N₀P₀

b₂= N₁₂₀P₈₀

b₃= N₁₂₀P₈₀+manure 10 t/ha (applied for every crop).

Number of repetition: 4. Cultivar used: Delia.

Total biomass and separately every plants parts were weighted in the laboratory. The results were analysed with ANOVA (analysis of variance), the biomass being expressed as g. dry weight/10 plants.

a)

b)

Fig. 1 Aspects from research field: a) winter wheat - monocrop ;
b) winter wheat-maize crop rotation

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From the data in Table 1, we notice the fact that until the beginning of the vegetation, the quantity of biomass accumulated in the wheat plants

on phenophases, is even larger as the precursory plant is better, that is 1.94 g. d.s./10 plants in the case of the crop rotation of two years (W-M), and of 2.72 g. d.s./10 plants in the crop rotation of three years (B-W-M), respectively of 3.88 g. d.s./10 plants in the case of the crop rotation of four years (M-G-P-P), compared to the monoculture of 1.70 g. d.s./10 plants.

Along with the advancement in vegetation of the wheat plants, we observe a gradual growth of the quantity of accumulated dry substance, but the quality step regarding the accumulation of biomass is recorded between the phenophase of the elongation of the straw and the phenophase of the formation of wheat spike, a case in which the quantity of accumulated dry substance is even larger as the precursory plant is better (peas), of 32.2 g. d.s./10 plants, compared to the monoculture of wheat (25.43 g. d.s./10 plants), and in the next phenophases the accumulation of dry substances will have a slowed rhythm, until the phenophase of full maturation.

Regarding the quantity of biomass (g. d.s./10 plants) accumulated in the wheat plants under the influence of the mineral and organic-mineral nutrition (table 2), we notice a growth of the dry substance even larger as the fertilization is better, complex organic-mineral (3.32 g. d.s./10 plants), compared to the unfertilized control sample (2.03 g. d.s./10 plants). Also in this case, the quality step of the growth of the biomass was recorded between the phenophase of the elongation of the straw and the phenophase of the formation of wheat spike, the accumulation being even larger as the fertilization level was better (complex, organic-mineral, - 31.64 g. d.s./10 plants), compared to the unfertilized control sample (22.97 g. d.s./10 plants). In the following phenophases until full maturation we notice a slowing of the rhythm of the biomass accumulation.

The data in table 3 point out better the features of the formation of the biomass of autumn wheat. Unlike other species, autumn wheat is characterized in spring by a very high growth rhythm, as in a period of 90 days over 90 % of the total biomass of the plant is realized. In the period previous to the intensive growth (October-March), the wheat plant accumulates only 5.5 % of the total quantity of biomass.

Until the formation of spike, the wheat plant has accumulated 60.4 % of the total biomass, and from this in the period 01. 04 – 15.05, in only 45 days – 54.9 %. It results that in the 45 days before the formation of spike, autumn wheat has the most intense growth rhythm, the plants requesting in this time span a large quantity of water and nourishing elements.

Table 1

The influence of crop rotation plant on total dry biomass (g.d.w./10 plants) in winter wheat cultivated on luvisols (Oradea, Romania 2018-2020)

Crop rotation	Stage															
	1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
1. Winter wheat- monocrop	1.70	100	4.19	100	10.70	100	25.43	100	33.42	100	38.21	100	40.70	100	40.93	100
2. Winter wheat-maize	1.94	114	4.52	108	12.08	113	26.16	103	34.21	103	41.47	109	44.69	110	45.25	111
3. Pea-winter wheat-maize	2.72	156	5.64	135	12.37	116	32.20	127	41.51	124	43.12	113	46.28	114	48.01	117
4. Pea-winter wheat-maize-maize	3.88	228	5.83	139	13.01	122	31.84	125	42.29	127	46.41	121	50.17	123	52.76	129

1. The beginning of the vegetation
2. The formation of the first internode
3. Straw elongation
4. The formation of spike
5. Beginning of seeds formation
6. Early ripening
7. Incomplete ripening
8. Complete ripening

Table 2

The influence of nutrition regime on total dry biomass (g.d.w./10 plants) in winter wheat cultivated on luvisols (Oradea, Romania 2018-2020)

Crop rotation	Stage															
	1		2		3		4		5		6		7		8	
	Total dry biomass															
	Val.	%	Val.	%	Val.	%	Val.	%	Val.	%	Val.	%	Val.	%	Val.	%
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	2.03	100	4.06	100	9.09	100	22.97	100	31.80	100	34.59	100	36.91	100	42.95	100
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	2.33	115	5.08	125	13.11	144	30.65	133	39.91	125	44.29	128	47.22	128	47.92	112
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +manure 10 t/ha	3.32	164	6.01	148	13.95	153	31.64	138	41.82	132	48.04	139	52.22	141	53.13	124

1. The beginning of the vegetation
2. The formation of the first internode
3. Straw elongation
4. The formation of spike
5. Beginning of seeds formation
6. Early ripening
7. Incomplete ripening
8. Complete ripening

Table 3

The influence of the phenophase on the progress of growth of the total biomass of the winter wheat, cultivated on luvisols Oradea, Romania 2018-2020

Phenophase/Date of taking of samples	Dry biomass (g)	% of the total biomass	Growth enhancement (g)	Growth enhancement (%)
At winter beginning	0.53	1.1	-	1.1
At the end of winter	0.95	2.0	0.42	0.9
Beginning of the vegetation	2.56	5.5	1.61	3.5 (5.5)
Formation of the first internode	5.04	10.7	2.48	5.2
Elongation of the straw	12.04	25.6	7.00	14.9
The formation of spike	28.40	60.4	16.36	34.8 (54.9)
Beginning of the formation of the grains	37.86	80.6	9.46	20.2
Maturation in milk	42.28	90.0	4.42	9.4
Maturation in ripening	45.44	96.7	3.16	6.7
Full maturation	46.98	100.0	1.54	3.3 (39.6)

If we analyse the structure of the biomass of autumn wheat, we notice that it shows significant variations, determined by the characteristics of the soil, crop rotation and the nutrition regime of the plants (table 4). Thus, the grain production is currently under 50% of the total production of the plants.

Table 4

The compounds of the winter wheat biomass, depending on the crop rotation and the nutrition regime of winter wheat cultivated on luvisols (Oradea, Romania 2018-2020)

Biological element	% of the total biomass
Root mass	4-9
Straw mass	22-42
Foliar mass	5-10
Grain mass	35-43
Chaff mass	4-14

Analysing the data in table 5, we notice a growth of the wheat production over the monoculture (29.2 q/ha), depending on the rotation, the production being larger as the precursory plant is better, 35.3 q/ha in the case of the rotation W-M (crop rotation 2 years) and of 45.5-45.9 in the case of the crop rotations of 3 and 4 years.

The mineral nutrition regime influences the growth of wheat production, so that over the unfertilized witness (26.1 q/ha), in the case of mineral and organic-mineral fertilization, a production of 43.9 q/ha and respectively of 46.9 q/ha was obtained.

Table 5

The influence of crop rotation, of the mineral and organic-mineral nutrition regime on the production of winter wheat cultivated on luvisols (Oradea, Romania 2018-2020)

Variant	Grains production kg/ha	Grains yield	
		%	
		winter wheat monocrop	winter wheat-maize
a. Rotation			
Winter wheat- monocrop	2920	100	83
Winter wheat-maize	3530	121	100
Pea-winter wheat-maize	4550	156	129
Pea-winter wheat-maize-maize	4590	157	130
b. Nutrition regime			
N ₀ P ₀ (Control)	2610	100	59,0
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀	4390	169	100
N ₁₂₀ P ₈₀ +manure 10 t/ha	4690	180	107

CONCLUSIONS

The results of the research obtained during 2018-2020 in a long term trial with crop rotation (winter wheat- monocrop, winter wheat-maize, pea-winter wheat-maize, pea-winter wheat-maize-maize) and nutrition regime (N_0P_0 ; $N_{120}P_{80}$; $N_{120}P_{80}$ +manure 10 t/ha applied for every crop) determined the following conclusions:

- the biggest quantity of total biomass was determined in the crop rotation pea-winter wheat-maize-maize and the smallest quantity was registered in the winter wheat monocrop in all the stages of the vegetation period. The difference between these variants were of 128% at the beginning of the vegetation, of 39% at the first internode formation, of 22% at straw elongation, of 25% at spike formation, of 26% at the beginning of the seed formation, of 21% at early ripening, of 23% at incomplete ripening and of 29% at complete ripening;

- the nutrition regime had a big influence, too on the total dry biomass. The biggest values were registered in the variant fertilized with $N_{120}P_{80}$ +manure 10 t/ha and the smallest in the variant N_0P_0 . Between these variants a following differences were determined: of 64% at the beginning of the vegetation, of 48% at the formation of the first internode, of 53% at straw elongation; at 38% at the formation of spike; of 32% at beginning of seeds formation, of 39% at early ripening, of 41% at incomplete ripening and of 24% at complete ripening;

- in the total biomass, the grain mass represented 35%-43%, straw mass 22%-42%, chaff mass 4%-14%, foliar mass 5%-10% and root mass represented 4-9%;

- the crop rotation influenced the yield level. The smallest yield was obtained in winter wheat monocrop, 2920 kg/ha. In the other variants the yields obtained were bigger; the differences were of 21% in winter wheat-maize, of 56% in pea-winter wheat-maize and of 57% in pea-winter wheat-maize-maize;

- the nutrition regime influenced very much (2610 kg/ha) the yield level, in comparison with the variant N_0P_0 , the winter wheat yield obtained in the variant with $N_{120}P_{80}$ increased with 69% and in the variant $N_{120}P_{80}$ +manure 10 t/ha with 80%.

The results of the research sustain the importance of the crop rotation (central pivot) and fertilizers, two important components of the sustainable agriculture system.

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THE EVOLUTION OF THE DEGRADATION PROCESSES OF THE PHYSICAL AND CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE SOILS FROM CRIȘURILOR PLAIN IN THE PERIOD 2017 – 2020

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Abstract

This paper aims to study the evolution of complex soil degradation processes in the Crișurilor Plain between 2012 and 2020 and a quantifiable assessment of these processes. Surveys on the identification and mapping of degraded soils were carried out between 2012 - 2017 and 2018 - 2020. The paper continues the studies conducted between 2012 and 2017. Correlation of field data with laboratory analyzes and previously existing scientific information, the soils from the Crișurilor Plain with low fertility potential were identified due to degradation processes and these areas were mapped in order to develop a complex of improvement measures to improve the fertility potential to increase the fertility potential.

Key words: erosion, clogging, compaction, sedimentation, water

INTRODUCTION

Soil degradation is a major environmental problem and there is strong evidence that such processes pose an immediate threat to both biomass and economic yields. The morphological characteristics and physico-chemical properties of the soils are strongly affected by all degradation processes. The total area of the studied soils was 294.229 ha, of which 217.281.1 ha have agricultural or forestry uses. The degradation processes led to a change in time of the physical and chemical properties of the soils from Crișurilor Plain. The intensity of degradation processes, against the background of changing climatic conditions, is due to: rain and wind erosion, primary and secondary compaction, excessive humidity - groundwater or rain, decreased humus reserves and soil nutrient reserve (N; P; K).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The identification of soils degraded by water erosion was performed in the field by direct observations of the intensity of surface erosion processes. The degree of erosion was determined by measurements of the eroded soil layer. The identification of degraded soils by primary compaction and secondary secondary compaction was performed by comparing the bulk density values determined in the laboratory analyzes

with the bulk density classes (for comparison and assessment of compaction was also necessary by particle size analysis). The identification of soils with excess rainfall (stagnant) moisture was performed on the soil by direct observation, based on the existence in the soil profile of the horizons of stagnation (measurable character). The identification of soils with excess groundwater was done in the field, by direct observation, based on the existence in the soil profile of the ice horizons (measurable character). The identification of the soil areas represented by the swamps was done on the field, by direct observation. The identification of soils with low humus content was made by comparing the experimentally determined humus content of the soils of the Crișurilor Plain with the ICPA Norms for the evaluation of the soil supply in humus and organic carbon. The identification of weak and moderately supplied soils in nitrogen was performed by comparing the nitrogen supply of the soils in the Crișurilor Plain with the ICPA Norms for the evaluation of the soil nitrogen supply.

The identification of weak and moderately phosphorus and potassium supplied soils was performed by comparing the phosphorus and potassium supply of the soils of the Crișuri Plain with the ICPA Norms for the evaluation of the phosphorus and potassium supply of the soil.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soils of the Crisului Plain degraded by water erosion

Water erosion takes place on lands located on relief units with inclination angles (inclined relief units).

Water surface. Occurs during torrential rains when the soil cannot store all the water, the surplus flows to the soil surface, causing the transport of soil material from the top of the slope and its deposition at the base of the slopes.

Together with the soil material, the existing nutrients are washed on top of the soil.

The localities and soil units affected by the surface water erosion processes are:

- Leș, Nojorid, Miersig, Sepreș, Bocsig with Cambisol Eutric
- Leș, Nojorid, Cheresig, Miersig, Ianoșda, Husasău de Tinca, Gurbediu, Călăcea, Olcea, Apateu, Sepreș, Cermei, Craiva with Haplic Luvisols.

Compared to 2017, in 2020 there is an increase in soil surfaces due to surface erosion, in the localities of Avram Iancu, Tălmaci, Ineu, Păușa, Girișul de Criș, Berechiu, Miersig, Husasău de Tinca. The increase is mainly due to the increase in the frequency of torrential rains and hill - valley plowing. Plowing on contour lines and overturning the furrow

upstream would slow down the erosion process. Also making grass strips and terracing are recommended methods to stop erosion.

Deep erosion. It is rarely found in Crișurilor Plain (in some of the high areas of Crișurilor Plain), it is the result of drained rainwater runoff on certain routes, which causes the entrainment of large amounts of soil material. In the area of Crișuri Plain, it is manifested on narrow surfaces, being specific to the High Plain.

Fig. 1. Crișurilor Plain. Representation of soil surfaces subject to or affected by water erosion in 2017 and 2020

The soils in the Plain are degraded by secondary compaction

Compaction is a form of degradation of the hydrophysical and aeration properties of soils that formed naturally during the soil formation process or as a result of anthropogenic activity.

Figure 2 shows the land area with secondary compaction, at the level of 2017 and 2020.

Secondary compaction

It is a process of degradation of the hydrophysical characteristics of soils due to human activity, mainly due to intensive use in agriculture and is manifested by the worsening of the aerohydric regime and the manifestation of nutritional disorders in plants. One of the causes of primary compaction is the practice of monoculture, crop rotation is practiced only in agricultural units with large areas of land. Individual producers practice monoculture intensively, due to the small areas of land they have. In Crișurilor Plain, they are affected by the secondary compaction of some soils located in areas

where mechanized agriculture is predominantly practiced, in the area of localities: Tămășeu, Hodoș, Sălard, Santău Mic, Bors, Palota, Tărian, Cihei, Nojorid, Sânicolau Român, Roit, Berechiu, Gepiu, Cefa, Leș, Miersig, Mădăras, Salonta, Gurbediu, Ciumeghiu, Avram Iancu, Călacea, Craiva, Cermei, Sepreuș, Beliu, Ineu, Șicula, Seleuș, Bocsig, Olari, Șimand, Macea, Avram Iancu. Compared to 2017, there is an increase in areas.

Fig. 2 The land area secondary compaction, at the level of 2017 and 2020

The soils in the Crișului Plain with excess moisture from rainfall

In the Plains of Criss, the excess rainfall of moisture is manifested on an area of over 18,847 ha, occupied by the type of soil stagnic soils. Representative surfaces of stagnic soils are found on surfaces, flat or slightly inclined, in the depression areas, in the area of Girișu de Criș, Talpoș, Ghiorac, Tamasda, Zerindu Mic, Vânători, Sepreuș, Oradea, Sânmartin, Cihei, Chișirid, Apateu, Gurbediu, Husasau of Tinca, Bicaci, Gurbediu, Inand, Vasile Goldiș, Avram Iancu, Coroi, Talmaci, Sosag, Berechiu. On smaller surfaces are found in luvisols and planosols. Figure 3 shows the distribution of stagnic soils in the Crișuri Plain.

At the level of 2020, there is a decrease of the areas affected by the temporary excess moisture from precipitations, due to the deficient pluviometric regime.

Fig. 3. Crișurilor Plain. Areas occupied by stagnant soils (2020) and the downward trend of areas due to poor rainfall (red)

The soils of the Crișului Plain with excess of ground water

The soils affected by the excess groundwater are the gleysols, occupying in the Crișurilor Plain a total area of 15,342 ha. The major areas are found in low meadows with groundwater at a critical depth of 1-2 m in Borș, Santău Mic, Santău Mare, Toboliu, Sântion, Mihai Bravu, Parhida, Inand, Satu Nou, Tămasu, Tulca, Ghiorac, Cefa, Inand, Homorog, Salonta, Ciumeghiu, Avram Iancu, Biharia, etc. Figure 5 shows the distribution of gleyosols in the Crișuri Plain. Compared to 2017, between 2017 and 2020, due to the deficient rainfall regime, the groundwater level was at minimum levels, without affecting agricultural crops. A 10% decrease in groundwater areas is estimated to fall. In the Crișuri Plain, in some low areas, the existence of the aquifer close to the surface, at depths less than 1 m, led to the formation of large areas of swamp, about 1200 ha, most of which are currently transformed and improved as ponds. : in Cepha (670ha), Inand Lake (200ha), Madaras (30ha), Homorog (105ha), Tamasda (206ha), Crisul Alb lakes (Bocsig, Ineu, Seleus), Cermei lake in Teuzu basin, Cigher, Socodor Lake (155ha), Pilu Lake (260ha). The low rainfall regime from 2017 to 2020, correlated with the decrease of the groundwater level led to the decrease of the areas occupied by the swamps by approximately 400 ha.

Fig. 4. The area occupied by gleysols and the tendency of decreasing the surfaces affected by the groundwater level

Soil humus reserve

Compared to 2012 at the level of 2020, there is a sharp decrease in the humus reserve in all soil units in Cîmpa Crișurilor. Due to the intensive cultivation of the soil, the monoculture, the lack of organic fertilizers, led to a continuous decrease of the humus reserve of the soils. The continuous decrease of humus reserve was due to the specific consumption of crops, unilateral fertilization, widespread use of chemical fertilizers, lack of organic fertilizers (Sandor, 2007).. Table 1 presents the humus reserve of some soils on the depth of 0 - 50 cm of the Crișuri Plain and the interpretation depending on the texture for the period 2012 - 2017 and the period 2017-2020.

For the types of stagnant soil and gleysol, there was a stagnation of the raw humus reserve (gleysol - Tulcea - 4.78% humus, stagnant soil - Callacea - 3.92%) the processes of humification of organic matter being slowed by the climate (high temperatures and lack of water in the soil) (Ciobanu and Domuța, 2003).

Table 1.

The evolution of the humus content and of the reserve, at the level of 2020 compared to 2017, for some soils from Crişurilor Plain

Soil Type	Locality	Texture	Humus (%) 2017	Humus (%) 2020
Luvic Chernozems	Sânmartin	LN	2.12	1.96
Haplic Chernozems	Livada de Bihor	LN	2.2	1.82
Greyic Phaeoyems	Nojorid	LL	1.55	1.36
Greyic Phaeoyems	Nojorid	LN	2.1	1.88
Eutric Fluvisols	Toboliu	LL	1.8	1.68
Eutric Cambisols	Sălard	LL	1.7	1.54
Haplic Luvisols	Palota	LL	1.76	1.62
Haplic Luvisols	Tulca	LL	1.1	0.90
Haplic Planosols	Ciuhoi	SF	1.64	1.46
Haplic Solonetz	Zerind	AL	1.32	1.18

Soil Type	Locality	Reserve (0-50 cm) tons/ha 2017	Reserve (0-50 cm) tons/ha 2020	Interpretation
Luvic Chernozems	Sânmartin	238.5	132.2	average content
Haplic Chernozems	Livada de Bihor	247.5	127.4	average content
Greyic Phaeoyems	Nojorid	96.87	95.3	small content.
Greyic Phaeoyems	Nojorid	131.25	131.6	average content
Eutric Fluvisols	Toboliu	112.5	117.6	small content.
Eutric Cambisols	Sălard	106.25	107.8	small content.
Haplic Luvisols	Palota	110	113.4	small content.
Haplic Luvisols	Tulca	71.5	63.0	small content.
Haplic Planosols	Ciuhoi	106.6	102.2	small content.
Haplic Solonetz	Zerind	85.8	82.6	small content.

Soils from Crişurilor Plain with low and medium nitrogen content

The chemical analyzes performed on the soils from Crişurilor Plain showed values of nitrogen intake between 5.2 ppm and 9.6 ppm for the period 2012-2017, which correspond to a low to moderate intake. For the period 2017-2020, a decrease of the ratio was found by approximately 0.4 units. Table 2 compares the nitrogen contribution at the level of 2017 and 2020, in the arable layer of some soil types from Crişurilor Plain and the interpretation according to the real acidity (pH).

Table 2

The evolution of the nitrogen content in the arable layer of certain types of soils from Crișurilor Plain during 2017 - 2020 and the effective acidity (pH).

Soil Type	Locality	pH	N – NH ₄ ⁺ + N – NO ₃ ⁻ (ppm) 2017	N – NH ₄ ⁺ + N – NO ₃ ⁻ (ppm) 2020	Interpretation
Luvic Chernozems	Sânmartin	6.65	8.3	7.9	average content
Haplic Chernozems	Livada de Bihor	6.6	9.6	8.6	average content
Greyce Phaeoyems	Nojorid	6.4	7.4	6.8	average content
Greyce Phaeoyems	Nojorid	6.5	7.9	7.2	average content
Eutric Fluvisols	Toboliu	6.4	6.6	6.1	average content
Eutric Cambisols	Sălard	6.3	5.7	5.8	small content.
Haplic Luvisols	Palota	6.4	5.6	5.2	small content.
Haplic Luvisols	Tulca	6.1	5.2	4.8	small content.
Haplic Planosols	Ciuhoi	6.2	5.2	4.9	small content.
Haplic Solonetz	Zerind	8.4	6.9	6.2	small content.

Figure 5 shows the areas with soils with low and moderate nitrogen content and the areas where the decrease in nitrogen content took place (for the period 2017 - 2020)

Fig. 5 The areas with soils with low and moderate nitrogen content and the areas where the decrease in nitrogen content took place (for the period 2017 - 2020)

Soils from Crişurilor Plain with low and moderate phosphorus and potassium content

Following the analysis of the phosphorus content in the soil in the Crisului Plain, values between 6 and 36 ppm in phosphorus were obtained, values corresponding to a very low to medium supply state in 2017. For 2020, there is a decrease of about 1.3 - 4.2 units. Most have a phosphorus content in the range of 4-16 ppm, corresponding to a very poor and poor supply state.

Fig. 6 The areas of the Crisului Plain with medium and low phosphorus content and the evolution in the period 2017 – 2021

In order to evaluate the potassium content of the soils in Crişurilor Plain, analyzes were performed on the potassium content of soils. At the level of 2017, the values were between 60 and 132 ppm, most of them presenting values in the range 60 -110, corresponding to a small to medium supply. For 2021, there is a decrease in content by 10 to 15 units.

Table 3

The phosphorus and potassium content in the arable layer of some soil types in the Crișurilor Plain and the interpretation at the level of 2017 and 2021

Soil Type	Locality	ppm P-2017	ppm P-2020	Interpretation
Luvic Chernozems	Sânmartin	28	24,6	average content
Haplic Chernozems	Livada de Bihor	19.7	17.5	average content
Greyic Phaeoyems	Nojorid	17.7	15.3	small content.
Greyic Phaeoyems	Nojorid	16.9	14.7	small content.
Eutric Fluvisols	Toboliu	15.8	13.4	small content.
Eutric Cambisols	Sălard	13.2	11.7	small content.
Haplic Luvisols	Palota	12.1	10.7	small content.
Haplic Luvisols	Tulca	9.4	7.2	small content.
Haplic Planosols	Ciuhoi	8.6	7.1	small content.
Haplic Solonetz	Zerind	6.1	5.2	very small content
Dystric Gleysols	Toboliu	14.5	11.9	small content.
Stagnic Luvisols	Călăcea	9.2	7.6	small content.

Soil Type	Locality	ppm K-2017	ppm K-2020	Interpretation
Luvic Chernozems	Sânmartin	120	115	average content
Haplic Chernozems	Livada de Bihor	110	95	average content
Greyic Phaeoyems	Nojorid	110	95	average content
Greyic Phaeoyems	Nojorid	105	90	average content
Eutric Fluvisols	Toboliu	90	80	average content
Eutric Cambisols	Sălard	65	55	small content.
Haplic Luvisols	Palota	60	50	small content.
Haplic Luvisols	Tulca	55	45	small content.
Haplic Planosols	Ciuhoi	60	50	small content.
Haplic Solonetz	Zerind	55	45	small content.
Dystric Gleysols	Toboliu	60	45	small content.
Stagnic Luvisols	Călăcea	65	45	small content.

Fig. 7. The soil areas in the Crișurilor Plain with low and medium potassium content, at the level of 2017 and 2021

Restoring degraded soils is crucial to stop the expanding footprint of land degradation and feed our growing human population. To return degraded landscapes to productivity, sandy soils must first be improved to enhance water and nutrient holding capacity (Menzies Pluera et al., 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

The studies and research carried out in the Crișurilor Plain constitute a real basis for solving some problems less studied or neglected so far regarding:

- obtaining and making maps on: soil characteristics, soil technology indicators and maps on production capacity;
- conservation and rational use of the entire land fund;
- knowledge of soils affected by erosion and establishment of anti-erosion measures for the capitalization of these lands;
- knowledge of soil surfaces affected by excess rainfall or groundwater;
- knowledge of soils degraded due to agricultural activities;
- knowledge of the soil areas affected by the decrease in humus and nutrient reserves
- improvement of soils affected by excess rain or flood moisture;
- organization of the territory and design of land improvement works;
- the correct application of the different agrotechnical units in the agricultural units by correlating the physico-chemical characteristics of the soil with the requirements of the crop plants.
- monitoring the evolution over time of the main soil trophicity indicators.
- performing crop maintenance works by correlating the N, P, K content of the soil, with the requirements of crop plants.
- raising the degree of soil trophicity
- crop rotation, as a measure of achieving an optimal ratio between nutrient consumption, to avoid imbalances due to preferential consumption (in the case of monoculture).
- differentiated application of cultivation technologies, in relation to the plant and the type of soil.

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THE EFFECT OF THE NITROGEN PHOSPHORUS AND POTASSIUM FERTILIZER UPON SOME ELEMENTS OF THE WINTER WHEAT CROP

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Abstract

The paper presents the experimental results obtained during 2018 – 2020, regarding the effect of the chemical fertilizer with nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, upon some of the elements of the winter wheat crop, grown in the pedo – climatic conditions of Inand region, Bihor county.

Key words: chemical fertilizers, winter wheat, degree of fraternity/unity, number of brathers, the length of the straw, the length of the ear, the weight of the ear.

INTRODUCTION

The wheat is the most important cultivated plant, with a main food importance. The large areas where it is growing as well as the attention paid to it are due to the carbon hydrate and protein contents of the grains and the ratio of there substances, in relation to the human body demands; the long – term period the grains can be preserved and the fact they can easily be transported; the plants present a high ecological plasticity, being cultivated in region of different climate and type of soil; the possibility of wholly – mechanized growing (Bîlteanu, 2003). The work “The effect of the nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium fertilizer upon some elements of the winter wheat crop” contributes to the fact of knowing the real possibilities of production increase. Fertilizer appliance is also of the measures that can increase the production potential of the cultivated soil. The intensifying of the use of fertilizer for the winter wheat is because of the fact that, as a result of the development of the chemical industry in our country, there are more opportunities of using larger quantities, as well as of the fact that there have been created winter wheat types which very well use the applied fertilizers.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experiment with the chemical fertilizers which took place in Inand region, Bihor county during 2018 – 2020 followed the influence of the nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium fertilizer used in different dosages as

follows: with no fertilizer, N₉₆P₉₆, P₆₄N₃₂, P₆₄N₆₄, P₆₄N₉₆, N₉₆P₉₆K₄₀, N₉₆P₆₄K₄₀, N₆₄P₆₄K₄₀, N₉₆P₃₂, N₉₆ – applied in spring.

The fertilizers used were as follows: ammonium nitrate, superphosphate and potassium salt. The fertilizers were applied in autumn in the same time the soil was prepared, except for the last variant, for which the fertilizers were applied when winter ended. The experiment was placed using the linear method, in four repetitions. The witness used during the experiment was the first variant, for which the chemical fertilizers were not used. The quantities of fertilizers used for each of the variants were:

with no fertilizers, superphosphate 400 kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 100 kg/ha, superphosphate 400kg/ha, superphosphate 400 kg/ha, superphosphate 400 kg/ha, superphosphate 400kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 100kg/ha, superphosphate 400 kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 100 kg/ha, superphosphate, 400 kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 100 kg/ha, superphosphate 400 kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 100 kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 300 kg/ha, superphosphate 600kg/ha, potassium salt 100kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 300 kg/ha, superphosphate 400 kg/ha, potassium salt 100 kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 200 kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 200 kg/ha, superphosphate 400 kg/ha, potassium salt 100 kg/ha, ammonium nitrate 300 kg/ha.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results regarding the winter wheat unity at the chemical fertilizer experiment are shown in table no 1, table no 2 and table no 3.

It can be noticed that during the first year of experiment, 2018, the number of productive brothers varied between 2,02 for the variant with no fertilizers and 3,90 for the variant which received the largest quantity of N₉₆P₉₆K₄₀ fertilizer.

The same thing can be noticed during the second year, 2019, the number of productive brothers varied between 243 for the variant with no fertilizer and 4.54 for the variant with the largest quantity of fertilizer. In the third year of the experiment, 2020, the number of productive brothers varied between 2.38 for the variant with no fertilizer and 3.68 for the variant with the largest quantity of fertilizer. It can also be noticed that the number of brothers was bigger for the variant with a larger quantity of nitrogen used in spring, at the beginning of growing. When taking into account the variants which received fertilizers in different quantities, there can not be noticed too much difference as concerns the unity degree.

As concerns the total number of the brother produced by each winter wheat plant until the bearing of winter and in spring until the end of unity, the data are presented in table no 2. It can be noticed that until the winter

begins, the N₆₄P₆₄K₄₀, variant developed with 90.4% more brothers than the variant with no fertilizers. In the case of the other variants the number of brothers increased by 47 – 71%. By the end of the period of unity the variants P₆₄N₆₄ and N₉₆P₉₆K₄₀ developed the largest number of brothers 97.6%, more than the variant without fertilizer.

Table 1

The influence of the chemical fertilizer upon the unity degree at the winter wheat

Year	Variant	Number of productive brothers			
		x	s	s %	s-x
2018	With no fertilizer	2.02	1.24	61.3	0.124
	P ₆₄ N ₃₂	2.40	1.00	41.7	0.100
	P ₆₄ N ₆₄	3.50	1.56	44.5	0.156
	P ₆₄ N ₉₆	3.24	1.27	38.8	0.127
	N ₉₆ P ₃₂	2.90	1.03	35.5	0.103
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆	3.70	1.67	45.1	0.167
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	3.90	1.34	34.3	0.134
	N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	3.38	1.15	34.0	0.115
	N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	3.36	1.17	34.8	0.117
N ₉₆ -applied in spring	3.36	1.43	42.5	0.143	
2019	With no fertilizer	2.43	1.21	49.8	0.121
	P ₆₄ N ₃₂	3.30	1.11	33.6	0.111
	P ₆₄ N ₆₄	3.25	1.03	31.7	0.103
	P ₆₄ N ₉₆	3.17	1.18	37.2	0.118
	N ₉₆ P ₃₂	3.41	1.10	32.2	0.110
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆	4.40	1.53	35.0	0.153
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	4.54	1.64	36.1	0.164
	N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	3.05	1.12	36.7	0.112
	N ₆₄ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	4.27	1.42	33.2	0.142
N ₉₆ - applied in spring	3.18	1.05	33.0	0.105	
2020	With no fertilizer	2.38	1.17	49.1	0.117
	P ₆₄ N ₃₂	2.56	1.12	43.7	0.112
	P ₆₄ N ₆₄	2.62	1.21	46.9	0.121
	P ₆₄ N ₉₆	2.70	1.10	40.7	0.110
	N ₉₆ P ₃₂	2.44	1.67	68.8	0.167
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆	3.32	1.34	40.3	0.134
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	3.68	1.14	32.9	0.114
	N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	2.80	1.28	44.1	0.128
	N ₆₄ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	3.10	1.42	45.8	0.142
N ₉₆ - applied in spring	2.50	1.05	42.0	0.105	

Table 2

Total number the beginning of winter and up to the end of unity period, for the winter wheat

Variant	Date of establishing					
	20.12		4. 03		24.03	
	Number of brothers	%	Number of brothers	%	Number of brothers	%
With no fertilizer	2.1	100.0	3.0	100.0	4.2	100.0
P ₆₄ N ₃₂	3.2	152.2	4.9	163.3	7.1	169.0
P ₆₄ N ₆₄	3.5	157.1	5.3	176.6	8.3	197.6
P ₆₄ N ₉₆	3.2	152.3	6.4	213.3	6.8	161.9
N ₉₆ P ₃₂	3.3	157.1	4.4	146.6	7.7	183.3
N ₉₆ P ₉₆	3.6	171.4	5.5	183.3	7.9	188.0
N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	3.1	147.6	5.8	193.3	8.3	197.6
N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	3.3	157.1	4.7	156.6	7.0	190.4
N ₆₄ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	4.0	190.4	6.5	216.6	6.8	161.9
N ₉₆ - applied in spring	2.1	100.0	3.0	100.0	4.9	116.6

It can be noticed the variants that received a big quantity of N96 nitrogen in spring, which produced a number of 2.8 brothers in spring, which represents 16.6% compared to the witness which was not fertilized.

The most important is not the number of brothers which can be formed under the influence of the chemical fertilizers, but the number of productive brothers which grow to make an ear.

Even if, out the total number of brothers, about 50%, appear in autumn and the rest of 50%, in spring less than 50% of the total number of brothers reach maturity. It should also be noticed the variant for which the nitrogen was applied in spring, at the beginning of vegetation, that presents a higher percentage of productive brothers compared to the total number of brothers formed on the plant 67.3%. This leads to the conclusions that the application of a certain quantity of nitrogen in spring at the beginning of the winter wheat period of vegetation stimulates, the growth of the brothers formed in autumn, that make an ear in a higher proportion.

The results regarding the influence of the chemical fertilizer upon the length of the straw are shown in table no 4, and table no 5. Generally speaking, in the case of grains there is a close relationship between the length of the straw and the resistance of plants when falling. The shorter and thicker an ear is, the higher resistance at falling. Plants falling is one of the most harmful phenomena which can appear during the vegetation period. It can be seen in table no 4 that during the there years of experimenting, for the

variant with no fertilizer, the length of the straw was smaller compared to the fertilized variants. The data in table no 5 show that, compared to the witness with no fertilizer, at the fertilized variants the plants length grew with a percentage of up to 77.7 %. That was. When winter began, the height of the plants at the fertilized variants was bigger than the variant with no fertilizer, the difference varying between 27.4% and 62.7%. For all the cases, we can see that when the dosage of fertilizer was small the height growth varied between 16.6% and 27.4%, while for the variants which received two or three dosages of nitrogen fertilizer, the height growth varied between 69.6% - 67.5%. It can also be noticed the positive influence of the nitrogen applied in spring upon the growth. Generally speaking the height growing of the plants is positively influenced by the chemical fertilizers, especially by the nitrogen fertilizer.

The increase of nitrate fertilizer dosage can lead to the increase of the plants height with up to 52% compared to plants cultivated without fertilizer but the resistance to falling decreases, in the same time

Table 3

The ratio between the number of brothers, formed in autumn of in spring and the number of productive brothers

Variant	Total number of brothers	Brothers made in autumn		Brothers made in spring		Productive brothers	
	x	x	%	x	%	x	%
With no fertilizer	4.2	2.1	50.0	2.1	50.0	2.0	47.2
P ₆₄ N ₃₂	7.1	3.2	45.1	3.9	54.9	2.4	33.8
P ₆₄ N ₆₄	8.3	3.3	39.8	5.0	60.2	3.5	42.1
P ₆₄ N ₉₆	6.8	3.2	47.1	3.6	52.9	3.2	47.0
N ₉₆ P ₃₂	7.7	3.3	42.9	4.4	57.1	2.9	37.6
N ₉₆ P ₉₆	7.9	3.6	45.6	4.3	54.4	3.7	46.8
N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	8.3	3.1	37.4	5.2	62.6	3.9	46.9
N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	7.8	3.3	52.6	3.7	47.4	3.4	48.5
N ₆₄ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	6.8	4.0	58.9	2.8	41.4	3.3	48.8
N ₉₆ - applied in spring	4.9	2.1	42.9	2.8	57.1	3.3	67.3

Table 4

The influence of the chemical fertilizers upon the straw`s length for the winter wheat

Year	Variant	Lenght of straw (cm)			
		x	s	s%	s-x
2018	With no fertilizer	77.2	7.9	10.2	0.79
	P ₆₄ N ₃₂	90.2	10.1	11.1	0.01
	P ₆₄ N ₆₄	93.5	11.1	11.8	1.11
	P ₆₄ N ₉₆	93.6	9.8	10.4	0.98
	N ₉₆ P ₃₂	95.4	8.4	8.8	0.84
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆	97.2	5.3	5.4	0.53
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	96.3	5.5	5.7	0.55
	N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	102.1	8.6	8.4	0.86
	N ₆₄ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	96.5	4.0	4.1	0.40
N ₉₆ - applied in spring	92.1	8.1	8.7	0.81	
2019	With no fertilizer	70.9	5.3	7.4	0.53
	P ₆₄ N ₃₂	95.7	4.8	5.0	0.48
	P ₆₄ N ₆₄	95.8	5.5	5.7	0.55
	P ₆₄ N ₉₆	96.8	6.9	7.1	0.69
	N ₉₆ P ₃₂	88.3	5.2	5.9	0.52
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆	93.1	10.7	11.4	1.07
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	98.4	5.6	5.7	0.56
	N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	98.8	4.1	4.2	0.41
	N ₆₄ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	99.5	6.1	6.1	0.61
N ₉₆ - applied in spring	87.4	9.2	10.5	0.92	
2020	With no fertilizer	117.6	6.8	5.7	0.68
	P ₆₄ N ₃₂	125.1	7.6	6.0	0.76
	P ₆₄ N ₆₄	124.8	9.7	8.0	0.97
	P ₆₄ N ₉₆	123.9	10.1	8.1	1.01
	N ₉₆ P ₃₂	118.5	6.4	5.4	0.64
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆	114.5	5.2	4.5	0.52
	N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	124.0	6.1	4.9	0.61
	N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	120.3	8.8	7.3	0.88
	N ₆₄ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	121.5	6.5	5.3	0.65
N ₉₆ - applied in spring	116.9	8.4	7.1	0.84	

Table 5

The influence of the nitrogen chemical fertilizer upon the rate of height growing for the winter wheat

Variant		Date of measurement				
		20.12	4.03	24.03	10.04	28.04
With no fertilizer	cm	10.2	15.9	18.8	18.8	47.8
	%	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0	100.0
P ₆₄ N ₃₂	cm	13.0	19.0	21.0	22.4	58.5
	%	127.4	119.4	116.6	119.1	122.4
P ₆₄ N ₆₄	cm	14.0	21.9	21.8	31.5	70.0
	%	137.3	137.7	121.1	167.5	148.5
P ₆₄ N ₉₆	cm	16.6	21.1	25.9	31.9	68.0
	%	162.7	132.7	143.8	169.6	146.4
N ₉₆ P ₃₂	cm	16.0	22.3	23.6	28.6	67.0
	%	156.8	140.2	131.1	152.1	144.7
N ₉₆ P ₉₆	cm	15.0	23.7	25.5	31.9	69.0
	%	147.0	149.0	141.6	169.6	148.5
N ₉₆ P ₉₆ K ₄₀	cm	15.2	24.4	26.1	31.2	72.6
	%	149.0	153.6	133.6	166.0	151.8
N ₉₆ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	cm	15.0	22.4	25.7	33.4	72.9
	%	147.0	140.8	142.7	177.7	152.5
N ₆₄ P ₆₄ K ₄₀	cm	15.7	21.3	29.4	32.3	68.5
	%	153.8	1345.0	163.0	171.8	147.4
N ₉₆ - applied in spring	cm	10.2	17.0	18.7	24.7	68.2
	%	100.0	107.0	103.9	131.0	146.8

CONCLUSIONS

Following the experiments which took place between 2018 – 2020, regarding the effect of the application of chemical fertilizers upon certain elements of the winter wheat crop, these conclusions can be drawn.

The fertilizers positively influence the elements of nitrogen fertilizer influence the unity degree, beforehand. Large numbers of productive brothers are assured by means of fertilizing the plants with nitrogen, in spring, at the beginning of vegetation.

The length of the straw is also related to the degree of nitrogen used in the soil larger dosages of nitrogen fertilizer can lead to an increase of the height with about 52% compared to the plants cultivated on the soil not fertilized, but in the same time, the resistance towards falling lessens.

It can be noticed that during the experimental years the variant with no fertilizer registered the shortest height of the ear 5,40 cm in 2018, 5,32 cm an in 2019 and 6,61 cm in 2020.

The weight of the ear was directly proportional to its length, the smallest being registered at the variant with no fertilizer.

The nitrogen fertilizers help the growing of a more numerous number of grains in the ear and there is a positive connection between the length of the ear and the number of grains in the ear, because for the same variant, P₆₄N₉₆, the ear was the longest and the most numerous number of grains were registered.

For the pedo – climatic conditions of Inand region, during the 3 years of experiments, the application of the chemical fertilizers at the winter wheat showed positive effects upon the grain production per hectare.

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PRODUCTIVITY STUDY OF SORGHUM VULGARE HYBRIDS IN INAND, BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

The evolution of research in the field of sorghum for grains has led to the creation of new hybrids with higher production potential and resistance to various diseases and pests. Sorghum cultivation technology is similar to that of corn. Sorghum has an explosive emergence at higher temperatures, early May where sowing at densities between 250.000 and 300.000 germinating grains/ hectare bring important yields.

Key words: sorghum, hybrid, sowing season, production

INTRODUCTION

Sorghum is a plant considered as an alternative to corn cultivation in conditions of global warming. This plant has the ability to withstand high summer temperatures having even significant yields even in conditions of water stress.

Sorghum cultivation technology involves lower production costs than corn. Sorghum has the ability to capitalize very well on soil resources, especially mineral nitrogen and is also a plant resistant to diseases and pests.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In 2020 we studied 5 sorghum hybrids, 3 Armorik, Moussone and Alizee hybrids from Euralis Semences France and 2 Arsenio and Lupus hybrids from KWS Germany. I sowed 2 experiments in 3 repetitions, the harvestable surface of the parcel being 10m², at a distance of 70 cm between rows and a density of 300,000 plants / ha in 2 sowing seasons, the first season April 15-April 30 and the 2nd season 1 May-May 15.

For the preparation of the germination bed, a plowing was performed at 22-25 cm then I made a passage with a disc harrow at 8-10 cm, and before sowing I performed a work with the combine to give quality to the germination bed, a good crushing and leveling.

Fertilization was performed in phases with the fertilization dose being N₁₀₁P₆₈K₄₈.

The first stage was applied under plowing, 300 kg of complex fertilizers 16.16.16., the second application of fertilizers was performed at sowing 100 kg of complex fertilizers 20.20.0, and the third application was performed at mechanical weeding 100 kg of azote.

For the weed control, a pre-emergent herbicide was performed with Dual Gold 980 EC 1.2 l / ha, the seeds being treated with Concept III, a "safener" type substance that protects the sorghum plant at sunrise from the action of the antigramine herbicide Dual Gold 980 EC.

At the 3-leaf stage of the sorghum plant, a post-emergent herbicide was performed with Casper 0.4 kg / ha.

The maintenance work of the paths was done with the cultivator.

Herbicides and phytosanitary treatments were carried out with the spraying plant worn.

Harvesting was done with a grain combine at a humidity of 14%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In table 1 we have presented the productions of sorghum hybrids on the parcel of 10 m² in two sowing seasons (PR1, PR2, PR3) at the harvest humidities (UMID 1, 2 AND 3). The productions per hectare brought to the humidity of 15 are then calculated, 5% (R1 pr / ha, R2 pr / ha, R3 pr / ha). On the last column of the table we have the average of the repetitions.

Table 1
Sorghum productions registered in 2020 for 5 sorghum hybrids

EXP epoch	HYBRID	PR1	PR2	PR3	UMID1	UMID2	UMID3	R1 pr /ha	R2 Pr/ha	R3 Pr/ha	TOTAL Average
	ARMORIK	7	7.2	6.9	16.3	16.5	16.1	6934	7115	6851	6967
	MOUSSONE	8.1	8	8.3	16.6	16.5	16.7	7995	7905	8182	8027
1	ALIZEE	7.9	8.2	8	16.5	16.7	16.5	7807	8084	7905	7932
April	ARSENIO	7.1	7.3	7.2	15.8	16.1	15.9	7075	7248	7166	7163
	LUPUS	6.8	7.1	6.9	16.1	16.3	16.1	6752	7033	6851	6879
	ARMORIK	7.3	7.5	7.4	16.4	16.6	16.5	7222	7402	7312	7312
	MOUSSONE	8.4	8.3	8.6	16.4	16.4	16.7	8311	8212	8478	8333
2	ALIZEE	8.5	8.4	8.4	16.9	16.7	16.8	8359	8281	8271	8304
May	ARSENIO	7.8	7.6	7.7	15.7	15.5	15.7	7782	7600	7682	7688
	LUPUS	7.2	7.3	7.1	16.4	16.6	16.2	7123	7205	7041	7123

PR1,PR2,PR3= productions / parcel repetitions 1,2 and 3

UMID1,UMID2,UMID3= humidity at repetitions 1,2 and 3

R1 pr/ha,R2 pr/ha,R3 pr/ha =productions per hectare of repetitions 1,2 and 3

Total average = average of the 3 repetitions per hectare.

Figure 1 shows the productions per hectare of sorghum hybrids, sowing season April 15-30, the highest production was recorded for the Mousson sorghum hybrid 8072 kg / ha followed by Alizee 7932 kg / ha with 2% lower production than Mousson, Arsenio 7163 kg / ha with 11% lower production than Mousson and the last two with yields below 7000kg, Armorik 6967 kg / ha and Lupus 6879 kg / ha with 14% and 15% lower production.

Fig 1. Variation of production per hectare of sorghum hybrids, sowing season 15-30 April.

Figure 2 shows the productions per hectare of sorghum hybrids, sowing season 1-15 May, the highest production was also recorded for the Mousson hybrid 8333 kg / ha, followed by Alizee 8304kg / ha with 0.5% higher production lower than Mousson, Arsenio 7688kg / ha production by 8% lower than Mousson, Armorik 7312 kg / ha and Lupus 7123kg / ha production lower by 12% respectively 15%.

Fig 2 Variation of production per hectare of sorghum hybrids, sowing season May 1-15

Figure 3 shows the variation of production in the two sowing seasons where we can see that the best productions were recorded in the sowing season May 1-15

Fig 3 Variation of productions in the 2 sowing seasons

Figure 4 shows the productions of each hybrid in the 2 sowing seasons as well as the difference in percentage of production increases recorded in the sowing season 1-15 May compared to the sowing season April 15-30.

For the Armorik hybrid in May, a production increase of 4.9% compared to April was obtained, for the Mousson hybrid an increase of 3.2%, Alizee 4.6% and for Arsenio and Lupus increases by 7.3% respectively 3.2%.

Fig 4. The difference in production in percentages in the 2 sowing seasons

CONCLUSIONS

The most productive sorghum hybrid is Mousson, at which the highest yields were obtained in both sowing seasons 8072kg / ha in the period 15-30 April respectively 8333kg / ha in the period 1-15 May, followed by Alizee 7932 and 8304 kg / ha, Arsenio 7163 and 7688 kg / ha, Armorik 6967 and 7312 kg / ha and Lupus 6879 and 7123 kg / ha.

The best time for sowing is May 1-15, when higher yields were obtained for all hybrids, at Armorik 4.9% more than in April, Mousson 3.2% Alizee 4.6%, Arsenio 7.3% and Lupus 3.2%. The hybrid with the highest production increase is Arsenio 7.3%

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SOME ASPECTS OF HYDROGEN UTILIZATION IN AGRICULTURE

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Abstract

The pressure to produce more food and less pollution has led to the need for identification of applicable solutions, to solve, to improve the sustainability of production processes and accelerate innovation in the agriculture industry. These solutions based on the technical revolution can be characterized by the Farming 4.0 concept.

One of the main issues to be addressed for effective environmental protection and sustainable production is the abandonment of the use of fossil fuels. One possible solution is to use hydrogen through Hydrogen Fuel Cells (HFC).

This article gives a brief overview of the achievements based on the use of HFCs in agriculture and tries to synthesize the main future directions.

Key words: hydrogen, HFC, Farming 4.0.

INTRODUCTION

The Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division, of the United Nations, (United Nations, 2019) has predicted that the global population will reach 8.55 billion people by 2030 and almost 10 billion people by 2050. In order to feed this growing population, according to FAO, food production must increase with 70 percent by 2050 and a 60 percent increase in demand for high quality protein such as milk, meat and eggs.

Agriculture is energy intensive and the pressure to produce more food requires more energy, an increasingly costly input to the production process. At the same time, the requirements for the use of sustainable methods and environmental protection for energy products have increased.

One of the projects that studies the solutions needed to achieve sustainable energy without pollution is RES4LIVE (<https://res4live.eu/>). This H2020 EU funded project, 2020-2024, with an overall budget € 5815206,88 have 17 partners from 8 countries. The strategic objective of RES4LIVE is to develop and bring into the market integrated, cost-effective and case-sensitive RES (Renewable Energy Systems) solutions towards achieving fossil-free livestock farming.

One of the many possible solutions is to use green hydrogen as an energy source. Green hydrogen is produced by electrolysis of water, using electricity from renewable sources like hydropower, wind, and solar. Zero carbon emissions produced. Turquoise hydrogen produced by the thermal

splitting of methane (methane pyrolysis). Instead of CO₂, solid carbon produced. Pink (Purple / Red) hydrogen produced by electrolysis using nuclear power. Black (Grey) hydrogen extracted from natural gas using steam-methane reforming. Yellow hydrogen produced by electrolysis using grid electricity. Blue hydrogen is Grey or Brown hydrogen with its CO₂ sequestered or repurposed. White hydrogen produced as a by-product of industrial processes. Brown hydrogen extracted from fossil fuels, usually coal, using gasification.

The European Commission has foreseen the use of hydrogen since 2003 (European Commission, 2003).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Hydrogen can be the sustainable energy source of the future, decrease the global dependence on fossil resources, and lower the pollutant emissions from the agriculture. Hydrogen can be used as an energy source for both stationary and mobile equipment. In agriculture, the major interest is for use in self-propelled equipment.

Hydrogen can be used as fuel in internal combustion engines and as a fuel cell in vehicles.

Using hydrogen as a fuel of internal combustion engine can improve engine efficiency, power output and reduce NO_x emissions. Has a heating value three times larger than petroleum, on a mass basis, and the emission is low compared to conventional vehicles but need additional space and weight to install the storage tank. This storage tank must comply with SAE J2579, the United Nations Global Technical Regulation No. 13 and the applicable standards for the country that the vehicle is deployed.

The first tractor converted to dual fuel was New Holland T5.140 Auto Command™, in the Netherlands (<https://h2dualpower.com/en>). The hydrogen is stored in five cylinders, placed above the tractor cab for increased safety without compromising functionality. Each cylinder contains 11.5kg of hydrogen pressurised at 350 bar. The engine is ideally suited for the use of HVO diesel. HVO (also sold as ‘blue diesel’) stands for “Hydrotreated Vegetable Oil” and is a new type of diesel fuel. It is made from waste vegetable oil together with other waste such as animal fat. HVO is thus a fossil-free, renewable fuel that offers huge sustainability benefits, such as an 89% reduction in CO₂ and lower emissions of harmful substances such as particulate matter, nitrogen and sulphur. HVO diesel is virtually odourless and easily biodegradable.

Hydrogen can be used in fuel cells for vehicular applications with several automotive manufacturers producing fuel cell vehicles currently. Fuel cells can achieve efficiencies of up to 60%, while the rest is lost as heat.

HFCs (Hydrogen Fuel Cells) are static energy conversion systems that generate electrical energy through an electro-chemical reaction of hydrogen and oxygen. The electrical energy will generated by HFCs as long as hydrogen and oxygen is conducted into the system. This electricity is used to charge the battery and to power the electric motors that drive the wheels. HFC system employs oxygen and hydrogen to generate electricity and water with no other pollutants.

Fig. 1. Basic structure of fuel cell based electric tractor (Manoharan et al., 2019)

China's first 5G+ hydrogen fuel electric tractor officially launched in 2020 by the China National Agricultural Machinery Equipment Innovation Center and the Luoyang Advanced Manufacturing Industry R&D Base of Tianjin High-end Equipment Research Institute of Tsinghua University. The HFC operates when tractor is normal loaded and at overload is helped by a lithium battery.

In 2021, Volvo Group has opened a dedicated Hydrogen Fuel Cell Test Lab at the Volvo Construction Equipment Technical Center in Eskilstuna, Sweden.

Starting in 2023, a dedicated line at Toyota Motor Manufacturing Kentucky will begin assembling integrated dual fuel cell modules destined for use in hydrogen-powered, Class 8 heavy-duty segment.

Cummins laid out an aggressive strategy for hydrogen today, addressing both production of the low-carbon energy source as well as the fuel cell technology to convert it into power for customers. Cummins announced it will work with Navistar on the development of a class 8 truck powered by hydrogen fuel cells. The truck will be integrated into Werner Enterprises' fleet of more than 7700 tractors for local and regional service on a year-long trial basis out of Fontana, California.

Germany, for example, plans to spend \$9 billion on hydrogen infrastructure this decade, with 5 Gigawatts of electrolyzer capacity by 2030. China and South Korea are developing fuel cell and hydrogen production targets. In the U.S., California expects to have spent about \$230 million on hydrogen projects by the end of 2023.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In October 1959 Allis-Chalmers demonstrated the first farm tractor with a fuel cell which powers an 20 horsepower DC electric motor.

The use of hydrogen as an energy source is not limited to agricultural tractors. Today, competitive solutions are being sought for its use in many applications such as commercial vehicles, trains, building heating, industrial heating etc.

As Leeuwen (Leeuwen, 2020) pointed out in the case of low-power tractors, at present, systems based on electric batteries are generally more advantageous than HFCs. Obviously, farm-level infrastructure can benefit from the use of HFCs.

On the other hand, Deloitte (Deloitte, Ballard, 2020) forecasts a strong advance in HFC technology and investment, so that in 5-6 years will be more profitable to use tractors, combines, high-power trucks equipped with HFC. The total cost of ownership will be smaller than battery-electric and traditional internal combustion engine vehicles. They also predict that in 9-10 years the technology will be extended to engines with lower powers.

The cost of hydrogen varies significantly across regions, as it depends heavily on the prices and availability of energy inputs. The cost of renewable hydrogen is expected to decline by about 60 percent in ten year. Since the costs of hydrogen production differ significantly between regions, long-distance transmission and international trade in hydrogen can be attractive. Even existing natural gas pipelines can transport hydrogen, often with only modest upgrades. Hydrogen refuelling stations are currently the highest cost element in the cost at the pump.

A solution to reduce costs, given the characteristics of agriculture, would be to produce hydrogen on farms. One of the applicable technologies is to obtain hydrogen from the air (Fasihi et al., 2019) but the most recommended, from my point of view, is the production of hydrogen from biomass (Binder et al., 2018).

There are two main methods of producing hydrogen from biomass: steam gasification and sorption enhanced reforming.

Although the initial investment is higher for the steam gasification method, the production costs are lower and the yields obtained are higher.

In Fig. 2. (Binder et al., 2018) is presented the concept of hydrogen production from biomass by steam gasification, DFB means dual fluidized bed, WGS means water gas shift and PSA means pressure swing adsorption.

It is necessary to modernize this process in order to accept as raw material all types of vegetable waste from the farm. Thus, the farm will not only provide its own hydrogen and energy needs, but will also be a supplier of hydrogen. When the production of hydrogen from fossil fuels is

abandoned, these production units will be competitive.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the DFB gasification based H₂ production (Binder et al., 2018)

CONCLUSIONS

As the agricultural industry faces pressure to achieve zero net emissions by 2040, the possibilities of alternative fuels in agriculture must be applied.

Hydrogen is the most abundant element in the universe and is also a key element in the fossil fuels that have powered mankind since the first industrial revolution. Hydrogen as an energy carrier has two major advantages over fossil fuels for mobility applications. Its energy release through oxidation produces only water as an output, and it is renewable.

Urgent action is needed to achieve net-zero targets quickly, and hydrogen is a necessary part of the answer. Hydrogen can become the most cost-competitive solution for several specific use cases near-term, and it can quickly become so for many more.

In order to meet commitments on environmental protection and decarbonisation, it is absolutely necessary for governments to support investment and the development of the entire hydrogen chain.

Within this hydrogen chain, agricultural farms could have in addition to the role of important consumer of hydrogen for energy for self-propelled equipment, warehouses, buildings but also a zonal producer of hydrogen, thus being able to help distribute hydrogen to other consumers.

Governments should apply incentives such as tax breaks, subsidies or penalties on conventional alternatives to encourage the initial acceleration of hydrogen.

To support the development of this area, governments should support research, modernization and pilot projects in this area.

In this context, governments need to be made aware of the important role that agriculture can play in the field of hydrogen. This new role will not only help farm prosperity but also help grow and diversify crops and create new jobs in rural areas. Hydrogen Fuel Cells will be able to ensure, at

competitive prices, the energy supply of all agricultural machines, warehouses and outbuildings.

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PRELIMINARY DATA ABOUT OPHRAELLA COMMUNA LESAGE, 1986 (COLEOPTERA: CHRYSOMELIDAE) IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

*This paper presents data on the species *Ophraella communa* LeSage, 1986 in Romania, with some references to the biology and ecology of this species recently reported nationally. In Romania, the species was detected in 2019 in Bucharest, but published pictures and data appeared in 2020. The researches were carried out in Bucharest during 2020 - 2021. The main host plant of this species is *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L., an invasive North American species whose pollen creates health problems for humans, causing allergies. This species of beetle can be used in the biological control of this plant. Other host plants also belong to the Asteraceae family: *Xanthium strumarium* L., *Helianthus annuus* L, *Ambrosia trifida* L. From the point of view of biology, the existence of two annual generations has been observed. The following natural enemies have been identified: *Perillus bioculatus* Fabr., *Zicrona caerulea* L.*

Key words: *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*, data, *Ophraella communa*, Romania, *Perillus bioculatus*.

INTRODUCTION

Ophraella communa LeSage, 1986 is a North American beetle, belonging to the Chrysomelidae family, Galerucinae subfamily. It was first detected in Europe in 2013 in Italy, near Milan airport (Boriani et al., 2013), then in Switzerland (Müller-Schärer et al., 2014), Slovenia (Seljak, 2017), Croatia (Zadravek et al., 2019), Serbia (Petrovic-Obradovic et al., 2020), Hungary (Horvath et al., 2020) and in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Karrer et. al., 2020).

In Romania, this species is allochthonous and has been observed for the first time in 2019, in Bucharest by Eugenia Petrescu on the 8th of July (unpublished date) and by iNaturalist user danamihaimileazachi in Bucharest on the 19th of June 2020 (www.inaturalist.org/observations/50185018).

Then Eugenia Petrescu and Alexandru Ștefan-Fotin observed the species also in Bucharest and in Popești-Leordeni (Ilfov County) during 2020–2021.

Ophraella communa LeSage is a natural enemy of *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L., an invasive North American weed expanding inside the green fields of Europe and whose pollen creates health problems for humans causing allergies.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The insects were gathered by hand. The observations were made periodically in Bucharest on some fields, between July and November 2019-2021. For the determination of the plant species different guides were used (Ciocârlan, 2000; Sârbu et al., 2013).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Description of the beetle species – *Ophraella communa* LeSage is characterized by a moderately dense pubescence on the body, with a specific elytral pattern of black stripes on a yellowish – ochre chromatic background: the discal stripe and the basal stripe are incomplete, the subsutural and submarginal stripes are sometimes joined at the elytral apex (LeSage, 1986). The punctuation of the elytra is rough, it is not arranged in rows. The pronotum has three black spots: one central and two lateral. The base of the head is black and has a blackish spot in the center. The antennae are dark in colour, sometimes the first antenna segment may be yellowish. The legs are yellowish, the last tarsal segment and claws are brown. The eyes are dark (Fig. 1a).

Body length in adults is 4–7 mm, the males being smaller than females.

Body length in larvae is approximately 5.5 – 7 mm, the size of the eggs is approximate 0.5 mm.

The colour of the pupa is yellowish – brownish, being located in a silky cocoon glued to the leaf (Fig. 1c).

The colour of the larvae is yellowish to brownish – dark, with the head brown – blackish, the legs are brownish to black, it presents hairs, capitata dorsal setae and tubercles (Fig 1b).

The colour of the eggs is yellowish and after a few hours becomes yellow – orange, with microsculpture on the chorion. The eggs can be laid alone on the leaves or in groups of up 20 – 25 (Fig. 1d).

Fig. 1 – *Ophraella communis* LeSage – a. adult on host plant *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* (photo by Alexandru Ștefan-Fotin); b. larva (photo by Eugenia Petrescu); c. pupa and eggs (photo by Alexandru Ștefan-Fotin); d. eggs (photo by Eugenia Petrescu)

Host plants – this species is an oligophagous beetle: its host plants belonging to the genus *Ambrosia* (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L., *Ambrosia trifida* L.). (Fig.2a, 2b, table 1, table 2)

Other attacked plants also belong to the Asteraceae family (*Xanthium strumarium* L., *Helianthus annuus* L.). Sometimes the beetle was observed on *Artemisia absinthium* L. (Table 1)

In Japan, the larvae and adults of this beetle feed on several cultivars of sunflower *Helianthus annuus* L. (Emura, 2000). The larvae and the adults feed on leaves and flowers of these plants. Sometimes, this insect destroys the plants before their flowering.

Biology: From the point of view of biology, the existence of two annual generations has been observed (bivoltine). Overwintered adults appear in nature in June. The adults live over 60 days/generation. Adults enter the hiemal diapause in October or early November.

The simultaneous existence of several stages of development was observed (Table1, Table 2).

Fig. 2 – *Ophraella communa* on host plants - a. adults on *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*; b. adult on *Ambrosia trifida*; c., d. pupae on *Helianthus annuus* (photos by Eugenia Petrescu)

The researches were carried out in Bucharest and in Ilfov County during 2019 - 2021 (Table 1, Table 2).

Table 1

Ophraella communa in Bucharest and Ilfov County (2019-2021)

Park or street in the vicinity/Geographical coordinates	Year	Host plant	Day /month	<i>Ophraella.communa</i> life stages
Bucharest sector 1				
Padina Street 44.523009°N ; 26.087131°E	2021	<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i> L.	23.07	eggs, larvae, adults
Bucharest sector 2				
Barbu Văcărescu Street 44.462518°N ; 26.107703°E	2019	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	08.07	adults
	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	04.09	eggs, larvae, adults
Plumbuita 1 Park 44.467256°N ; 26.128231°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	31.08	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
Tei Park 44.465309°N ; 26.128231°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	25.08	adults
Râul Colentina Park 44.454791°N ; 26.149718°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	21.08	eggs, pupae, adults
Păsărari Park 44.449802°N ; 26.123854°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	19.07	adults
Bucharest sector 3				
Theodor Pallady Boulevard 44.406909°N ; 26.184472°E	2019	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	13.07	larvae, adults
			21.08	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
	2020		11.09	adults
			17.09	adults
			28.09	adults
	2021		12.07	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			16.07	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults

		<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	20.07	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			12.08	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			15.09	pupae, adults
			23.09	pupae, adults
			08.10	adults
			11.10	adults
		<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	14.07	adults
Theodor Pallady Boulevard 44.407444°N ; 26.187091°E	2020	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	11.08	adults
			20.08	adults
			06.09	larvae, adults
	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	20.07	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			22.07	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			11.10	adults
		<i>Artemisia absinthium</i>	08.08	adults
			08.10	adults
			08.08	adults
		<i>Helianthus annuus L.</i>	11.08	pupae
			05.09	larvae
			12.09	adults
	18.07		adults	
	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i>	20.07	pupae	
22.07		adults		
11.08		adults		
21.08		larvae		

Theodor Pallady Boulevard 44.406825°N ; 26.196583°E	2019	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	13.07	eggs, larvae, adults
	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	04.09	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
Theodor Pallady Boulevard 44.409021°N ; 26.186801°E	2020	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	19.08	adults
			23.08	eggs, larvae, adults
			24.08	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			25.08	eggs, larvae, adults
			03.09	adults
			24.09	adults
			01.10	adults
	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	04.10	adults
			04.07	eggs, pupae, adults
			11.10	adults
Liviu Rebreanu Boulevard 44.424233°N ; 26.172232°E	2020	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	27.09	adults
	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	15.07	larvae, adults
IOR Park 44.425435°N ; 26.029230°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	22.09	adults
Miniș Park 44.426576°N ; 26.173992°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	15.07	larvae, adults
			05.09	adults
Pantelimon Park 44.439605°N ; 26.195217°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	22.08	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
Bucharest Sector 4				
Văcărești Natural Park 44.392639°N ; 26.135370°E 44.394997°N ; 26.129559°E	2020	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	28.08	eggs, larvae, adults
			29.08	eggs, larvae, adults
			02.09	larvae, adults
			13.09	adults
			20.09	adults
			26.09	adults
			28.09	eggs, larvae, adults
03.10	adults			

	2021	<i>Xanthium italicum</i> Moretti	13.09	larvae, adults
		<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	05.07	larvae, adults
			07.07	pupae, adults
			10.07	adults
			22.07	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			28.07	adults
			04.08	adults
			11.08	eggs, pupae, adults
			28.08	eggs, larvae, adults
			23.09	adults
		<i>Ambrosia trifida</i> L.	22.07	eggs, pupae, adults
		<i>X. italicum</i> Moretti	22.07	adults
24.08	eggs, adults			

Bucharest Sector 5				
Kogălniceanu Boulevard 44.435089°N ; 26.079012°E	2020	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	10.10	larvae, adults
Bucharest Sector 6				
Lacul Morii Island 44.458738°N; 26.029230 °E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	25.09	adults
Ifov County				
Popești-Leordeni				
Oituz Street 44.375335°N; 26.151164°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	13.08	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			11.09	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
Oituz Street 44.376725°N; 26.149494°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	13.08	adults
			11.09	eggs, larvae, pupae, adults
			13.08	adults
Oituz Street 44.376816°N; 26.149914°E	2021	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	13.08	adults
			<i>X. strumarium</i>	13.08

Natural enemies: The eggs, larvae, adults or pupae were attacked by several predators: *Perillus bioculatus* Fabr., *Zicrona caerulea* L.

A recently new established shield bug species for Romania, found by Eugenia Petrescu in Bucharest, is the two spotted stink bug - *Perillus bioculatus* Fabr. (Rădac et Teodorescu, 2021). This bug seems to be the main predator for *Ophraella communa*; we found the predatory shield bug attacking all of the beetles's life stages (Fig 3.a, b, c, Table 2) and almost always sitting on *Ophraella*'s main host plant, the common ragweed, *Ambrosia artemisiifolia*, but also occasionally on the large cocklebur, *Xanthium strumarium*, another host plant for the beetle (Table 2).

Zicrona caerulea L. is another predatory shield bug feeding on *Ophraella communa*, but not as common as *Perillus bioculatus*; we only found the blue shield bug in connection with the beetle in Văcărești Natural Park, in Pantelimon Park and in a field in the vicinity of the boulevard Theodor Pallady (Fig.3d, Table 2)

Fig. 3 Natural enemies of *Ophraella communa*: *Perillus bioculatus* – a adults (photo by Alexandru-Ștefan-Fotin), b. *P. bioculatus* – nymph on *O. communa* pupa (photo by Alexandru-Ștefan Fotin), c. *P. bioculatus* feeding with an adult of *Ophraella* (photo by Eugenia Petrescu), d. *Zicrona caerulea* eating a nymph of *O. communa* (photo by Eugenia Petrescu)

Table 2

Interactions between *Ophraella communa* LeSage and natural predators (2020-2021)

Park or street in the vicinity/ Geographical coordinates	Date of observation	Predator		<i>Ophraella communa</i> Life stage	Host plant
		species	Life stage		
Bucharest					
Tei Park 44.465309°N; 26.128231°E	25.08.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	nymph	adult	<i>Ambrosia. artemisiifolia L.</i>
Râul Colentina Park 44.454791°N; 26.149718°E	21.08.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	nymph	pupa	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
Theodor Pallady Boulevard 44.406 909°N; 26.184 472°E	15.09.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	pupa	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
	23.09.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
Theodor Pallady Boulevard 44.407 444°N; 26 187 091°E	18.07.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	adult	<i>X. strumarium</i>
	21.08.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	nymph	larva	<i>X. strumarium</i>
	11.10.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
Theodor Pallady Boulevard 44.409 021°N; 26.186 801°E	24.09.2020	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
		<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	2 adults	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
		<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
		<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	nymph	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>

	04.10.2020	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
Văcărești Natural Park 44.394997°N; 26.129559°E	02.09.2020	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	larva	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
	23.09.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
	10.10.2020	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	nymph	larva	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
Kogălniceanu Boulevard 44.435 089°N; 26.079012°E					
Văcărești Natural Park 44.394997°N; 26.129559°E	13.09.2020	<i>Zicrona caerulea</i>	adult	larva	<i>Xanthium italicum</i>
Theodor Pallady Boulevard 44.407 444°N; 26 187 091°E	06.09.2020	<i>Zicrona caerulea</i>	adult	larva	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
Pantelimon Park 44.439605°N; 26.195217°E	22.08.2021	<i>Zicrona caerulea</i>	adult	larva	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>
Ifov-County (Popești Leordeni, Oituz Street)					
44.375335°N; 26.151164°E	13.08.2021	<i>Perillus bioculatus</i>	adult	adult	<i>A. artemisiifolia</i>

CONCLUSIONS

Ophraella communa LeSage is reported to be an effective species for the biological control of *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L. Because this species also attacks the sunflower, careful monitoring of its numbers as well as new research on its biology and ecology are required.

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RAPESEED AGROTECHNICS IN RELATION WITH THE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY IN BIODIESEL PRODUCTION - REVIEW

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Abstract

This paper represents a documentation of the existing relations between the agrotechnics of rapeseed culture in the production of biodiesel from pure rapeseed oil and from waste showing its quality and efficiency.

The pure biodiesel, called B100, is a monoalkylester of fatty acids derived from vegetable or animal oils. It is obtained chemically through the transesterification reaction, where a glycerol reacts with an alcohol in the presence of a catalyst forming alkyl esters of fatty acids (crude biodiesel) and an alcohol (crude glycerin).

The raw materials used in the production of biodiesel from waste are mainly residues left over from the technological process of obtaining alimentary rapeseed oil

It will be compared the quality, quantity and economic efficiency of biodiesel obtained from pure oil and waste from each parcel of rapeseed and the best method of biodiesel production shall be determined.

Key words: rapeseed, biodiesel, waste, transesterification, esterification

INTRODUCTION

The continuous increase in global energy consumption raises important issues for finding alternative sources of renewable and sustainable energy, environmentally friendly, to ensure energy security and socio-economic development. Has been set an energy efficiency target of at least 32.5% set by 2030. (C.E., 2019)

In Romania, the increase in primary energy consumption and the need to ensure energy independence, according to European Directives, must take measures to replace fossil fuels used in transport with biofuels, which would represent min. 20% by 2020. (CE Directive, 2009)

Considering the climate conditions, the agricultural potential and the social-economics aspects of Romania, rapeseed oil and its derivatives are among the most suitable biofuels (Energy / Climate Package, 2020) along with sunflower oil (Bunta and Baldini, 2008) and soy.

The rapeseed belongs to the family *Cruciferae*, genre *Brassica*, which includes 34 species. For oil is cultivated *Brassica napus* L. *ssp. oleifera*

Metzg (*rapseed colza*) and *Brassica campestris* L. ssp. *oleifera* D. C. (rapseed naveta). Both species have autumn and spring forms, the varieties of autumn forms being more productive. (Muntean et al., 2014)

In Romania, rapeseed was cultivated on larger areas before the First World War and between the two world wars. Thereby, in 1913, it occupied 80.38 thousand ha, and in 1930 approx. 77.32 thousand ha. After 1948, the areas varied from one year to another, passing a little over 20 thousand ha only in 1953, 1955, 1956. In 1935, the statistical yearbook of Romania mentions 5.9 thousand ha. (<https://www.cartiagricole.ro/cultivarea-rapitei/?v=f5b15f58caba>) The area cultivated with rapeseed in 2018 was 633 thousand ha, and the total national production was 1611 thousand tons. (Anghelache et al., 2020)

Rapeseed currently occupies a particularly important place in the world economy, as a source of vegetable oils. The seeds contain 42 - 48% oil used both in food, in the preparation of margarines and in industry. (Muste, 2001)

Rapeseed cultivation has multiple phytotechnical advantages: it is sown and harvested outside the crowded periods; has a favorable reaction to fertilization; allows the complete use of the same set of machines as for cereals; can be used as an excellent precursor for successive crops or for autumn cereals; raises soil fertility and prevents erosion on sloping lands; it is a good honey plant; the cakes being rich in protein (38 - 41.9%), carbohydrates (31.5 - 36.6%) and mineral salts (8 - 9.8%), have a good feed value; the epigee part of the plant (straw) can be used in the manufacture of particle board; it can also be used as green fodder in late autumn and early spring. (Muste, 2002; Guş et al., 2003; Guş et al., 2004)

Rapeseed also has some disadvantages due to: drought during sowing; the alternation between frost and thawing in spring and the frosts during the buding-flowering period. (Pirnă et al., 2011)

Biodiesel is an alternative fuel that can be used in pure form or in a mixture with diesel (Soriano et al., 2005), when burned in internal combustion engines. (Ingendoh, 2010) Pure biodiesel, called B100, is a monoalkylester of fatty acids derived from vegetable or animal oils. (Turck, 2003) It is obtained chemically by the transesterification reaction, where a glycerol reacts with an alcohol (methanol) in the presence of a catalyst (potassium hydroxide) forming alkyl esters of fatty acids (crude biodiesel) and an alcohol (crude glycerin). (Brighila, 2015)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study presents research results on the agrotechnics of rapeseed culture and its influence on the quality and economic efficiency in biodiesel production from pure oil and from waste. The aim of this study is to

determinate which process leads to a greater reduction of the carbon dioxide emissions and other greenhouse gases involved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RAPESEED CULTURE TECHNOLOGY

Scientific classification. Rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.) is part of the cruciferous plant family (*Brassicaceae*). (Figure 1) The flowers form pods of 5 - 10 cm with round seeds, color black - bluish till brown - bluish, weighing 1000 seeds between 3.5 and 6.5 g. Between the beginning of the flowering period and maturity is a distance of 70 days.

Figure 1. Rapeseed (*Brassica napus* L.)

(source: https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/5/57/Brassica_napus_-_K%C3%B6hler%E2%80%93s_Medizinal-Pflanzen-169.jpg;))

Rapeseed (*Brassica napus oleifera* and *Brassica rapa oleifera*) is a plant in the Brassicaceae cruciferous family with yellow flowers and a thin, long and branched stem. Its seeds are rich in oil used to produce biodiesel.

Rapeseed - canola is a registered trademark of a rapeseed hybrid, originally produced and cultivated in Canada, in areas with dry climates, excessive continental temperate. Rapeseed oil was produced in the 19th century as a source of lubrication for steam engines. The oil has a bitter taste due to the high level of acids. Canola was produced precisely to reduce this amount of acid, resulting in a tasty oil. (Dulf, 2008)

The rapeseed is cultivated on an area of over 27 million ha., Globally. The largest cultivators are China with 7.2 million ha and India with over 6.9 million ha, followed by Canada with 5.1 million ha, Germany with 1.3 million ha, and France with 1.2 million ha. The progress made worldwide and in our country in the improvement of this plant and in the multiple use of oil, fully motivates the reconsideration of the areas cultivated with this plant in

Romania as well. The vegetation period of the autumn varieties is 270-300 days and of the spring varieties 110-130 days. In the official catalog of plant varieties in Romania are registered 24 plant varieties. (Pirnă et al., 2011)

Place in crop rotation The best precursors for the autumn rape are the crops that release the soil early until the beginning of August, ensuring good soil preparation conditions, the accumulation of water necessary for emergence. (Samuil, 2007)

The best precursors are: autumn cereals (wheat and barley), early potatoes, legumes (peas), autumn borscht and red clover, after the first harvest. Spring rape can be sown after late harvests such as corn, sugar beet, potatoes, etc. Is not cultivate after soybeans and sunflowers, to prevent the spread of the attack of *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum*. Rapeseed can return to the same field after 3 years, and in case of *Sclerotinia* attack, after 7-8 years. (Harwood, 1985)

After rapeseed, most plants can be grown, because it releases the soil early and leaves the soil clean of weeds, being a good precursor for winter wheat.

Soil tillage Plowing will be carried out immediately after the release of the soil to a depth of 20-25 cm, in the aggregate with the star harrow. In the situation when the soil is dry and the plowing cannot be carried out without removing boulders, it is necessary to process the soil with the disc harrow in the aggregate with the harrow with adjustable fangs, following the plowing to be done after the first rain. Until sowing, the plow is kept clean of weeds, crushed and loosened by working with the disc harrow in the aggregate with the corner harrow.

The last work is performed with the combine at the sowing depth. If the soil is too loose, roll it before sowing, to ensure the incorporation of the seed at the optimum depth. At the time of sowing, the soil must be well crushed and settled. (Altieri, 1987)

Seed and sowing The seed must come from the year of sowing (it loses its germination by aging), to come from certified crops, from higher biological categories and have a minimum purity of 97% and a minimum germination of 85%.

The sowing period in the south of the country is September 5-15, and for the east, west and north of the country it is September 1-10. Both early and late sowing do not make the plants last well over the winter, and production decreases. In the first case, the plants enter the winter with a too vigorous vegetative mass, and in the second case there is a weak development of the plants until the coming of the cold season. (Zăhan 1983)

Spring varieties are sown early, in the first emergency, immediately after entering the field, because the rapeseed germinates at 2 - 3 ° C.

Bîlteanu, 2001, reports that the optimal sowing density in our country is 100 - 150 germinating grains / m² to ensure 80 - 120 harvestable plants / m². Large cultivating countries in Europe use densities between 50 and 80 plants / m² for harvesting (Soltner, 1990). Volioud, 1992, quoted by Axinte, 2006, mentions that, in Switzerland, the largest harvests are made with 30 - 50 plants / m². For the pedoclimatic conditions in the Romanian Plain Georgescu et al., 2015, report the use for sowing rapeseed in experimental fields with a density of 60 plants / m² (Table 1.)

Table 1.

Seed quantity and optimum density for autumn rapeseed cultivation				
Nr. crt.	Seed quantity (kg/ha)	Density (plants/m ²)	Country	Author
1.	-	30 -50	Switzerland	Volioud, 1992; Axinte, 2006
2.	4 - 6	50 – 80	France	Soltner, 1990
3	3.5 - 4	-	Germany	Samuil, 2007
4	6 - 10	80 -120	Romania	Bîlteanu, 2001
5	-	60	Romania (Romanian Plain)	Georgescu et al., 2015

The quantity of seed is 6 -10 kg / ha, depending on the soil moisture and the quality of the germination bed, in order to have 80-110 plants / m² at harvest. At these densities, a more uniform ripening is ensured, due to the reduction of the degree of plants branching, so the losses by shaking are reduced. In Germany, are used sowing quantities of only 3.5 - 4 kg / ha due to the varieties with a high degree of branching and the specific climatic conditions that favor this. (Samuil, 2007)

The sowing is done with the cereal seeders (SUP - 21, SUP - 29, SUP - 48) at the distance between rows of 12.5 cm and at the depth of 2-3 cm.

Works to be carried out immediately after sowing: the roller for bringing the seed into contact with the soil. Pre-emergent herbicide is the safest solution for keeping weeds clean until the ground is completely covered.

Fertilization. system Rapeseed is one of the crops with the highest specific consumption. For a ton of seeds and the related biomass production, the specific consumption is 50 - 60 kg nitrogen, 30 - 60 kg phosphorus, 40 - 50 kg potassium, 50 - 60 kg calcium, 20 - 30 kg sulfur and important quantities of microelements. (Muntean et al., 2014) According to Soltner, 1990, for 100 kg of seeds, plus the aerial part of the green mass, rapeseed consumes 2 kg N, 2.5 kg P₂O₅, 10 kg K₂O. (Table 2.)

For production, rapeseed plants use applied fertilizers and soil elements, depending on soil fertility. The soils in Romania "provide" to the plants annually between 20 - 60 (80) kg N, around 20 - 25 kg nitrogen for each percentage of humus. When fertilization has been inadequate, or

climatic conditions have adversely affected nutrient uptake, symptoms of deficiencies in various chemicals may occur.

Table 2.

Fertilization system for autumn rape					
Nr. crt.	Specification	Dose	Unit of measurement	Author	Observations
1	Specific consume (per tona of seed)			Muntean et al., 2014	
	Nitrogen (N)	50-60	Kg		
	Phosphorus (P)	30-60	Kg		
	Potassium (K)	40-50	Kg		
	Calcium (Ca)	50-60	Kg		
	Sulfur (S)	20-30	Kg		
2.	Specific consume (per 100 kg seed)			Soltner, 1990	
	N	2	Kg		
	P ₂ O ₅	2.5	Kg		
	K ₂ O	10	Kg		
3	Fertilization with N			Sieling and Kage, 2010	Achieving 500-600 g / m ² at the end of winter
	Azot	35-45	Kg/ha		
	Mineral nitrogen (from soil)	45-60	Kg/ha		
4	Fertilization with P			Orlovius, 2016	Before sowing
	P ₂ O ₅	50-80	Kg/ha		
5	Fertilization with K			Orlovius, 2016	The concentration in seeds is 0.9 - 1.0% K.
	K ₂ O	200-400	Kg/ha		
6	Fertilization with S			Hălmăjan et al., 2007	Optimum 20-30 kg/ha
	(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	125	Kg/ha		

The manure applied directly to the rapeseed crop in the amount of 20 - 30 t / ha, has determined the obtaining of economic increases, both for rapeseed and for the double crop that followed, or for the wheat sown in autumn (Bîlteanu and Bîrnaure, 1979) . In this case, the chemical fertilizers are reduced by 1.0 -1.5 kg N, 0.75 kg P and 2.0 -2.5 kg K for each ton of manure.

Nitrogen fertilization in autumn At the end of winter, a promising rapeseed crop must have the biomass of the aerial part at least 500-600 g / sqm (fresh substance). To achieve this biomass, rapeseed plants absorb between 35 - 45 kg N / ha, which means that in the soil there must be between 45 - 60 kg of mineral nitrogen / ha at sowing. (Sieling and Kage, 2010)

Excessive increase in applied nitrogen doses, does not increase the amount of seed harvested. Also, the high doses of nitrogen administered reduce the amounts of obtained oil. (Béřeš et al., 2019)

Phosphorus fertilization. Rapeseed is a crop with high phosphorus requirements. Some experts believe that phosphorus fertilizers can be applied

at any time to keep a high level of mobile phosphorus in the soil. In most cases, it is best to fertilize with phosphorus before sowing. (Orlovius, 2016)

On soils poor in phosphorus, french specialists even recommend the application of fertilizers on plowing, so that, following the work of preparing the germination bed, rapeseed seedlings find phosphorus in the surface layers very quickly. (Soltner, 1990) If they had been applied before plowing, the fertilizers would be placed too deep for the young plants (at the bottom of the furrow) and would be inaccessible in the first phases of vegetation.

Non-phosphorus fertilization (especially on poorly supplied soils) severely penalizes the production. At rapeseed, phosphorus deficiencies can occur in the first phases of vegetation, even in the second week after emergence, because the phosphorus reserves in the seed is depleted in the first 7 days. (Grzebisz et al., 2018)

High phosphorus rates increase oil and protein content (Bailey and Grant, 1990) and cause rapeseed plants to mature faster.

Potassium fertilization Rapeseed with oilseeds has a high demand for potassium. The assimilation of potassium by winter rape in seeds is between 200 and 400 kg / ha K₂O, although the concentration in seeds is relatively low, with values of 0.9 - 1.0% K in the dry matter. Thus, there is a considerable difference between the absorption of K by rapeseed and the removal of K from the field with the seeds, if the straw is not harvested but remains in the field. Although the export of potassium with the seeds from field is reduced to about 30 - 60 kg / ha K₂O, growth is severely restricted by insufficient intake of K. (Orlovius, 2016)

In China, optimal potassium (K) fertilization is beneficial for the efficiency and quality of oilseeds (*Brassica napus* L.). However, the discrepancy between the high K demand for winter rape and the low soil fertility and the insufficient potassium intake, limited the sustainable development of rapeseed production. (Ren et al., 2013)

Sulfur fertilization. For rapeseed, sulfur is considered the third most important element, after nitrogen and phosphorus. (Poisson et al., 2019)

The best way to cover sulfur needs would be to use superphosphate. Due to the high sulfur content, fertilization with 125 kg of ammonium sulphate is sufficient to cover the sulfur needs of the rapeseed crop. Ammonium sulfate is cheap, but it is more difficult to apply, because it looks like a powder (fine crystals) that spreads with some difficulty. It should not be spread when the plants are wet or frozen. (Hälmäjan et al., 2007)

Ammonium sulfate also has the advantage of reducing the pH on basic soils, favoring the absorption of phosphorus. The optimal dose of sulfur (S) for rapeseed is 20-30 kg / ha. For rapeseed, the ratio of sulfur to nitrogen should be 1/7. Sulfate ions are soluble and easily leachable. Therefore, sulfur

fertilizers (except superphosphate) should not be applied in the fall. (Hälmäjan, 2007)

Soltner, 1990, mentions crop increases of 2.25 - 3.70 q / ha by using sulfur fertilizers on some soils.

Chemical fertilizers applied alone are very well used. The absorption of nutrients takes place with intensity from the first phases of vegetation; but the largest amounts are absorbed in the period from the end of spring to the beginning of fruiting.

The doses of fertilizers for rapeseed cultivation depending on the planned production and the values of the agrochemical mapping, regarding the phosphorus, potassium and nitrogen index, are, in general, the following: nitrogen 80 - 180 kg; phosphorus 50 - 80 kg; potassium 60 - 80 kg. In the absence of agrochemical analyzes, the recommended doses are variable depending on the expected production: 80 - 180 kg N / ha, 50 - 120 kg P₂O₅ / ha and 65 - 150 K₂O / ha.

The full dose of phosphorus and potassium and 1/3 of the nitrogen dose will be applied under the basic plow, and the remaining 2/3 of the nitrogen dose will be given in early spring. Late fertilization around the formation of siliceous, aims to increase the mass of 1,000 grains. (Samuil, 2007)

Calcium amendments are applied to acid-reactive soils to correct for pH 6.5-7.5.

Care work. Chemical weed control is done with herbicides, Volatile herbicides are preferred because they control very well wheat or barley samulastra and many annual weed species, including Sorghum halepense from seed. It is applied pre-emergently and is incorporated by double threading.

Annual and perennial monocotyledonous species (rhizome crust) can be controlled by applying in vegetation (postemergent) selective herbicides such as: Fusilade forte 1 - 1.3 l / ha, Pantera, Targa super, Select super, 1.5 l / ha. Gallant super 1.0 l / ha. (Guş et al., 2003)

Pest control. Earth Fleas (*Phylottreta* sp.) are controlled by treating the seeds with Nuprid AL 600 FS, 6 l / t of seed. (Georgescu et al., 2015) The stem weevil (*Centorrhynchus* sp.) is controlled by Cruiser 35 CE treatments, 3 l / ha.

The glossy rapeseed beetle (*Meligethes aeneus*) is controlled with Fastac 10 CE - 0.075 l / ha by two treatments, with a break interval of 7 - 10 days.

The harvesting of rapeseed. Rapeseed is one of the agricultural plants for seeds that requires special attention in terms of establishing the time of harvest, due to the easy shaking of the seeds, registering shaking losses of 30 - 40 and even 50%.

Rapeseed is harvested when the plants are bent, the whole chain acquires a rusty yellow color, the sheaths are yellow-lilac, and on most seeds there is a brown spot.

Harvesting is carried out mechanically, in two phases, or directly with the grain combine. (Sims, 1979)

Harvesting in two phases is performed when the plants are yellow, and the seeds have started to turn brown and have a humidity of 25-30%. Cutting the plants in the ripening phase in the lever (yellow color of the silica and the seed with browning beginning) is done with the vindrover and remain on the stubble 25-30 cm high, until the seeds mature (until they reach a humidity of 12-14%) .

After a few days, when the seeds reach full maturity and the humidity decreases to 12-14%, the plants are threshed on the go with the combine, cutting the stubble under the rapeseed furrow, making the necessary changes to prevent the loss and breaking or peeling of the seeds. .

The direct harvest with the combine will be carried out 5 - 7 days after the application of the Reglone desiccant, 2 - 3 l / ha and 150 - 200 l of water, in the phase when the siliceous turned yellow-lilacs and the coloring of the seeds started. At the time of harvest, the seed moisture should be around 16%. The work is performed in the evening, in the morning and during the night.

The seeds are immediately cleaned and dried at a humidity of 9-10%. When immediate drying cannot be ensured, the storage will be done in layers of 5 - 10 cm, with the capsule on, and will be shoveled until the humidity drops to 10%. (Muste, 2002)

The obtained productions are between 2.000 – 4.000 kg / ha. The average rapeseed production in Europe in recent years has been around 2,800 kg / ha. The ratio between seed and straw production is 1: 1.5 - 2.0.

THE TEHNOLOGICAL PROCESS OF OBTAINING BIODIESEL

Agricultural crops used for the production of biofuels and biomass energy are called energy crops. Romania's potential in biomass energy production is estimated at 65% of the total green energy potential. (Brighila, 2015). 75% of the world's biodiesel is produced in European Union countries, with Germany producing over 50%, meaning 1.03 million tonnes in 2004. (17th International Congress for Renewable Mobility "Fuels of the Future", 2020)

World biofuel production has increased by an average of 11.4% in the last ten years. Biodiesel production increased by 4% in 2018, the main countries supplying biodiesel are mainly Indonesia, India, China, Norway, Hong Kong, Argentina taking the lead in the production and supply of rapeseed biodiesel to EU countries. The biodiesel market is expected to grow remarkably between 2018 and 2023 (Figure1.)

Fig. 1. Global demand for biodiesel in transport
(Source: Oyetola and Noor 2019)

An analysis of the European Commission's agricultural data shows that 53% of the raw materials used to produce biodiesel from crops in the EU in 2015 (approx. 3400 trillion liters) were imported. In 2016, 33% of biodiesel in EU crops comes from imported palm oil. (Figure 2.)

Fig.2. Raw material used for biodiesel production (2009-2016)
(Source: <https://www.transportenvironment.org/press/around-half-eu-production-crop-biodiesel-based-imports-not-crops-grown-eu-farmers-new-analysis>)

Due to the fact that between 2005 and 2015, total consumption of vegetable oil in the EU decreased in the food sector (from 15.1 to 13.7 million tonnes), while bioenergy production increased 4 times (from 2.9 to 10.5 million tonnes), mainly due to biodiesel, produced in proportion of 60% from rapeseed. Also, the production from oil residues predominates, to the detriment of crude oil. (<https://www.transportenvironment.org/press/around-half-eu-production-crop-biodiesel-based-imports-not-crops-grown-eu-farmers-new-analysis>)

So, it can be noticed that there is a growing trend in rapeseed areas in Europe and a growing concern for the economic efficiency of rapeseed biodiesel production.

The process of obtaining biodiesel is very easy, involving a reaction of a vegetable oil with an alcohol (methanol), in the presence of a catalyst, resulting an ester (biodiesel) and glycerin. This ester can replace diesel fuel in most diesel engines. It is biodegradable, renewable and non-toxic, with a low level of pollutants. (Baldini et al., 2003). In the case of biodiesel produced from rapeseed, the raw material can be pure (crude) oil or various residues from the oil.

The process of obtaining biodiesel from pure oil. Pure vegetable oil is an oil produced from oilseeds by pressing, extraction or comparable processes, crude or refined, but not chemically modified. Of these, rapeseed is best suited for biofuel.

To obtain crude oil from rapeseed before pressing, it is necessary to clean, dry, peel (resulting in husks, ash and furfural) ground and burned. (Găgeanu, 2012) After pressing results crude press oil which is the raw material for biodiesel, and broken cakes. (Figure 3.)

Fig.3 The process of obtaining oil and residues

After the purification of the rapeseed oil, in order to obtain the biodiesel it is necessary to go through the following steps:

Transesterification (Ingendoh, 2010) is the chemical reaction between an ester (vegetable oil) and an alcohol (Methanol) in the presence of a catalyst (KOH - Potassium Hydroxide)

1. The purification of the resulting material will be performed by sedimentation..

2. Washing with acidic water to remove any free fatty acids left after transesterification. (Brighila, 2015)

3. Wash with neutral water to reduce acidity after acid washing.

4. Drying - heating the biodiesel to 130⁰C to evaporate the water content.

The process of obtaining biodiesel from waste. The technological process is cheaper, due to the low price for the raw material, but it involves additional steps (Turck, 2003), being more complicated than in the case of using pure oil:

1. Separation of fatty acids from residues: the reaction takes place in the presence of an acid (96% concentrated sulfuric acid) and steam (up to a temperature of 100 °C) the result being fatty acids and acidic water.

2. Sedimentation causes fatty acids to rise to the surface and acidic water to settle to the bottom

3. The process of esterification under pressure using an acid (Methanesulfonic acid) and an alcohol (Methanol) the result being the crude ester and water. This reaction takes place at a pressure of 5 bar and a temperature of 130 °C. (Ingendoh, 2010)

4. The crude ester refining process: here the glycerin phase of the tranesterification process will be used to reduce free fatty acids. (Turck, 2003)

5. The process of tranesterification of crude ester

6. Purification of biodiesel.

7. Acid washing.

8. Neutral washing.

9. Drying of biodiesel.

Given the agrotechnics of rapeseed cultivation and the technological process of obtaining biodiesel, there is the problem of identifying possibilities to increase economic efficiency given the quantity and quality of biodiesel produced.

The economic efficiency of biofuel production is largely influenced by the amount of vegetable oils and their derivatives and last but not least by the quality of diesel substitutes. The quantity of vegetable oils is directly dependent on the economic efficiency of the agricultural farm, and implicitly on the price of the production of raw material (seeds) for the production of biodiesel. (Mateoc – Sîrb et al., 2013)

The quality of biodiesel obtained, either from crude oil or from oil residues can be assessed by laboratory analysis of physicochemical properties, such as: ester content, density, flash point, CFPP (limit of filterability), cloud point, sulfur content, ash content, water content, total contamination, oxidation stability, acidity value, iodine value, Linolenic acid-methyl ester content (C18: 0), methanol content, monoglyceride - diglyceride - triglyceride content, content of free glycerin, total glycerin content, alkali metal content (Na + K), alkaline earth metal content (Ca + Mg), phosphorus content. (Beșleagă et al., 2015)

CONCLUSIONS

Biodiesel production has increased significantly in Europe even in Romania. Rapeseed, the energy plant from which the best biodiesel is produced, was cultivated in Romania in 2018 on 611 thousand ha.

Agricultural rapeseed production is directly dependent on soil and climatic conditions (climate, topography and especially soil fertility) and last but not least on the applied cultivation technologies. Among the important technological links are: the quantity of seed used for sowing, the density of plants at the end of winter (Bîlteanu, 2001; Georgescu et al., 2015) and especially the applied fertilization system (Hălmăjan et al., 2007; Muntean et al., 2014)

Studies have shown that the administration of high doses of single nitrogen does not always lead to an increase in the production of rapeseed, nor to an increase in the amounts of oil obtained. (Béřeš et al., 2019) being necessary the application in complex with the other fertilizing elements. The importance of sulfur fertilization was also detached (Poisson et al., 2019) indicating the S: N ratio of 1: 7

High doses of applied phosphorus to rapeseed cultivation increase the content of oil and protein and cause faster maturation of plants. (Bailey and Grant, 1990). The export of potassium from the soil with rape seed is reduced to about 30 - 60 kg / ha K₂O, but nevertheless insufficient intake of K severely restricted plant growth. (Orlovius, 2016)

Therefore, the efficiency of rapeseed production, and implicitly of the amount of oil obtained, implies the application of a balanced fertilization system. The biodiesel produced from waste is more common than that produced from pure oil, but the applied technology involves a greater number of steps in the case of waste.

The quality of the biodiesel obtained depends, first of all, on the applied technological process, from crude oil and / or from oil residues. It can be estimated that in the first case a high quality biodiesel results, compared to the one obtained from residues, but the price of rapeseed is higher than the price of oil residues. Also a particular importance are the production costs, the price / quality ratio being decisive.

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IMPORTANCE OF COOPERATION FOR SMALL FARMERS IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

At national level, agriculture is the basic branch of Romania's economy that has a more important role in the economy of our country than in other European countries because Romania has a very high agricultural potential, but it is insufficiently used by Romanian farmers. Following the studies and analyses, we believe that there are many factors that influence the development and consolidation of agricultural farms, which influence the profitability of agricultural farms, the most important factors, the technical factors, natural factors, and, last but not least, the weather factors that determine wide oscillations of agricultural productions each year. Only by solving these problems can be achieved maximum possible yields and a development and consolidation of family farms in Romania, comparable to those in developed EU countries, capable of ensuring the food safety and security of the population, of providing raw material for the manufacturing industry and for many other industries of Romania's economy and related activities needed to be developed and, at the same time, to be able to provide export products.

Key words: small farmers, agriculture, cooperation, growth, efficiency

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays agriculture, as a vital branch of the national economy through its social and economic functions of ensuring the need for food for the population, the quantities of raw material for the processing industry and also for other industries, of ensuring sufficient production of agri-food products for export and of contributing to the development of rural areas in a sustainable way is also ground by a profound crisis of production, structure, organization and management. (Brînzan et. al, 2020)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This article analyses the evolution of agricultural farms on size classes and highlights the role of agricultural cooperatives in Romania for small farmers. The evolution of cooperatives is presented by counties and development regions. As a working methodology, the research of available statistical data was used and published at national level. Information collected

on the basis of bibliographic sources and national studies have been processed and analysed. For analysis and study, quantitative and qualitative analysis methods have been combined to better understand the problem studied and to formulate relevant results and conclusions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At national level, agriculture is the basic branch of Romania's economy that plays a more important role in the economy of the country than in other European countries because Romania has a very high agricultural potential that is insufficiently used by Romanian farmers. (Ciolac et al., 2021)

Statistical data confirms that agriculture is one of the few sectors of our economy that ranks Romania first in European tops, in terms of the cultivated area and, at the same time, in the production of cereal crops and oil plant crops. (Iancu, 2013)

Romanian farmers are facing fiscal, economic, and financial blockage, which create great financial problems impeding from resuming the production cycle and leading to bankruptcy. (Florea et al., 2017)

Although, in economy, we know the role and importance of commercial farms from a social point of view, it is very important to put special emphasis on small farms (up to 5 ha) because they represent 91.8% of the total Romanian holdings and use 28.7% of Romania's useful agricultural area (UAA), playing a particularly important role in the life of the inhabitants of our country. (Oțiman et al., 2013)

Since 1990, Romania's agriculture has been facing different economic and social issues and problems: the existence of numerous non-viable small farms (economically inefficient), excessive land plotting in small farms on the one hand and the emergence of large and high agricultural farms (of corporate type), on the other hand – great land owner holdings. (Mateoc-Sîrb, 1999) Thus, in 2016, 12,310 farms of over 100 ha, i.e., 0.36% of the total Romanian farms of 3.422.030, hold a share of 47.78% of Romania's UAAs (12,502,000 ha), respectively 5.973. 450 ha of agricultural land, and **2,480,770 farms below 2 ha, i.e., 72.49% of the total farms, used 12.32% of the total UAAs, i.e., 1,539,790 ha of agricultural land.**

These small farms provide the need for self-consumption in the vast majority of Romanian villages. This is the main reason for cooperating these farmers to achieve a level of economic development and efficiency that allows decent living, which makes it a mandatory necessity.

Table 1

Agricultural farms per size categories in Romania

Size categories	Indices		
	Number of agricultural holdings	Used agricultural area (ha)	Used agricultural area / holding (ha)
< 2 ha	2,480,770	1,539,790	0.62
%	72.49	12.32	-
2 - 5 ha	660,000	2,048,620	3.10
%	19.29	16.39	-
5 - 50 ha	262,930	2,522,230	9.59
%	7.73	20.17	-
50 -100 ha	6,010	418,450	69.62
%	0.17	3.35	-
>100 ha	12,310	5,973,450	485.25
%	0.36	47.78	-
Total	3,422,030	12,502,540	3.65

Source: APIA

Regarding the number of farmers by area categories, the data in Table 1 confirm that there is a concentration of farms up to 50 ha. Thus 91.3% of holdings up to 50 ha, respectively 823,119 holdings use an area of about 3,700,000 ha, i.e., 40.28% of the UAAs, and **2,427 holdings above 500 ha (0.27% of the total), exploit 2,850,000 ha of the UAAs, i.e., 31.07%.**

Fig. 1 Number of agricultural farms per size categories in Romania

Fig. 2 Agricultural area used by farms by size categories in Romania

For the economic development of agriculture of the two sectors, vegetal and animal, a policy of concentrating land, in particular small farms, is required by the establishment of agricultural cooperatives.

Neither *Law 566 from 2004 of Agricultural Cooperation* long waited by small farmers who should have solved some of their problems contributing to the organization of appropriate agricultural structures that can compete with the developed EU countries, nor *Law 1 from 2005 of Cooperation*, unfortunately, does not solve the major problems rooted in the establishment of agricultural cooperatives for small farmers.

These issues are related to the facility of access to European funding and the possibility of investing in cooperatives, the issue of the land fund, and the existence of tax facilities or, rather, the elimination of tax barriers to the establishment of cooperatives.

The way of defining “agricultural cooperative” would be an important element in the context of access to European funding. In this case, a cooperative would be assimilated to a farmer, agricultural producer, and the agricultural size of the holding of a cooperative should be made up of the size of the farms of the cooperative members.

There are also legislative proposals such as:

- Reduction of profit tax;
- Exemption from the payment of the property tax of cooperative members;
- Removal of double taxation applied to commercial transactions made by cooperative members through cooperatives.

The grouping of producers and the establishment of cooperatives for the supply, storage, processing and sales of agri-food products for, primarily, economic reasons, have not been achieved as expected through the National Rural Development Program of Romania – the program for the creation of producer groups is so far a failure. The explanation of this reticence is, first

of all, a matter of the *poor economic performance of small (but also medium agricultural holdings of subsistence and semi-subsistence), of precarious management and of eluding taxation in the case of non-grouped farmers*

Table 2

Situation of agricultural cooperatives in Romania in 2015

Nr. Crt.	County	Agricultural cooperatives per county	Region	Total agricultural cooperatives per region
1.	Bacău	9	Nord - Est	171
2.	Botoșani	104		
3.	Iași	9		
4.	Neamț	8		
5.	Suceava	27		
6.	Vaslui	14		
7.	Brăila	9	Sud - Est	97
8.	Buzău	15		
9.	Constanța	34		
10.	Galați	8		
11.	Tulcea	3		
12.	Vrancea	28		
13.	Argeș	7	Sud - Muntenia	131
14.	Călăraș	27		
15.	Dâmbovița	27		
16.	Giurgiu	7		
17.	Ialomița	19		
18.	Prahova	14		
19.	Teleorman	30		
20.	Dolj	21	Sud- Vest Oltenia	57
21.	Gorj	3		
22.	Mehedinți	6		
23.	Olt	18		
24.	Vâlcea	9		
25.	Arad	19	Vest	57
26.	Caraș -Severin	16		
27.	Hunedoara	6		
28.	Timiș	16		
29.	Bihor	19	Nord-Vest	117
30.	Bistrița- Năsăud	18		
31.	Cluj	30		
32.	Maramureș	12		
33.	Satu- Mare	25		
34.	Sălaj	13		
35.	Alba	15	Centru	88
36.	Brașov	32		
37.	Covasna	7		
38.	Harghita	20		
39.	Mureș	10		
40.	Sibiu	4	București - Ilfov	25
41.	București	11		
42.	Ilfov	14		
43.			TOTAL România	743

Source: After the Romanian Centre for European Policy – Agricultural Cooperatives

Table 2 presents the situation of agricultural cooperatives per Romanian counties and development regions.

From the analysis of the data, we find that, in North-East Region, there were 171 agricultural cooperatives ranking first place in 2015, and in South-Muntenia Region operated a number of 131 agricultural cooperatives. There were 117 cooperatives in the North-West Region, ranked third of the total cooperatives registered at national level of 743.

It is important for these cooperatives to develop in the agri-food sector, especially in the small and medium-sized farms segment, which, through these structures, could be able to play an important role in the agri-food market, at least nationally in the ensuring basic products for the population, and with the possibility of expanding European markets.

CONCLUSIONS

1. *Whereas the structure and size of Romania's farms are not yet comparable to the family farms of the EU Member States, we consider that some legislative decisions are required to adjust the farm structure, especially those of small and medium size, such as:*

- Stimulating the cooperation and association of small family farms in upstream and downstream activities of agricultural production;
- Stimulating the development of economically efficient family farms;
- Stimulating agricultural households by young farmers eager to develop the farm according to modern principles;
- Encouraging farmers to produce in the organic farming system;
- Reducing the number of plots of properties by merging land and ensuring an appropriate infrastructure in extra-villa, etc.;

2. The development of agricultural cooperatives in Romania did not have the estimated success, recording a weak development in particular after 2000;

3. The lack of confidence of farmers in Romania in associative forms, first, because of the term “cooperative” which has had a negative connotation, reminiscent of communist farmers and property loss;

4. Also, the low level of trust and the level of suspicion in the correctness of people, existing at national level, can, to a certain extent, explain the poor development of Romanian cooperation;

5. Agricultural cooperatives, defined as autonomous and voluntary associations made up of several farmers pursuing economic, social or cultural objectives, represent a type of enterprise with a double goal: economic and social. Their activity is governed by cooperative principles, namely free and voluntary association, economic democracy, autonomy, transparency, solidarity, and concern for the community it belongs to;

6. For the proper functioning of agricultural cooperatives on the agri-food market, it is necessary to identify the forms of incentives regarding the number of cooperatives by creating a legislative framework appropriate to this area;

7. In rural areas in Romania, cooperatives have a determining role because they can contribute to the stability of the rural population in the socio-economic balance of rural areas.

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SELECTIVITY AND EFFICIENCY OF SOME HERBICIDES IN THE WHEAT CULTURE DEPENDING ON THE MOMENT OF APPLICATION

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Abstract

In the spring of 2021, it has been made some research on the application of some herbicides at SCDA Livada: Bizon 1l/ha, Trinity SC 2l/ha and Joystick 200g/ha, BBCH 30-32, in spring, these herbicides being recommended to be applied in the post emergence.

The application in autumn of these herbicides reduces the competition between weeds and culture plants for nutrients and water from the early stages of growth providing a better emergence of the cereal, but because of the weather conditions in the autumn of 2020, we have opted for the spring application of Bizon, Trinity SC and Joystick herbicides.

Key words: wheat, application stage, selectivity and efficiency of herbicides, production.

INTRODUCTION

The synthesis and launching on the market of new herbicides against weeds upon the straw cereals culture is a main concern of global researchers and in our country, as well.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The research was carried out on the experimental field, being done on a gleyed preluvosoil with a 5.1 pH, a 20.9% of clay content and 2.8 content of humus, the wheat culture sowed was Glosa.

The sowing was done according to the randomized blocks method, the cultivated surface being of 21 m², four types of herbicides in three doses. It was used 500 l/ha in spring at the appearance of the first internode.

The experiment was monitoring the selectivity level of wheat culture and the fighting level against annual and evergreen monocots and dicotyledons weeds while applying the mentioned herbicides (Table 1).

Table 1

Herbicides applied on the wheat culture in 2021

No. Var	Herbicides	Doses l,kg/ha	Active substance
1	Untreated	-	-
2	Bizon	1	diflufenican100g/l+penoxulam15g/l+ florasulam 3,75g/l
3	Trinity SC	2	pendimetalin300g/l+diflufenican40g/l+clortoluron250g/l
4	Joystick	0,2	iodosulfuron50g/kg+florasulam20g/kg+diflufenican400g/kg

The agricultural year of 2020-2021 ended up with an average temperature of 11⁰C and a sum of rainfall of 1010.7 l/m² from September 2020 until August 2021. The absolute temperatures of -13.5⁰C and -14.7⁰C were registered in January and February.

The highest temperature of 35.9⁰C was recorded in June 2021, when there were 11 days of high temperatures of more than 30⁰C. In comparison with the previous years, spring was colder and wetter than usual. March, April and May were under the multi annual levels with 0.9⁰C; 2.1⁰C and respectively with 1.4⁰C.

The rainfall regime was rich, registering over 1000 mm of precipitations in that year (1010.7 mm). October 2020 was very rich in precipitations with 117.1 mm (with 61.8 mm over the normal values); January and February with 46 respectively 77.2 mm of precipitations over the multi annual average, but also April and May months in which the level of rainfall exceeded 100 l/ m² (107.8 in April and 111.0 in May), (Table 2).

Overall, the climatic conditions of the 2020-2021 agricultural year were favourable for the autumn and spring straw cereals.

Table 2

Meteorological data in Livada weather station in the 2020-2021 year

Specification		IX	X	XI	XII	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	Total per agricultural year.
Temperature °C	Decade I	17.6	15.2	7.4	4.5	2.9	4.8	2.7	6.4	12.6	17.1	22.3	21.3	
	Decade II	18.9	10.5	5.7	3.8	-3.6	-2.6	4.0	8.5	15.3	20.6	24.9	21.0	
	Decade III	15.5	10.7	0.1	5.2	2.8	5.0	4.8	10.4	15.2	25.2	23.1	17.3	
	Absolute minimum	3.6	3.5	-6.2	-8.4	-13.5	-14.7	-5.6	-1.4	3.0	5.2	13.6	9.1	
	Absolute maximum	30.4	26.0	17.1	15.1	10.9	17.4	16.8	22.7	29.3	35.9	34.8	33.8	
	No of days with $T^0 \geq 30^0C$	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11	19	8	41
	No of days with $T^0 \leq -10^0C$	0	0	0	0	3	2	0	0	0	0			5
	Monthly average	17.3	12.1	4.4	4.5	0.7	2.4	3.8	8.4	14.4	21.0	23.4	19.9	
	Normal average	15.4	9.8	4.8	0.1	-2.2	0.1	4.7	10.5	15.8	19.0	20.5	19.9	
Normal difference \pm	1.9	2.3	-0.4	4.4	-1.5	2.3	-0.9	-2.1	-1.4	2.0	2.9	0		
Rainfall mm	Decade I	20.4	45.2	5.6	2.4	50.3	78.8	2.6	64.4	22.8	1.1	39.2	22.4	355.2
	Decade II	0	43.2	4.8	18.7	16.4	41.0	25.1	23.5	74.2	7.6	32.5	10.0	297.0
	Decade III	79.7	28.7	6.0	64.8	27.0	0	5.9	19.9	14.0	35.1	10.7	66.7	358.5
	Total monthly	100.1	117.1	16.4	85.9	93.7	119.8	33.6	107.8	111	43.8	82.4	99.1	1010.7
	Multiannual average	65.0	55.3	55.6	60.0	47.7	42.6	46.7	48.9	76.8	93.3	81.8	74.6	748.3
	Normal difference \pm	35.1	61.8	-39.2	25.9	46.0	77.2	-13.1	58.9	34.2	-49.5	0.6	24.5	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the vegetation period, after the herbicidal treatment, there were done some observations concerning the level of selectivity and efficiency upon the weeds from the wheat culture.

The selectivity of the tested herbicides in what concerns the wheat culture was marked according to the visual observations after the EWRS scale (from 1 to 9 grades; 1= selective, 9=phytotoxic), (Table 3).

The appreciation of the herbicides efficiency was done numbering the weed species per m² in each version.

Joystick herbicide 200g/ha which was used in spring assures a 100% efficiency, and the application of Bizon herbicide 1l/ha and TrinitySC 2l/ha have an efficiency of 99% respectively 98% in comparison with the untreated part, (Table 3).

Table 3

Selectivity and efficiency of herbicide treatments on the wheat culture in 2021

No. Var	Herbicides	Doses l,kg/ha	Period of application	Selectivity EWRS grades	Efficiency %
1	Untreated	-	-	-	-
2	Bizon	1	Post	1	99
3	Trinity SC	2	Post	1	98
4	Joystick	0.2	post	1	100

Untreated

Treated

Fig. 1 Image from the experimental field SCDA Livada in 2021

The production while analyzing the alternatives shows a positive influence of Joystick herbicide with 0.2 kg/ha surplus extra production to the untreated culture of 5.33q/ha. Bizon 1l/ha and Trinity SC 2l/ha give an increase production but these increases are not ensured statistically, (Table 4).

Table 4

The influence of the herbicides treatment upon the wheat culture in 2021

No. Var.	Herbicides	Doses l, kg/ha	Period of application	Production q/ha	Difference +/- towards Mt	Significance
1	Untreated	-	-	66.28	-	-
2	Bizon	1	Post	68.00	1.71	-
3	Trinity SC	2	Post	69.90	3.62	-
4	Joystick	0.2	post	71.62	5.33	x

LSD 5% = 4.99 q/ha LSD 1% = 7.55 q/ha LSD 0.1% = 12.13 q/ha

CONCLUSIONS

In the experiment that was carried out at SCDA in Livada, while in post emergence using Bizon 1l/ha, Trinity SC 2l/ha and Joystick 200g/ha herbicides, these are recommended to be used in autumn because they have shown a very good selectivity and efficiency of the autumn wheat culture.

The best herbicide in tackling the weeds from the wheat culture was Joystick 200g/ha herbicide, this version gave a 100% efficiency.

The best result in what concerns the wheat production was obtained V4, a version that was treated with the Joystick herbicide, but the others such as Bizon and Trinity gave good results: 1.71 q/ha respectively 3.62 q/ha, these increase productions not being statistically ensured.

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REPRESENTATIVE TYPES OF SOIL FROM MIERSIG PLAIN

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Abstract

In the Crișurilor Plain, the excess rainfall of humidity is manifested on an area of over 18,847 ha, occupied by the type of stagnant soil. Representative areas are found in Miersig Plain - 3304.6 ha, Veljurilor Plain - 740.4 ha, Cermei Plain - 5395.1 ha, Craivei Plain- 9188.2 ha, Crișul Negru Plain - 217.8 ha. In addition to this type of soil, in the Miersig Plain we also find in a significant proportion, luvosol type soil.

Keywords: soil, plain, Miersig, clay.

INTRODUCTION

Located on a Carpathian foundation covered with Quaternary sediments (clays, clayey sands, fine and coarse sands, gravels etc.) on top of which the current landscape was formed, Crișurilor Plain comprises two main orographic stages: one high, from glaciers to hills and another low, alluvial, to the west.

At the level of the terraces the plain was formed as a result of an erosion process, facilitated by the vicinity of the Crișuri rivers. Although arranged in steps, the surface of the landscape is, on the whole, a slightly inclined plane, from 200 m, as many as are in the vicinity of the hills, up to 110 m towards the low plain.

The Miersig Plain is a Piedmont type of plain being in contact with the Crișul Negru Hills and Depressions. Thus, the Miersig Plain is part of the higher plains of the Western Plain, along with Carei, Ierului, Cernei, Arad, Vingăi and Gătaiei.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The present study aims at presenting the soil taxonomic units that are found at the level of the Miersig Plain.

The morphological, physico-chemical properties and the interpretation of the study are presented, these being included in the soil profile sheet.

The particle size analysis was performed by the Kacinski method, which involves separating the fractions by sieving (> 0.02 mm) or pipetting

(<0.02 mm), after a pre-treatment for dispersion with potassium hexametaphosphate (10%) in carbonate-free soil samples and organic matter below 5%; with hydrogen peroxide (6%) in carbonate - free soil samples with organic matter above 5% or in 2N hydrochloric acid and then with 1N sodium hydroxide solution during boiling in the case of carbonate soil samples. The results were expressed as a percentage of the material remaining after pretreatment.

Mobile phosphorus: by Egner-Riehm-Domingo method, by extraction in solution of ammonium lactate acetate at pH = 3.75. The phosphorus was measured colorimetrically with molybdenum blue-stannous chloride-ascorbic acid, according to the Nicolov method.

Potassium mobile: by extraction according to the Egner-Riehm-Domingo method and dosing by flame photometry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The soil types found in the constituent plains of the High Crişurilor Plain (including the Miersig Plain) are shown in Table 1.

Table 1
Areas occupied by different soil taxonomic units in the High Plain of Crişuri by subunits (according to SRTS-2012).

Soil taxonomic units	Plain subunits (areas occupied by soil types)					
	Bihariei Plain	Bihariei Field	Miersigului Plain	Veljurilor Plain	Cermeiului Plain	Craivei Plain
Total area	10354.2	1890.9	21496.6	21088.1	20940.2	16567.6
eutricambosols	3452.8	151.5	934.7	2448.6	1417.4	34.3
prelvisols	2854.2	728.1	2339.9	3296.4	742.4	-
phaeozems	2552.7	175.3	4639.4	2067.8	104.4	-
gleiosols	726.2	208.8	162.8	550.9	1533	1039.1
allvisols	108.4	566.4	885.9	469.7	4042.5	542.1
solonetz	55.6	32.7	-	-	762.0	-
Luvvisols	445.8	-	9211.1	3068.0	4426.9	2857.3
stagnosols	-	-	3304.6	740.4	5395.1	9188.2
vertisols	-	-			2497.2	23.6
plane soils	-	-			19.4	2882.9
Areas occupied by: rivers, lakes, canals, building						

PROFILE SHEET

REPRESENTATIVE PROFILE

Location: Bihor county, Miersig commune

Soil taxonomic unit: Luvosolalbicstagnic, clay, fine sandy clay, medium clay (SRTS), StagnicLuvvisols (WRB-SR-1998), Epiaquic Hapludalfs (USDA-ST-1999).

Layers profile: Ao – Ea – EBw – Bt – BC – C

Microrelief: negative profile

Soil appearance: normal

Parental material: clay

Groundwater depth: 5-8 m.

Morphological traits

Ao Layer: from 0 → 18 cm deep (25 cm thick), wet brownish gray (10YR5/2) and dry yellowish brownish gray (10YR6 / 2), grainy, disturbed by cultivation, fine, firm sandy clay wet, hard dry, poor plastic, poor adhesive, reclaimed.

Ea Layer: 18 → 34 cm deep (16 cm thick), wet yellowish gray (10YR6 / 2) and dry light yellowish gray (10YR7 / 2), unstructured, fine sandy clay, firmly wet, hard in the dry state, weakly plastic, weakly adhesive, moderately compact, damp.

EBw Layer: from 34 → 55 cm deep (24 cm thick), rusty yellowish brown (10YR5 / 4) with 25% reduction colors in the wet state and light hue brown in the dry state (10YR6 / 4), polyhedral angular, clay medium, firmly moist, hard in the dry state, weakly plastic, weakly adhesive, weakly moderate-compact.

Bt1w Layer : from 55 → 70 cm depth yellowish brown with rusty shades (10YR5 / 4) with 25% discount colors in the wet state and light brown in the dry state (10YR6 / 4), prismatic, medium clay, firm in the state wet, hard dry, poor plastic, poor adhesive, poor moderate-compact, reclaimed.

Bt2 Layer: from 70 → 110 cm deep (22 cm thick), wet brown yellow (10YZ5 / 6) and light brown dry yellow (10YR6 / 6), prismatic, well developed, firmly wet, hard in the dry state.

Table 2

Analytical data of the soil from Miersigului Plain

Layers	Ao	Ea	EBw	Bt1w	Bt2
Depths (cm)	0-18	18-34	34-55	55-70	70-140
Coarse sand% (2-0.2 mm)	6.1	4.4	5.6	2.3	1.6
Fine sand% (0.2-0.02 mm)	30.8	45.5	29.9	29.5	30.4
Dust% (0.02-0.002)	38.7	26.7	33.5	18.5	19.4
Clay (less than 0.002 mm)	24.4	23.4	31.0	49.7	48.6
Texture	LP	LL	LP	AL	AL
Water Ph	6.1	5.8	5.9	6.3	6.6
Humus	1.97	1.74	1.12	-	-
Total nitrogen%	0.098	0.087	-	-	-
Mobile phosphorus (ppm)	5.7	5.7	-	-	-
Mobile potassium (ppm)	50	40	-	-	-
Amount of exchange bases (me / 100 g. Soil)	14.4	14.4	-	-	-
Hydrolytic acidity (me / 100 g soil)	5.8	5.9	-	-	-
Degree of saturation in bases%	68.57	67.60	-	-	-

Interpretation of analytical data

-*texture*: it is medium in the first 34 cm.

-*soil reaction*: it is moderately acidic on 0-55 cm.

-*humus content*: it is small on the depth of 0-18 cm., reserve on ad. 0-50 cm of 137.9t / ha

-*nitrogen content*: it is very low

-*Potassium content*: it is small in all depth, poor supply

-*phosphorus content*: it is small on the depth of 0-18cm, poor supply

CONCLUSIONS

- Miersigului Plain is part of the High Crișuri Plain, occupying a total area of 21496.6 ha.
- The soil taxonomic units that dominate in the Miersig Plain are: preluvosols, phaeozomes, luvosols, stagnosols.
- The soil has a predominantly acidic character, poor in salts and minerals (predominantly in the surface layers).

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RESEARCH REGARDING COMPETITION IN PURE AND MIXED CULTURE BROMUS INERMIS AND MEDICAGO SATIVA

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Abstract

*The sown meadows are of particular importance in increasing the productivity and quality of the fodder obtained. Sown meadows are usually associated crops of poaceae and perennial legumes that are equally suitable for organic or intensive cultivation, depending on their structure. The research carried out between 2016 and 2020 aimed at the behavior of associated and pure cultures of *Medicago sativa* and *Bromus inermis* in uniform technological conditions. The highest DM productions were obtained for *B.inermis* monoculture in the third year of establishment (2019), which is explained by the tolerance by this species of unfavorable conditions, respectively drought. Regarding the evolution of the floristic composition of the mixtures cultivated under the conditions of a uniform technology, it is necessary to emphasize the fact that in the culture associated with *M.sativa* + *B.inermis* as the years pass the participation of legumes in the structure of the vegetal carpet decreases not by sown grass (*D.glomerata* or *B.inermis*), but by species belonging to other botanical families. The amount of crude protein varies between 1300.2 - 2285.70 kg / ha, the lowest value being recorded in the pure culture of *Bromus inermis*, and the highest value was in the monoculture of *Medicago sativa* (2020).*

Keywords: productivity, grassland, dry matter, associated crops

INTRODUCTION

Many researchers have studied sown meadows, developing recommendations for growing perennial fodder plants. Frame, 2000, emphasizes the role of sown meadows in Eastern European agriculture, appreciating that mixtures of grasses and corn for silage are the basic fodder for many EU countries. In general, in the countries of Western Europe, countries with a highly developed livestock sector, the area occupied by sown meadows is constantly growing (Rotar, 2010, 2011). Obtaining high, constant and quality feed production is possible only by applying a complex of technological measures that will aim at overseeding degraded meadows and setting up cultivated meadows where the choice of species and varieties is an important element. Following the effect of nitrogen fertilizers applied in different doses on the dry matter content of different species of perennial grasses grown in pure culture and mixture, there is a decrease in dry matter content and an increase in water content (Carlier et al., 1998; Oprea et al. 1986). The productivity of grass mixtures with legumes gives higher yields

than grasses fertilized with 200N. (Mossimann et al. 1994, 2008. Cited by Şuteu Alina, 1997, Cardaşol et al. 1987, Samuil et al. 2009, 2010; Rotar et al. 2014).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The experiment was established in 2016 and carried out over a period of four years (2017 - 2020), in which the behavior of some species of perennial grasses and legumes in specific technological conditions was studied. The experience includes 4 variants, in 4 repetitions, arranged in randomized blocks. The surface of a plot is 20 m².

This experiment was set up in the spring of 2016 on a plowed land from the autumn of the previous year and where the basic fertilization was done with 80 kg / ha P₂O₅ and 80 kg / ha K₂O, uniform in all experimental variants, and the spring before sowing they carried out the work of preparing the germination bed and the administration of nitrogen fertilizers (100 kg / ha N) for the variants sown with grasses in pure culture, following that these variants will be administered 50 kg / ha after each mowing. In the year of establishment, due to the fact that from a climatic point of view and also in order to obtain a well-coagulated and hollow plant carpet, only uniformity harvests were carried out, thus achieving a control of weeds in these crops. During the vegetation, a series of observations were made regarding the emergence, growth and development of plants, the dates of the start of vegetation in spring, the degree of weeding, the entry and exit of winter, the persistence of some species sown in the vegetation and their degree of dominance. Harvesting was done at plot level, in the first year when the legumes fully bloomed, and in the following years when the legumes sprouted and the grasses sprouted. The green mass crop was transformed into SU and statistically processed according to the variance analysis method.

Objectives pursued were: estimating the productive potential of simple mixtures of perennial grasses and legumes in order to ensure economic exploitation; the influence of differentiated nitrogen fertilization of grass and legume mixtures on the evolution of the carpet and on the chemical composition of the feed and the obtaining of a high quality feed. The annual average temperature was 10.17⁰C and the annual average rainfall of 566.3 mm.

Soil - Chernozem, cambic subtype, on clays, sandy-clayey clay on medium clay (SRTS), Haplic Chernozems (WBR-SR-1998), Typic Haplustosolls (USDA-ST-1999)

Succession of horizons: ***Am – Bv – C***

Table 1.

Analytical data

Horizons	Am ₁	Am ₂	B _v	C
Coarse sand % (2-0,2mm)	0-25	25-48	48-78	78-100
Fine sand % (0,2-0,02mm)	0,50	0,50	0,40	0,20
Dust % (0,02-0,002mm)	61,7	51,70	60,10	56,10
Physical clay % (sub 0,01 mm)	13,1	18,00	12,10	19,40
Texture	LN	LL	LN	LL
Carbonates	-	-	-	-
Ph in water	7,1	7,25	6,75	7,85
Humus	2,13	1,40	-	-
Total nitrogen %	0,105	0,070	-	-
Mobile phosphorus (ppm)	12	3	-	-
Mobile Potassium (ppm)	120	130	-	-
Amount of exchange bases (me./100 g. sol)	18,3	-	-	-
Exchangeable hydrogen	3,0	-	-	-
Degree of saturation in bases	96	-	-	-

Interpretation of analytical data - the texture is medium; the soil reaction is neutral at a depth of 0-48 cm and slightly alkaline at a depth of 78-100 cm; the nitrogen content is small at a depth of 0-25 cm and very low at a depth of 25-48 cm; the potassium content is low; sum of exchange bases: is small, degree of saturation in bases: indicates a eubasic soil.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The highest level of DM production was obtained in 2018, and the lowest in 2019. We consider that these large and relatively constant productions in the three experimental years are due to nitrogen fertilization. kg / ha / year applied after each mowing.

Fig.1 DM harvest t / ha on repetitions in the studied crops (2017-2020)

Analyzing statistically the data obtained in the three experimental years, it can be observed that in the pure culture of *B.inermis* were obtained differences of production ensured as distinctly significant positive, in 2019 the harvest of DM obtained being 10.23 t / ha DM. We can say that this level of harvest obtained for the species *B.inermis* was, in general, due to the climatic conditions and drought of the last years, knowing that this species is recommended for the drier areas, with southern exposure. From the point of view of the floristic composition, the *B.inermis* species maintains a high percentage of participation in the vegetal carpet, during the three experimental years, respectively 88-86%, decreasing in the fourth year from sowing to a 54%. What we must emphasize is that in this experiment the monocultures of legumes were not fertilized with nitrogen-based chemical fertilizers. The basic fertilization was done at the land preparation with 80 kg / ha P_2O_5 and 80 kg / ha K_2O . The very good behavior of the *M. sativa* species can be noticed, which recorded in each experimental year with 2-4 t / ha the DM crops obtained from *M. sativa*, the latter being considered the most productive fodder legume.

Table 2

Influence of fertilization on dry matter yield (t/ha) (2018)

Variant	Yield t/ha	Diferencet	%	Semnificances
A1 Martor	7.05	0.00	100	Mt
A2 (<i>B.inermis</i>)	7.26	0.21	102.97	-
A3 (<i>M.sativa</i>)	10.64	3.59	150.92	***
A4 (<i>M.sativa</i> + <i>B.inermis</i>)	11.64	4.59	165.10	***

LSD (p 5%) = 1.11 LSD (p 1%) = 1.59 LSD (p 0.1%) = 2.35

Table 3

The yield differences among variants and their significance (2018)

Variant	Yield (t/ha)	Variants in order of increasing crop		
		2	3	4
		SU t/ha		
		7.26	10.64	11.64
A1 Martor	7.05	0.21	3.59	4.59
A2 (<i>B.inermis</i>)	7.26		3.38	4.38
A3 (<i>M.sativa</i>)	10.64			1.00
A4 (<i>M.sativa</i> + <i>B.inermis</i>)	11.64			

Table 4.

Influence of fertilization on dry matter yield (t/ha) (2019)

Variant	Yield t/ha	Diferenc et	%	Semnificances
A1 Martor	8.18	0.00	100	Mt
A2 (<i>B.inermis</i>)	10.23	2.05	125.06	**
A3 (<i>M.sativa</i>)	11.25	3.07	137.53	***
A4 (<i>M.sativa</i> + <i>B.inermis</i>)	11.96	3.78	143.21	***

LSD (p 5%) = 1,69 LSD (p 1%) = 2,43 LSD (p 0.1%) = 3,57

Table 5.

The yield differences among variants and their significance (2019)

Variant	Yield (t/ha)	Variants in order of increasing crop		
		2	3	4
		SU t/ha		
		10.23	11.25	11.96
A1 Martor	8.18	2.05	3.07	3.78
A1 (<i>B.inermis</i>)	10.23		1.02	1.73
A2 (<i>M.sativa</i>)	11.25			0.71
A3 (<i>M.sativa</i> + <i>B.inermis</i>)	11.96			

The evolution of the floristic composition in the conditions of a uniform technology demonstrates the very good persistence of the *M.sativa* species (98-73% dominance in the vegetal carpet) even in the IV year from the sowing. In the crop associated with *M.sativa* + *B.inermis*, statistically assured yields were obtained as very significant positive compared to the crops associated with pure crops. There is a difference in production between the associated culture of *M.sativa* + *B.inermis* and those obtained in the monocultures of *M.sativa* and *B. inermis*, but the difference is smaller than in the previous year. In 2020 (the fourth year after sowing) the yields decreased compared to previous years, however the monoculture of *M.sativa* obtained a yield increase of 2.08 t / ha, statistically assured as distinctly significant.

In the crop associated with *M.sativa* + *B.inermis*, statistically assured yields were obtained as very significant positive compared to the crops associated with pure crops. There is a difference in production between the associated culture of *M.sativa* + *B.inermis* and those obtained in the monocultures of *M.sativa* and *B. inermis*, but the difference is smaller than in the previous year. In 2020 (the fourth year after sowing) the yields decreased compared to previous years, however the monoculture of *M.sativa* obtained a yield increase of 2.08 t / ha, statistically assured as distinctly significant.

Table 6

Variant	Yield t/ha	Diferencet	%	Semnificances
A1 Martor	6.75	0.00	100	Mt
A2 <i>B.inermis</i>	7.71	0.96	114.22	-
A3 <i>M.sativa</i>	8.83	2.08	130.81	**
A4 <i>M.sativa</i> + <i>B.inermis</i>	7.85	1.10	116.29	*

LSD (p 5%) = 1,26 LSD (p 1%) = 1,82 LSD (p 0,1%) = 2,68

Table 7

Variant	Yield (t/ha)	Variants in order of increasing crop		
		2	3	4
		SU t/ha		
		7,71	8,83	7,85
A1 Martor	6,75	0,96	2,08	1,10
A2 <i>B.inermis</i>	7,71		1,12	0,14
A3 <i>M.sativa</i>	8,83			-0,98
A4 <i>M.sativa</i> + <i>B.inermis</i>	7,85			

Feed quality is a complex attribute to the shaping of which contributes a number of interdependent elements (chemical composition, digestibility, efficiency of use of digestion products), which determine the nutritional value and voluntary consumption, and finally its nutritional value.

Table 8

Chemical composition	Variant / Year					
	<i>B.inermis</i>		<i>M.sativa</i>		<i>M.sativa</i> + <i>B.inermis</i>	
CF %	29.35	29.30	27.42	29.56	28.44	28.90
F %	3.01	1.90	2.47	2.35	2.63	2.05
A %	8.33	9.10	9.92	12.05	8.72	10.72
ESN %	41.40	44.15	42.19	35.73	40.19	37.80
BP kg/ha	1300.2	1590.7	1915.20	2285.70	2218	2243

A remark should be made about the production of crude protein per hectare. As can be seen from the figures in Table 8, the production of crude protein per hectare in *B.inermis* monoculture satisfactorily fertilized with nitrogen amounts to significant values, between kg / ha 1300.2 - 1590.70 Kg / ha. Higher values are obtained for pure and associated crops of *M. sativa* and *B. inermis* (1915.20 - 2285.70 kg / ha and 2218 - 2243 kg / ha in the case of the associated crop). The crude protein content varies from year to year within very limited limits, these variations being significant, and the differences between species are influenced by the varieties used. Thus, in the case of *M.sativa* monoculture, the highest values of PB (1915,20 - 2285,70) were obtained, which are mainly due to the variety used (Madalina), a variety in which the percentage of crude protein is higher than to the other improved varieties.

CONCLUSIONS

The yields obtained from the pure crops of *M.sativa* and *B. inermis*, in all the three experimental years are between 7.26 - 11.25 t / ha SU, it was found that the highest yields of SU in conditions of non-fertilization with nitrogen were obtained for the monoculture of *M.sativa*, respectively 8.83 - 11.25 t / ha SU.

In the structure of the mixture of *M.sativa* + *B.inermis* can be observed some changes that are generated by the high competition capacity of the partners. It can be noticed that the *M.sativa* species has the highest dominance in the vegetal carpet, having a percentage of participation between 88-86%, and 54% in the fourth year of use. *B.inermis* has a low percentage of participation in the first 2 years of use (22-26%) while in the third year it reaches a dominance of 14% in the vegetation, while weeds occupy 38%.

The chemical composition of the feed obtained was influenced by the species used, but nitrogen fertilization influenced to some extent the chemical composition of the feed, so that there is a slight increase in the values of all constituents depending on the doses of nitrogen applied. However, it should be noted that although there is a slight increase in the amount of crude protein per hectare when applying nitrogen, it is of the same order of magnitude as that obtained under uniform technology.

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BIOACTIVE COMPONENTS OF ALLIUM URSINUM FROM TOMNATIC, CRAIULUI FOREST MOUNTAINS

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Abstract

This paper is based on studies conducted both in the field in the Craiului Forest Mountains but also on analyzes performed on soil and tincture of Allium Ursinum, collected, prepared and notified by us. The soil analyzes were performed in the OSPA Bihor laboratories, while the analyzes of the finished product were performed by the Bihor Public Health Directorate. The Allium Ursinum tincture studied in the DSP Bihor laboratories, comes from the plant harvested in the studied area from the Pădurea Craiului Mountains, namely from the area of Tomnatic village, Vadu Crișului commune, Bihor county. The allium ursinum, was harvested when the plant was maturing, when, according to specialists, the active principles of the plant are at maximum capacity to interact with the human body.

Key words: massive, spontaneous flora, climate, forest, allium ursinum

INTRODUCTION

The area, studied by us, corresponds from a qualitative point of view for the cultivation of medicinal plants and obtaining phytotherapeutic products: teas, tinctures, syrups, etc. The Pădurea Craiului Mountains area is an ecological area, unaffected by daily pollution only to a small extent. The results of the soil tests, made by OSPA Bihor specialists certify this. Soil structure is an important agronomic index, because it is a property on which some soil properties depend directly, especially the physical ones influencing the chemical and biochemical processes in the soil, the activity of microorganisms, the mobility of nutrients (Brejea, 2017). The Pădurea Craiului Mountains represent the compartment between the Crișului Repede and Crișului Negru valleys of the Apuseni Mountains, separated from Vlădeasa by the Iada and Meziad valleys, reaching the Tășadului Hills in the west, (Brejea, Domuța, 2009). Drumul Aștilenilor, the harvest point of bear's garlic is located at an altitude of 608 m, Latitude 46 54 41N and Longitude 22 26 46 E, in Tomnatic locality, Vadu Crisului commune.

Fig. 1. The road of the Aștilenilor- Tomnatic 2021

Fig. 2. The place of harvest of the Allium ursinum- Tomnatic 2021

At the same time, we managed to produce *Allium ursinum* tincture, and the analyzes made by the specialists of the Bihor Public Health Directorate confirm that the values of this tincture are clearly superior to other similar products existing on the shelves of specialty stores in Romania.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Allium ursinum, also called "wild garlic", grows in forests and its leaves, with a slight smell of garlic, are a rich source of health. For fresh food and preparation, the young, young leaves are harvested in March and April. The Latin name of the wild garlic is *Allium ursinum*. It is a medicinal plant that grows in the alpine area or in plains with fertile soil, loving moisture.

Strong healing forces lie in it and it is said that bears also look for it when they come out of hibernation to clean their stomachs, intestines and blood. Because the leaves lose their healing function in the dry state, *Allium ursinum* tincture is prepared by chopping the green leaves, which are mixed with alcohol at 40 degrees, which is then left to soak for two weeks, preferably near a heat source. *Allium ursinum*, has a favorable effect on the digestive

tract, colic, intestinal worms, worms, prevents insomnia, heart disorders, hypertension, also cleanses the kidneys and bladder, promoting urination (Treben, 2007). To see how well-known Allium ursinum is, we designed questionnaire on the degree of product satisfaction.

Do you live healthy?

136 answers

Do you use leurda?

138 answers

How do you use leurda?

117 answers

What influences you in using a product?

135 answers

Which manufacturers do you trust?

135 answers

AGE

140 answers

SEX

138 answers

Fig. 3. Question about the Allium ursinum

This product must be notified in order to be placed on the market. Consequently, Allium ursinum tincture was notified on the website of the European Commission (Cosmetic Product Notification Portal), where the data needed to approve the marketing of this product were presented.

REFERENCE CPNP: 3795490

REFERENCE INDUSTRIAL: 1

VERSION: 1

Date of first notification 03/10/2021 10:37:37

Date of last change: 03.10.2021 10:37:37

The name of the product Shades (If applicable) Language

Tincture of leurde

Romanian

ID: 89211

RESPONSIBLE PERSON: HERBAMON SRL

The address of the responsible person: Romania, Bihor, Oradea, 410211,

Phone: 0040740936045

E-mail: office@herbamon.ro

Contact person: Matei Mircea

The address of the contact person: Merilor, 410117 Oradea, Romania

F-mail: mircea.matei3@gmail.com

Product imported into the community: No.

Member State in which it was first placed on the market: Romania

Product details

Category level: 1

Physical forms: Liquid

Packaging: Pressurized container

Type of notification: exact concentrations

CMR

No one

NANOMATERIALS

No one

NAME

Capture 16.jpg

Original label: photo

original packaging: photo

Capture 17.jpg

Fig. 4. Product Notification Data

Fig. 5 Commercial Presentation Of The Product

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Allium ursinum tincture is a hydroalcoholic solution which makes it very easily assimilated by the body. Contains 1: 2 extract in hydroalcoholic solution (ethyl alcohol / water - 45/55 by mass) from Allium ursinum leaves.

It is recommended for; to fluidize the blood, keep the concentration of cholesterol in the blood within normal limits, against fat deposition on the walls of blood vessels, protect blood capillaries, prevent sclerosis of blood vessels and promote cerebral circulation, eliminate the discomfort that occurs in: venous system of the lower limbs and hemorrhoidal veins, eliminates excess fluid retained in the body, maintains blood pressure within normal limits, detoxifies the body and fights intestinal parasites, protective role of cells against oxidative stress.

Do not administer, in bleeding, pregnancy, lactation (Allium ursinum transmits an unpleasant taste to milk), intolerance to any of the components of the product. It is administered with caution to people undergoing treatment with anticoagulant drugs. In people with gastric sensitivity, it is recommended to administer the product after a meal. The product is administered internally, before use the product will be shaken. Keep well closed, protected from moisture and heat.

CONCLUSIONS

Due to the fact that it has been scientifically proven that natural products are good for the body and to reduce the consumption of medicines we recommend you to consume natural products from ecological areas.

At the same time, besides the fact that the products are of quality, the spontaneous flora and the soil are not polluted, you can enjoy a walk in nature, and if you don't do this, we recommend you to buy products from us. Products beneficial to your health.

In conclusion: Take care of your health!

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THE INFLUENCE OF TREATMENT GROWTH SUBSTANCES ON ROOTING OF THE AZALEEA INDICA

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Abstract

The azalea can multiply through seeds and vegetatively: seedlings, grafting, layering. More sensitive than Mimosa pudica and more beautiful than any adornment detached from nature by man, the azalea (Azaleea indica) gathers through its shapes a real symphony of colours and enchanting hues, of elegant shapes, having no rival in the flower world.

The widest reproduction method remains that through semilignified seedlings, a method that can be used throughout the year avoiding the months less favourable for propagation by seedlings, with poor light: November and October. The best results are given by the spring propagations by seedlings (February-March) and the summer propagations by seedlings (July-August). The rooting can last for 12-14 weeks until the seedlings can be transplanted in flower pots without risks.

A wide application in horticultural practice is the use of growth substances, that take part in the faster formation of roots and in a higher percent for species of plants, that, normally, root with difficulty through seedlings. Under this aspect, many synthetical compounds have proved to be very active (NAA, IAA, IBA, 2,4,5-T acid etc.) (Milica and all., 1983).

Key words: NAA, IAA, IBA, growth regulators, seedlings, rooting, growth substances

INTRODUCTION

The rooting medium that gave best results was sand from which the coarse and the fine fractions were removed. Transplants about 4–12 months old were used as ortets, some of them repeatedly (Flake and all., 1978). Single node cuttings with part of one leaf were tested. In early experiments “first top node” cuttings were much poorer than cuttings which included second or third nodes from the apex, it was too early to conclude how cuttings from lower down on the ortet would perform (Hare, 1984). There was some indication that better rooting occurred in cuttings from younger than older ortets (Halls, Lowell, 1977, Ross and all., 1983, Taiz, Zeiger, 2002).

The ornamental ligneous species can multiply vegetatively through propagation by seedlings, grafting, layering, separation of the bush, propagation by basal shoots. The most often used reproduction method in the case of most species is by seedlings, the material used for this type of reproduction being the seedlings, meaning those portions of the plant that, placed in favourable vegetation conditions according to the principle of

restitution, restore organisms that are identical with those of which they were harvested (Adams, 1987, Bandici, 2012, 2013).

Survival after potting of rooted cuttings ranged from 10 to 50% in spite of the several weaning periods and transplanting methods tried. The reason for this, the most important problem encountered, is not known. This transplanting phase is the highest priority for future work (Piney, 1970, Ormsbee and all., 1976, Peterson and all., 1979).

No clear trend resulted from tests of shading cuttings, though it seemed to promote rooting in younger “first top node” cuttings. Hormone treatment with NAA, IAA, and IBA suspended in talc seemed to have a negative effect, while IBA trended to promote rooting of “2nd top node” cuttings. In trials to date water stress seems to lower rooting percentages. Excessive reduction of the leaf left on the cutting appears to have the same effect (DeYoe, Zaerr, 1976, Gill-Albert, Boix, 1978, Litle and Pharis, 1995, Bandici, Vlad, 2000).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the examination of the influence of some biostimulators of the type NAA (alpha naftilacetic acid), IAA (indolilacetic acetic acid) and IBA (indolil butyric acid) on the rooting percent of the seedlings, on the diameter of the root bale, on the number of roots and on the length of the roots for the species *Azalea indica*, an experiment was organized in period 2019-2020, at the University of Oradea, Environmental Faculty, Romania.

The species that were used were chosen taking into account the tendency of the cultivators to spread them more than the others due to their decorative value, to the possibility to multiply by seedlings or by grafting, their resistance to different attacks of diseases and pests: Apollo, Madame John Häerens, Reinold Ambrosius, Memoire August Häerens.

For the choice of the substances used as stimulators, of the concentrations and the duration of treatment, as starting points were taken the recommendations found in the specialty literature, so that the studied variants were:

- V1 = untreated witness (Mt);
- V2 = NAA 500 ppm, treatment time 60 seconds;
- V3 = NAA 1000 ppm, treatment time 60 seconds;
- V4 = NAA 1500 ppm, treatment time 60 seconds;
- V5 = IAA 500 ppm, treatment time 60 seconds;
- V6 = IAA 1000 ppm, treatment time 60 seconds;
- V7 = IAA 1500 ppm, treatment time 60 seconds;
- V8 = IBA 1000 ppm, treatment time 60 seconds;

V9 = IBA 1500 ppm, treatment time 60 seconds;

The solutions NAA, IAA and IBA, have been prepared in the morning of the treatment of the seedlings so that they should not reduce or change their influence. After weighting, they were dissolved one at a time in alcohol of 960.

The variants were placed straight, with separation strips between them to prevent mutual influence, 50 plants of each species were planted, considering 12 seedlings in a repetition.

The results were statistically processed using the method of the “analyses of variance (ANOVAs)”. Two proportion tests were used to determine significant differences in percentage analyses.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The calculations were carried out only for the species azalea Apollo because there are no significant differences among the species. By analysis the data in table 1, we notice that the moment of the appearance of the calus is not the same for all variants, being recorded gaps of 10-13 days. The appearance of the calus was recorded the fastest for variants V2 and V7.

Table 1

The influence of the investigated factors on some phonological determinations for the species Azalea race Apollo, Oradea 2019- 2020

Var.	Applied treatment/ concentration	Date of propa- gation by seedlings	Date of the appearance of the calus	Date of the app. of roots	Date of the compl. rooting	Date of planting in the flower pot	Days necessary for rooting
V ₁	Untreated witness (Mt)	22.03	23.04	02.05	17.05	21.05	67
V ₂	NAA 500 ppm,	22.03	15.04	23.04.	30.04	21.05	40
V ₃	NAA 1000 ppm	22.03	20.04	29.04	06.05	21.05	46
V ₄	NAA 1500 ppm	22.03	20.04	28.04	07.05	21.05	47
V ₅	IAA 500 ppm	22.03	23.04	02.05	13. 05	21.05	63
V ₆	IAA 1000 ppm	22.03	23.04	03.05	15. 05	21.05	65
V ₇	IAA 1500 ppm	22.03	10.04	18.05	28.04	21.05	38
V ₈	IBA1000 ppm	22.03	23.04	02.05	13.05	21.05	63
V ₉	IBA1500 ppm	22.03	23.04	03.05	18.05	21.05	68

The appearance of the first roots was recorded the latest for V2, weaker than witness V1, and the earliest for V4. The faster appearance of the roots after calusare favours faster complete rooting by reducing the time necessary for rooting. For the variants treated with IAA 1500 ppm (V7) and with NAA 1500 ppm (V4), the rooting time was shortened a lot.

If the witness V1 needed 67 days, the variants V2 and V7, needed approximately 6 weeks, the rooting time shortening significantly (3 weeks). For these variants we can observe the appearance of the calus, the

appearance of the first roots and complete rooting in a reduced number of days.

The species of azalea behave differently at rooting, a situation that is illustrated in practice. The species Madame John Häerens presents the highest percent of rooting of all variants. The use of growth stimulators offers the possibility for these species to multiply constantly through propagation by seedlings, good results being obtained with IAA 1500 ppm (V7) with 92 %.

The length and diameter of the root bale are indexes that, through the reached value mark the moment of planting in the flower pot of the rooted seedlings. The seedlings can be planted when the diameter of the root bale reaches 1,5-2 cm.

In order of the value of the performed morphological determinations, the best and worst results, according to species, are presented in table 2. The data refer only to the diameter of the root bale, their length being in close and positive correlation with the diameter.

Table 2

The situation of the diameter of the root bale for different races of Azaleea, Oradea 2019-2020

Races	Good results (cm)	Bad results (cm)
August Häerens	V ₇ – IAA 1500 ppm = 2.70 V ₂ – NAA 500 ppm = 2.30	V ₅ – IAA 500 ppm = 0.78
Apollo	V ₇ – IAA 1500 ppm = 2.82 V ₂ – NAA 500 ppm = 2.79	V ₉ – IBA 1500 ppm = 0.79 V ₆ – IAA 1000 ppm = 0.88
Reinhold Ambrosius	V ₇ – IAA 1500 ppm = 1.02	V ₆ – IAA 1000 ppm = 0.63 V ₅ – IAA 500 ppm = 0.67
Madame John Häerens	V ₄ – IAA 1500 ppm = 2.16	V ₈ – IBA 1000 ppm = 0.87 V ₅ – IAA 500 ppm = 0.78

After the statistical calculation performed only on the data referring to the diameter and length of the roots (tables 3 and 4), we notice the fact that the rooting stimulators used for azalea have a positive effect both regarding the rooting time and the sizes of the roots, being statistically secured – very significant the variants: NAA 500 ppm (V2); NAA 1000 ppm (V3), NAA 1500 ppm (V4) and IAA 1000 ppm (V7).

Also as very significant in the sense of weak rooting were noticed the variants that were treated with: IAA 1000 ppm (V6) and IBA 1500 ppm (V9). No significance was recorded for the variants: IAA 500 ppm (V5) and IBA 1000 ppm (V8).

For the fulfilment of the profitability of the azaleea culture the use of stimulants is compulsory.

Table 3

The synthesis of the results regarding the diameter of the roots Oradea 2019-2020

Variant/tratament/conc. (ppm)	Average diameter of the root bale (cm)	% over the witness	Signification
Untreated witness (Mt)	1.22	100	-
NAA 500 ppm,	2.58	213	xxx
NAA 1000 ppm	0.14	176	xxx
NAA 1500 ppm	2.17	178	xxx
IAA 500 ppm	1.02	84	-
IAA 1000 ppm	0.64	52	000
IAA 1500 ppm	2.92	242	xxx
IBA1000 ppm	1.33	109	-
IBA1500 ppm	0.61	49	000
LSD 5%	0.31		
LSD 1%	0.39		
LSD 0.1%	0.52		

Note: NS = Non-significant = under 0.28; * = Significant = 0.28 – 0.38; ** = Significantly different = 0.38-0.51; *** = very significant = over 0.51

Table 4

The synthesis of the results regarding the length of the roots Oradea 2019-2020

Variant/tratament/conc. (ppm)	Average length of the roots (cm)	% over the witness	Signification
Untreated witness (Mt)	0.81	100	-
NAA 500 ppm,	1.68	208	xxx
NAA 1000 ppm	1.22	161	xxx
NAA 1500 ppm	1.47	182	xxx
IAA 500 ppm	0.68	86	-
IAA 1000 ppm	0.49	58	000
IAA 1500 ppm	1.95	212	xxx
IBA1000 ppm	1.03	127	x
IBA1500 ppm	0.54	66	00
LSD 5%	0.25		
LSD 1%	0.29		
LSD 0,1%	0.38		

Note: NS = Non-significant = under 0.20; * = Significant = 0.20 – 0.27; ** = Significantly different = 0.27-0.36; *** = very significant = over 0.36

CONCLUSIONS

Through the use of stimulents, the time necessary for rooting is reduced from 9-11 weeks to 5-6 weeks for azalea seedlings;

The reduction of the time necessary for rooting removes the exhaustion of the seedlings, determining at the same time a better evolution of the plants in flower pots;

For more complete information on the influence of the stimulants on the rooting of azalea plants, we recommend the continuation of the observations on the plants rooted with stimulants also after the planting in the flower pot, following their behaviour and evolution until blooming.

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STUDY OF THE QUALITY POTENTIAL IN THE BIHARIA VINEYARD OF THE AUTHORIZED VARIETIES IN THE CRISANA REGION

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Abstract

The present study has as object the way in which the grape varieties authorized for planting in the Crisana region adapt in the pedoclimatic conditions of the Biharia viticultural center which is part of the geographical indication Dealurile Crisana. We had in mind a producer of the Darabonts winery with 40 ha, an investment from 2017, which created a professional plantation with trellis cultivation system with management in semi-high bilateral cordon Lentz Mozer. The study considered the representative varieties Feteasca regala, Feteasca alba, Pinot gris, Rhine Riesling, Sauvignon blanc and Traminer rosé. The study considered the main quality parameters of the resulting wine: alcoholic concentration in % volume, residual sugars in g/l, fixed acidity g/l, volatile acidity g/l and dry extract g/l.

Key words: authorized grape varieties, composition parameters, quality steps.

INTRODUCTION

The planting of grape varieties in the viticultural area of Biharia center, with large vineyards and different varieties, involves a risk considering the climate changes in this area and the planting of some varieties, although authorized, they have not been verified on this pedoclimatic area.

Sadelli Prodcum has assumed these risks based on studies that have suggested that there are favorable conditions in this area to produce quality wines. In these conditions, the Darabonts domain was created with an area of 40 ha and a processing winery with a capacity related to this area with all the necessary facilities.

The region has been known since the Middle Ages as a producer of quality wines and our intention is to bring the area back to the attention of wine lovers. Biharia and the Crișana region have been wine-growing areas known throughout history, the tradition being interrupted due to the political context and various agricultural policies.

Today there are more and more producers in the area that prove the potential of this wine region. The wines we make here at Biharia are made exclusively from grapes from our own plantations. The treatments applied to

the vineyard and the wine are the minimum necessary to maintain the health of the grapes and the hygiene of the wine, otherwise we leave nature to follow its course. More details soon. Under these conditions it becomes mandatory to monitor the wines obtained, which will confirm the potential of each grape variety and will be the basis for future decisions in the field of viticultural technological solutions on the most advantageous way to exploit the quality of production.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

This study considers a period of three years from the entry into fruit bearing of the plantations 2019, 2020 and 2021, on the basic varieties of the plantation: Feteasca regala, Feteasca alba, Pinot gris, Rhine Riesling, Sauvignon blanc and Traminer rosé.

The production of these varieties was vinified in the three years and the parameters of the monitored wine were: alcoholic concentration in % volume, residual sugars in g/ , fixed acidity g/l, volatile acidity g/l and dry extract g/l.

These parameters are part of the criteria for granting quality categories according to the Wine Law applied under the authority of ONVPV. The analyses were carried out in an authorized laboratory according to the standards in force for wine analysis.

Reporting parameters to the GI category.

Wines with the GI "Dealurile Crisanei" must present the following composition parameters:

- alcoholic strength: minimum 10,0 % by volume - total acidity (tartaric acid): minimum 4,5 g/l
- volatile acidity (acetic acid): maximum 1,2 g/l
- non-reducing dry extract: minimum 17 g

Parameters relating to the D.O.C. category

Wines with D.O.C. "CRIȘANA" must have the following compositional characteristics:

- actual alcoholic strength: minimum 11 % by volume
 - total acidity (tartaric acid): minimum 5.5 g/l for white varieties and minimum 4.5 g/l for red varieties
 - volatile acidity (acetic acid):
 - * 18 milli-equivalents per liter or 1.08 g/l for white and rosé wines;
 - non-reducing dry extract: minimum 17 g/l for white and rosé wines
- D.O.C.-C.M.D.

GRAPE VARIETY	ALC. CONC. % VOL.	SUGARS g/l	TOT.ACIDITY g/l	VOLATILE ACIDITY g/l	DRY EXTRACT g/l
Feteasca alba 2020	12.5	1.28	5.52	0.16	23.12
Feteasca regala / Pinot gris	12.12	1.52	5.62	0.14	20.98
Pinot Gris 2020	13.69	1.28	4.95	0.20	22.02
Rhine Riesling 2020	12.13	1.68	5.60	0.15	20.82
Traminer rose 2020	12.32	1.52	6.60	0.20	23.88
Sauvignon blanc 2020	13.31	1.52	6.37	0.16	20.78
Chasselas 2020	11.07	0.88	5.55	0.15	17.02
Chasselas/Pinot gris 2020	11.27	1.16	6.00	0.13	18.14

Comparing the composition parameters made with the minimum mandatory parameters for inclusion in the IG quality category, we find that all the wines studied from this point of view fall into the DOC quality category.

If we classify the wines in the DOC category in terms of alcohol concentration, which must be above 11% alcohol by volume, they all fit in every year we studied. Also, for the extract parameter they all fit into this category. Only one parameter is deficient in total acidity on the first year of production 2019 for all the white varieties analyzed. In the production year 2020, only Pinot gris does not fit in the total acidity, at 4.95 g/l, probably due to the delayed harvest resulting from the acquired alcohol of 13.69 % volume.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The varieties studied in the three years of harvesting give reason to be confident about the future of these plantations. All the varieties studied gave very promising results, especially when we look at the first years of production, which are usually less relevant. The parameters studied, especially those related to accumulation, achieving alcohol concentrations between 11% by volume and 13.69% by volume, with the possibility from this point of view to be classified in the DOC quality category, is an argument that all the varieties planted have prospects to produce quality raw material. One of the reasons for these results is the climatic data.

Ecoclimatic data: average annual temperature 9.6 °C, sum of annual rainfall 626 mm, sum of active temperatures 3,125 °C, sum of sunshine hours 1,301 and sum of active precipitation 389 mm.

The relative humidity is about 75%, 10-year average. The oenoclimatic suitability of wine-growing region (thermoheliodryc index) is 4.287, particularly favorable for white wines, red varieties producing rosé wines of great finesse and quality.

The significant drop in rainfall in August, September and October gives better soil warming and ripening conditions for the harvest, with better conditions for good plant health. The noticeable decrease in average air temperatures by 3-4 °C in September helps to preserve the higher temperature-sensitive components - aromas, acids - in the grapes.

To establish the value of each grape variety in this area still requires monitoring at least until year five under different climatic conditions and with different technological decisions.

CONCLUSIONS

The wine-growing area in which the Biharia wine-growing center is located has all the pedo-climatic conditions for the varieties studied. The quality of the wines obtained in young vineyard conditions, based on the composition parameters studied, certifies a good decision regarding both the varieties planted and the cultivation system and viticultural technology applied. One parameter that needs to be monitored more closely seems to be the acidity, which in this area should be higher, with the observation that there could be two reasons for a certain lack of acidity, either late harvesting or years with excessive temperatures during the ripening period.

One conclusion that emerges from this research is that in the Biharia wine-growing center there is a wine-growing potential that needs to be exploited and that promises quality wines with DOC certificates.

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ANALYSIS OF THE WALNUT PRODUCTION AND MARKETING SECTOR IN ROMANIA

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Abstract

This paper analyzes the walnut production and marketing sector in Romania during 2016-2020. In order to capture the evolution of this sector better, it was necessary to analyze specific indicators such as: the number of walnuts existing in fruit-bearing plantations at national and macro-regional level; total walnut production achieved at national and macro-regional level; average nuts production per tree at national and macro-regional level; average prices for the category "Walnuts in shell"; average annual consumption per capita of nuts; quantitative imports and exports for the category "Walnuts in shell" related to Romania. Nowadays, Romania currently ranks first in walnut production in the European Union.

The increase in the interest for this culture was highlighted on the one hand, as the demand on the internal market increased, and on the other hand, as the fruit growers' accessed the European Union funds.

The statistical data that were used to carry out this study were taken from the National Institute of Statistics and from the FAO website.

Key words: walnuts; nuts production; average annual consumption per capita of nuts; exports and imports for the category "Walnuts in shell"; Romania

INTRODUCTION

Walnut (*Juglans regia* L.) is a tree that belongs to the family Juglandaceae, with about 40 species, and has as its area of spread, especially the temperate and Mediterranean areas, on the one hand, as spontaneous flora and, on the other hand, as crops. Walnut is native to Central Asia (<https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nuc>).

Walnut is especially important for its fruits. These are considered a concentrated food because they have a very complex chemical composition.

Nuts are very good for human health if they are eaten regularly. Specialist studies have shown that antioxidants in nuts help prevent many diseases that are so prevalent today (https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/Moldova-NGER-Report-Edited-05-07-2018_translated_Conft_checked_RO.pdf)

Romanians appreciate and consume fresh fruit, especially those who prefer healthy foods or those who follow certain diets. The list of favorite fruits includes pears, plums, peaches, apples, grapes and nuts. (Chiurciu, 2019; Soare et al., 2019, Soare and Chiurciu, 2018).

In Romania, walnut culture is found in all macro-regions. The activity of producing walnuts is favored, on the one hand, by the pedoclimatic conditions, and on the other hand, by the increase of the interest for this culture (<https://www.madr.ro/docs/agricultura/legume-fructe/Ghid-Pomicultura-final.pdf>).

Walnuts along with other categories of fruits are produced in Romania, in significant quantities and provide, on the one hand, a large proportion of the consumption needs of the population, and on the other hand, considerable income for fruit growers (https://www.economica.net/romania-in-topul-producatorilor-de-nuci_158834.html).

In the future, Romania may expand the area cultivated with walnuts to the level of all macro-regions, which would entail the increase of the nuts production realized internally. This fact would lead to placing Romania in the top of the first registered producers worldwide (Cuzino, 2021; Tănăsescu, 2005).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the period 2016-2020, in this research were analyzed the most representative indicators for the sector of production and marketing of walnuts in Romania.

The analyzed indicators focused mainly on: the number of walnuts existing in fruit-bearing plantations at national and macro-regional level; walnut production at national and macro-regional level; the average production of nuts per tree obtained at national and macroregional level; average prices for the category "Walnuts in shell"; average consumption of nuts per capita; quantitative imports and exports for the category "Walnuts in shell" related to Romania.

The statistical data that were processed and analyzed in this research were taken from the National Institute of Statistics and the FAO website. In order to highlight as concisely as possible, the results of the research, it was necessary to present them both in tabular and graphic form.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It should be noted that the number of walnuts in fruit-bearing orchards is an important aspect for the walnut production sector in Romania.

During the period on which this analysis was focused, walnut orchards were owned by farmers of smaller sizes compared to other crop categories. Another important aspect to be mentioned is the growing interest in this crop with the provision of EU funds for fruit growing (Romania-Tree Nuts report, 9/26/2016).

Table no. 1 shows the evolution of the number of fruit-bearing walnuts existing in plantations at national and macro-regional level, in the period 2016-2020. From the presented data it can be seen that the number of walnuts changed from one year to another during the analyzed period. The highest number of nuts was registered in 2020 (2,067,880 trees), and the lowest was in 2017 (1,842,007 trees). In the year 2020, at national level there was an increase in the number of nuts by 12.03%, compared to 2016.

At the macroregional level, the highest number of walnuts was registered in Macroregion 2. The highest number of walnuts was 799,609 trees (2020). This macro-region held in 2020, 38.66% of the number of walnuts registered at national level.

Macroregion 1 ranks second in terms of the number of existing fruit-bearing walnuts. The most significant number of walnuts was recorded in 2019 (552,509 trees). In 2020, this macro-region accounted for 26.71% of the number of existing walnuts nationwide.

Table 1

Evolution of fruit-bearing walnuts existing in plantations at national and macro-regional level in the period 2016-2020 (number)

Specification	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2020/2016 (%)
Romania	1,845,824	1,842,007	1,918,156	1,936,247	2,067,880	112.03
MACROREGION ONE	545,052	539,487	546,559	552,475	552,509	101.36
MACROREGION TWO	575,677	596,665	638,273	666,555	799,609	138.89
MACROREGION THREE	261,658	245,343	247,092	254,061	251,715	96.20
MACROREGION FOUR	463,437	460,512	486,232	463,156	464,047	100.13

Source: Source: NIS, 2021; own calculations

Macroregion Four is on the next position in terms of the number of fruit-bearing walnuts. In 2020, there was an insignificant increase in the number of fruit-bearing walnuts, of only 0.13%, compared to 2016. This macro-region,

in 2020, accounted for 22.44% of the number of existing fruit-bearing walnuts at national level.

Macroregion 3 recorded in the analyzed period the lowest number of fruit-bearing walnuts existing at macroregional level. In 2020, there was a decrease in the number of fruit-bearing walnuts by 3.80%, compared to 2016. This macroregion accounted for 12.17% of the number of existing fruit-bearing walnuts at national level.

In the future, we expect an increase in the areas occupied by walnut plantations, because we are witnessing an increase in the demand for walnuts both on the domestic market and on the international market, as consumers become more and more aware of the importance of a varied and healthy alimentation (Romania-Tree Nuts report, 9/26/2016).

Fig.1. Dynamics of fruit-bearing walnuts existing at national and macro-regional level, in the period 2016-2020 (number)

Source: Own graph based on data provided by NIS

During the period under analysis, Romania passed from ranking second in the top of walnut producers in the European Union, on the first place, outrunning countries with tradition such as France and Spain. Another significant aspect that is worth mentioning is the fact that Romania is in the top ten nuts producers, registered worldwide. In table no. 1 it is shown the evolution of walnut production at national and macro-regional level.

From the data presented in the mentioned table it can be seen that, in the period 2016-2018, there was an increase in walnut production at national level, and in the period 2019-2020, walnut production decreased, compared to 2018. The highest nut production achieved at national level was 56,053 tons (2018), and the lowest was of 34,095 tons (2015). In 2020, the nut production achieved at national level increased by 47.42%, compared to 2016. This increase in walnut production by about 50% was mainly due to the expansion of fruit-bearing walnuts areas.

Table 2

Evolution of walnut production at national and macro-regional level in the period 2016-2020 (tons)

Specification	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2020/2016 (%)
Romania	34,095	45,797	56,053	51,602	50,266	147.42
MACROREGION ONE	9,836	13,195	16,636	15,103	14,477	147.18
MACROREGION TWO	10,673	14,602	17,569	16,310	16,052	150.39
MACROREGION THREE	4,988	6,468	7,798	7,315	7,545	151.26
MACROREGION FOUR	8,598	11,532	14,050	12,874	12,192	141.80

Source: NIS, 2021; own calculations

At the macroregional level, the production of nuts varied from one year to another during the analyzed period. From the data presented in the previous table at macroregional level, it was observed that Macroregion 2 (North-East and South-East Development Regions) achieved the most significant nut production in the analyzed period. The highest production was recorded in 2018 (17,569 tons). The second macroregion in 2018 achieved 31.34% of the walnut production registered at national level. In 2020, walnut production increased by 50.39% compared to 2016. This increase in walnut production in Macroregion 2 slightly exceeded the national increase for the same period analyzed.

Macroregion 1 (North-West and Central Development Regions) (NUTS 2 regions in Romania, 2010 and 2013) is on the second position in the top of walnut production carried out at the macroregional level. The highest nut production in this macroregion was of 16,636 tons (2018). This macroregion achieved 29.67% of the walnut production obtained at national level, in 2018.

Fig. 2. Total walnut production achieved at national and macroregional level, in the period 2016-2020 (tons)

Source: Own graphic based on data provided by NIS

Macroregion Four (South-West Oltenia and West Development Regions) obtained productions between 8,598 tons - 14,050 tons in the analyzed period. In 2018, Macroregion Four achieved 25.06% of the walnut production obtained at national level. In 2020, here, the production of nuts increased by 41.80%, compared to 2016. The growth registered was below the national growth rate.

Macroregion three (Development regions Bucharest-Ilfov and South - Muntenia) is ranked on the last place at the macroregional level in terms of nut production. The largest production of nuts was achieved in 2018 (7,798 tons). Here, in 2018, 13.91% of the total production was obtained at national level. In 2020, there was an increase in production by 51.26%, compared to 2016. From the data presented in the table above, it is easy to see that 2018 was a year in which record productions were obtained both nationally and at macroregional level.

The evolution of the average production of nuts per tree at national and macro-regional level, in the period 2016-2020, is presented in table no. 3.

From the data regarding the average nut production achieved per tree at national level, it can be seen that it fluctuated during the analyzed period. The most significant average production of nuts per tree at national level was recorded in 2018 (29 kg / tree). In 2020, the average production per tree increased by 33.33%, compared to 2016. The average production of walnuts per tree, realized in 2018, determined at a national level the achievement of a record production.

Table 3

Evolution of average walnut production per tree at national and macroregional level, in the period 2016-2020 (kg / tree)

Specification	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2020/2016 (%)
Romania	18	25	29	27	24	133.33
MACROREGION ONE	18	24	30	27	26	144.44
MACROREGION TWO	19	24	28	24	20	105.26
MACROREGION THREE	19	26	32	29	30	157.89
MACROREGION FOUR	19	25	29	28	26	136.84

Source: NIS, 2021; own calculations

Macroregion 3 recorded the highest average walnut production per tree in 2018 (32 kg / tree). This production exceeded the average production registered at national level for 2018. From the presented data it is found that in 2020 the average production increased by 57.89% compared to 2016.

Fig. 3. Average production of nuts per tree achieved at national and macro-regional level, in the period 2016-2020 (kg / tree)
Source: Own graphic based on data provided by NIS

In the rest of the macroregions, in 2020, the following increases of the average production of walnuts per tree were observed, compared to 2016, as follows: Macroregion 1 (+ 44.44%); Macroregion 4 (+ 36.84%) and Macroregion 2 (+ 5.26%).

The evolution of the average price for the category "Walnuts in shell" is presented in figure no.4. In the period 2016-2020, the average price registered a series of changes. The highest average price was recorded in 2018 (8.95 lei / kg), and the lowest average price was 7.02 lei / kg (2016).

In 2020, the average price for the category "Walnuts in shell" increased by 13.67% compared to 2016.

Fig. 4. The average price for the category "Walnuts in shell" at national level, in the period 2016-2020 (lei / kg)
Source: Own graphic based on data provided by INS

It is worth mentioning that there is a substantial difference between the average price for the category "Walnuts in shell" and the category "Walnut kernel", the latter having a higher average price. The price is influenced by a series of factors, the most representative of which are: the supply of nuts; the demand for nuts; consumer preferences, traditions, etc.

The average annual consumption of nuts per capita in the period 2016-2019, varied from one year to another (see Fig. 5) The highest average annual consumption of nuts per capita was achieved in 2016 (4.1 kg), and the smallest was of 2.1 kg (2017). In 2019, the average annual consumption of nuts per capita increased by 34.15% compared to 2016. This decrease in consumption can also be attributed to the increase in the price for the category "Walnuts in shell" by 9.40% in 2019, compared to 2016.

Fig. 5. Average annual consumption of nuts per inhabitant in Romania, in the period 2016-2019 (kg)

Source: Own graphic based on data provided by NIS

In the future, the average annual consumption of nuts per capita is expected to increase, as people tend to be more and more concerned about healthy diets. According to experts in the field, walnuts contain a number of minerals and vitamins that directly contribute to maintaining human health.

In table no. 4 are represented the quantitative imports and exports for the category "Walnuts in shell" related to Romania, in the period 2016-2019. From the data presented in the table it can be easily seen that imports are clearly superior to exports.

The most significant imports were made in 2017 (4,383 tons), and the lowest were 1,423 tons (2016). In 2019, the quantitative imports increased by 58.88%, compared to 2016.

Regarding the quantitative exports for the category "Walnuts in shell", it was found that they have decreased massively since 2017.

The largest quantitative exports were recorded in 2016 (946 tons). On the other hand, the lowest quantitative exports were recorded in 2018 (180 tons).

Table 4

Quantitative imports and exports for the category "Nuts in shell" related to Romania, in the period 2016-2019 (tons)

Specification	2016	2017	2018	2019
Import	1.423	4.383	2.899	2.261
Export	946	347	180	192

Source: FAOSTAT, 2021

Romania's quantitative exports for the "Walnuts in shell" category are low compared to domestic production. This fact demonstrates, on the one hand, that Romanian producers are mainly oriented towards the domestic market, and on the other hand, the domestic market has the capacity to absorb domestic production.

In 2019, the top 5 exporters for the category "Walnuts in shell" registered worldwide consisted of: United States of America (157,554 tons); China (74.193 tons); Chile (73.792 tons); United Arab Emirates (49,487 tons); Mexico (47,800 tons) (FAOSTAT, 2021).

CONCLUSIONS

Following the analysis of the main indicators specific to the production and marketing sector in Romania, the following were found:

- In 2020, at national level, the highest number of existing nuts was recorded in fruit-bearing plantations, of 2,067,880 trees;
- Macroregion 2 registered the highest number of nuts in 2020 (799,609 trees);
- In 2018, the highest nut production was registered at national level, of 56,053 tons;
- The highest production achieved at the macroregional level was recorded at the level of Macroregion 2 in 2018 (17,569 tons);
- In 2018, the most substantial average production of nuts per tree at national level was achieved, of 29.0 kg;
- Macroregion 3, in 2018, recorded the highest average production of nuts per tree, of 32.0 kg, exceeding the average production achieved at national level;
- In 2018, the highest average price was registered for the category "Walnuts in shell", of 8.95 lei / kg;

- In 2016, the most substantial average annual consumption of nuts per inhabitant was highlighted, of 4.1 kg;
- In 2017, the largest quantitative imports were made for the category "Walnuts in shell" of 4,383 tons;
- In 2016, the largest quantitative imports were made for the category "Walnuts in shell", of 946 tons.

In the future, Romanian fruit growers have a high chance of producing significant quantities of nuts that will be directed more towards exports, because the demand on the international market tends to increase.

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THE CALCULATION OF ECONOMIC INDICATORS FOR SETTING UP A BILBERRY PLANTATION

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Abstract

Berries have always been a precious delicacy for foreigners, but also a chance to make a profit for local producers. Taking a risk and investing in a bush business is rewarding. From this point of view, bilberry is one of these crops, which deserves to be cultivated by farmers. Cultivation of bilberries is currently one of the best agricultural investments on small areas. The good production yield, but also the high demand on the market make the bilberries to bring to the farmers a consistent annual profit. The investment in such a plantation is worth it because it is a long-term one. A bilberry farm offers productions for up to 50 years. The establishment of the plantation is a very big investment, but it is compensated with the fact that the fruits have a great search on the Romanian market, the capitalization price is the highest of all the small fruits and the productions are high. This paper resembles the importance of the bilberry plantation from the technological and economical point of view.

Key words: bilberry, expenses, production, profit rate, investment value

INTRODUCTION

The bilberry or the American blueberry, is a shrub species with a special dynamic in the last years, it is extending more and more in the culture in our country due to the high demand on the market that is growing in Europe (Chira, 2014). Bilberry adapts well both in lowland areas but especially in hilly and mountainous areas being a rustic species resistant to severe winter frosts and foliar diseases with fewer pathogens than other more sensitive species. (Braniște N., 2007) Bilberry is part of the Ericaceae family, genus *Vaccinium*, which includes over 200 wild and cultivated species. Bilberry (*Vaccinium Uliginosum* L.), Bilberry (*Vaccinium Myrtillus* L.) and Red Bilberry (*Vaccinium vitis idaea* L.) are among the spontaneous species in our country and are found, especially, in the pre-mountainous hilly areas in the form of short bushes (between 20-50 cm tall and, very rarely, up to 80 cm), with creeping stems and small fruits (Dumitru, 2019). Cultivated bilberry varieties (with tall shrubs, which can reach 1 to 3 m in height) have fruits 2-4 times larger than those produced by

wild bilberries and generally come from three American species: *Vaccinium Corymbosum* (mainly *Vaccinium Lamarckii* and *Vaccinium Angustifolia*).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Bilberry with tall bush is a species of temperate climate, with moderate temperature requirements. Prefer cool and humid climate. The optimal hourly temperatures of the species are between 18 and 30⁰ C, and the absolute minimum is 7⁰ C and maximum 42⁰ C. Temperature is a major factor in production, the heat requirements are high in order to obtain high yields (Eaton & co., 2004). Bilberries are affected by extremely high summer temperatures, especially if they are associated with severe atmospheric drought. Temperature affects both plants and fruits. In the Northern areas with long days and cool nights during the ripening of the fruits are more fragrant and tastier (Hoza, 2008). Although concerning the light bilberry has moderate pretensions, it also supports semi-shade, but it achieves the best productions in full light conditions, having maximum requirements during the flowering and fruiting period. In partial shade the stems grow shorter and thinner, bear less fruit, and the fruit remains smaller and less colored. Bilberries have high water requirements, with maximum consumption during fruit growing and ripening. Requires a constant humidity in the soil, not tolerating drought and prolonged excess water in the soil (Moon, 2020).

Soil is one of the most important environmental factors for the success of bilberry cultivation, both in its physical properties (texture) and in its chemical properties. The optimal limits of the soil reaction for bilberries, expressed in pH values are between 4.3 and 5.5 (James, 2019). Bilberries can grow and develop well on a wide range of soils, provided they are acidic, well-drained, rich in organic matter and well exposed to light. It does not tolerate water stagnation in the soil for several days (Kovacs, 2016). The establishment of a plantation requires compliance with the climatic and soil conditions that must meet the ecological requirements of bilberries. The preparation of the land for the establishment of bilberry cultivation consists in clearing woody vegetation and removing the roots, after which the surface leveling is performed in the direction of the slope (Venig, 2012).

After leveling, a clearing plow is applied, at 40-50 cm, 120 -150 kg of P₂O₅ per hectare are incorporated. On soils with a pH above 5.5, an additional 2-4 tons of sulfur powder / ha is administered. In soils with low permeability, scarification is performed at 60-80 cm to ensure internal drainage of water (Mateescu, 2002).

Planting distances are determined by the crop system and soil vigor. The optimal distances for the correct development of the plants are 2.5-3.0 m between rows and 1.0 m between plants per row.

Bilberries are planted in autumn, in October, in November, and in drier areas in early spring, or in March in April, in wetter areas (Retamales, 2018)

Some aspects must be taken into account when planting, namely: planting is done in pits of 40x40x40 cm, in which 15-20 kg of acid peat is administered and only on poor soils 5-7 kg of well-fermented manure / pit are added. . Due to the very fine root system that can be easily broken, the handling of the plants is done with great care. The planting will be done with the bale of soil fixed on the roots following the abundant watering of the pots in which the plants were placed. The plants are placed in the pit 4-5 cm deeper than in the fortification field, taking care to evenly distribute the roots and cover with the above-mentioned soil mixture (Retournad & co., 2021). After planting, the plants are watered with 10-15 l of water per plant and mulched with loose soil.

Cultivation is conducted in the form of a bush, because it corresponds to the peculiarities of growth and thus requires minimal interventions for its formation and management. It is also possible to adopt the fruit fence, without a support system, by removing the stems that tend to develop towards the interval between the rows. In this case, the distances between plants in a row will be greater, namely 1.2-1.5 m.

In the first year after planting, sometimes in the 2nd it is recommended to maintain the soil in a black field clean of weeds. This can be done by superficial work at a depth of 5-10 cm in a row and 10 -15 cm in intervals. Another way to keep the soil clean of weeds is by mulching. Vegetable waste, straw leaves are used as mulch, but the best results are the use of softwood sawdust and acid peat. The mulch is applied in summer, after the first tillage or after the ripening of the fruits, in a thick layer of 6.0-8.0 cm, on a wide strip of 0.6 -1.2 m between the plants (Schmid, 2007).

Acid peat can also be used successfully as mulch, the application is done in the same way as sawdust, with the exception that the peat must be ground. The amount used per hectare is 6-10 to / ha.

In the first year after planting the 2-year-old plants, the 2-4 branches with which the plant came for their branching, all vigorous growths, upright, and well placed in the bush, are shortened, removing half to 1 / 3 of their length. The weaker branches with lateral position are removed. Any stems that appear from the basal area and favorably complete the skeleton are preserved, shortened for branching. In the next 2-3 years, pruning is applied only to half of the vigorous growths, for the staged arrangement of the fruit production and the lighting of the crowns (Spiridon, 2008).

The fruit ripens in a period of 4-7 weeks, depending on the variety, the cultural area and the climatic conditions of the respective year. Harvest maturity is considered when the fruit acquires the color specific to the variety (blue, shiny, blackish, etc.), and the skin becomes elastic when pressed. The ripening of the fruits in bunches takes place in the order of their formation, namely from the base to their top.

Harvesting can be done manually, mechanized or semi-mechanized. Manual harvesting is recommended for fresh fruit. It is carried out in dry weather, avoiding the hours of strong sunshine during the day. Harvesting is done on varieties in plastic baskets (pots) with a capacity of 0.5 kg, placed in a row in crates with a capacity of 3 or 5 kg. During harvesting, the fruit packs are kept under shade or sheds, protected from rain and sun.

Bilberries are temporarily stored in cool rooms, protected from rain and sun, at temperatures of 10-12⁰C, where they can be stored for 4-5 days. Mechanized harvesting is performed with the combine. There are quantitative and qualitative losses, so production is destined for industrialization.

Semi-mechanized harvesting consists of harvesting bilberries by hand and collecting them in a common bunker. At the same time, the bushes are hit with short rubber tubes and the fruit is collected in baskets placed under the bush (Westhumble Mary, 2014).

Bilberries are characterized by a good storage capacity. This ability is closely linked to the fact that healthy berries remain intact after peeling and do not lose easily their juice during handling or transport. Keeping them fresh for consumption or industrialization can be done for 4 weeks in cold storage, at temperatures of 0-2⁰C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Number of plants = 5714/ ha

Exploitation Period (De) = 25 years

Investment value (It) = 145195 Ron

Setting up expenses = 120836 Ron

- Handmade works = 7729 Ron
- Mechanical works = 8848 Ron
- Materials = 104259 Ron

Maintenance costs = 24359 Ron

- Handmade works = 5391 Ron
- Mechanical works = 6364 Ron
- Materials = 12604 Ron

Ca (annual depreciation rate) = 5808 Ron/year

Operating expenses (Ce) = 30942 Ron
 - Handmade works= 22771 Ron
 - Mechanical works= 3562 Ron
 - Materials= 4609 Ron
 Direct annual expenses (Cd) = 36750 Ron
 Indirect annual expenses (Ci) = 3675 Ron
 Entire yearly expenses (Ct)= 40425 Ron
 Production (P) = 8000 kg/ ha
 Production cost (Cp) = 5,05 Ron/ kg
 Selling price (Pv) = 8,0 Ron/kg
 Annual production value (V) = 64000 Ron
 Gross annual profit (Pab) = 23575 Ron
 Tax (I) = 3772 Ron
 Net annual profit (Pn) = 19803 Ron
 Annual profit rate (R) = 49 %
 Term of investment recovery (T) = 7,3 years
 Total profit during exploitation (Pt) = 495075 Ron
 Economic return on investment (Rec) = 340 %

Fig. 1. Entire investment value

Fig. 2. The structure of setting up expenses and plantation establishment

Fig. 3. The structure of the plantation maintenance expenses

Fig. 4 . The structure of the annual operating expenses

CONCLUSIONS

In the entire investment value, the largest share is the cost of land preparation and the establishment of the culture (83.2%). In the structure of the costs for the land preparation and the establishment of the plantation, the largest share is represented by the material expenses (86.3%) due to the cost of the planting material.

In the structure of the annual operating expenses, the highest value is represented by the handmade work expenses (73.6%) due to the fruit harvesting works.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE REGENERATIVE AND ORGANOGENIC CAPACITY *Aylostera (speg.) heliosa* IN THE PRESENCE IN CULTURE MEDIUM 2,5 mg/l benzyladenine (BA) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4 dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D)

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Abstract

Aylostera heliosa is a cactus that, like other cacti, can multiply quickly and efficiently by *in vitro* micropropagation (Karimi *et al.*, 2010) which ensures a virus-free planting material. It is considered a species with very high decorative potential both by flowers, port, and by the presence of thorns with white-silver edges aligned in the form of (Fig.1b) comb (Mihalte *et al.*, 2008), but which multiplies very hard by grafting (Myeong *et al.*, 2004).

Future inocula of *Aylostera heliosa* were harvested under sterile conditions from young stems sectioned into spherical slices about 1 cm long, 0,5 cm thick and 0,5-1,5 cm in diameter, depending on the area from which they were taken, and with at least 2-3 areolae.

The explants were inoculated in a mineral environment - macro, Murashige-Skoog (1962), with the addition of growth regulators, microelements Heller (1953) - V_0 (control), and on media supplemented with 2,5 mg/l benzyladenine (V_1) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (V_2).

The evolution of the explants was monitored for 90 days. Their response was different depending on the phytohormones added to the culture medium, auxin (2,4 D) or cytokinin (BA). *Aylostera heliosa* explants, grown on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l BA (V_1), were shown to have the largest and largest newly formed strains. The process of callusogenesis was manifested with my best results in explants grown on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (V_2) but also on medium without growth regulators (V_0 - control), while rhizogenesis did not occur in any of the varicose veins experienced.

Keywords: cacti, vitrocultures, benzyladenine BA, dichlorophenoxyacetic 2,4 D, callus

INTRODUCTION

It is known that auxins together with cytokinins, are substances with direct action on cell growth, they stimulate cell division, (Cachiță *et al.*, 2004).

Benzyladenine (BA) is a cytokinin with a role in boosting the processes of cell division and caulogenesis, bud formation in the inoculum, from which new strains will be generated (Mauseth, 1976), exerting an antagonistic effect on auxins, inhibiting rhizogenesis. (Cachiță *et al.*, 2004), In *in vitro* cactus cultures, it is considered that in order to multiply the plant material, the most effective growth regulator to generate new strains is BA (Escobar *et al.*, 1986).

Dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) or is an auxin with great efficacy in callus formation and rhizogenesis, according to Sandra Aparecida et al., 1996, its introduction into the culture medium is sufficient to induce callus, later it can be detached, cut and then transferred to fresh culture medium to obtain seedlings.

Aylostera heliosa or *Rebutia heliosa* is a species native to Bolivia, one of the cacti with the most spectacular and abundant blooms, which makes them particularly decorative. (Fig. 1a and b)

Fig. 1. Plant of *Aylostera heliosa*, where: a - colored flowers; b- strain silvery white spines aligned as comb.

The aim of this research was to study how the presence in the culture medium of an equal amount of cytokinin (2,5 mg/l benzyladenine) and auxin (2,4 dichlorophenoxyacetic acid) influences the regenerative and organogenic capacity of vitroplants *Aylostera heliosa*.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In this experiment in order to initiate the *Aylostera heliosa* in vitro culture, the plant material consisted from young stems harvested from mother plants. The material was sterilized by placing for one minute, in alcohol 96°, followed by a submersion operation, in a sodium hypochlorite solution 0.8% in proportion of 1:2 with water (one part sodium hypochlorite, 2 parts sterile water), which were added three drops of Tween 20, shaking continuously (Cachiță et al., 2004). After 20 minutes, the removal of disinfectant agent was achieved by washing the plant material in sterile water, in five consecutive rinses, of five minutes each, after which the plant material was deposited on aseptic filter paper rings, introduced in sterile Petri dishes. Sizing future inocula was performed under aseptic conditions in horizontal laminar flow hood, with sterile air. Young stems were cut into spherical slices, which had the following dimensions: about 1 cm long, 0,5 cm thick and a diameter of 0,5-1,5 cm, depending on the area from which they were harvested. Explants modeling (Fig. 2) were done so that each has at least 2-3 areolae (Karimi1 et al., 2010).

Fig.2. Schematic representation of sectioning method of the young stems to obtain *Aylostera* (Speg.) *heliosa* explants (where: -young strain, b-sizing of young stems, c- explant represented from young stem d- explant represented as spherical rings).

The mineral medium culture used in this experiment consisted of: macroelements and Fe-EDTA, (Murashige and Skoog, 1962), microelements (Medeiros et al., 2006), mineral mixture to which were added vitamins: HCl pyridoxine, HCl thiamine and nicotinic acid (each 1 mg/l), 100 mg/l m-inositol, 20 g/l sucrose and 7 g/l agar-agar, pH of the medium was adjusted to a value of 5,8.

To obtain the proposed results, we added in the culture medium without regulators of (V_0) and considered as a control, 2,5 mg/l benzyladenine (V_1) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (V_2).

Sterilization of vials with medium was performed by autoclaving at a temperature of 121°C for 30 minutes. The recipients with medium culture had a capacity of 15 ml, and each were placed 5 ml of the medium. After cooling the media proceeded to inoculate explants, operation conducted in aseptic camera on a laminar flow hood, horizontal, with sterile air.

After inoculation, explants were vials were filled with polyethylene folia. Conditions in the growth chamber were as follows: illuminated with white light emitted by fluorescent tubes, photoperiod was under 16 hours light/24 h 1700 lux light intensity, temperature between 20-24°C.

Vitroplantlets reaction after inoculation was monitored for 12 weeks. Biometric assessments were taken at intervals of 30 days. Observations consisted from biomeasured: vitroplantlets length regenerated from explants, number of rotes, callus formation, determining the number of neostems and branches developed on the initial inocula.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

He readings made 90 days after the initiation of in vitro cultures of *Aylostera heliosa* showed that, during this time, the average basal diameter of the stem recorded the highest value -1,6 cm - cm (Fig.3) in the explants.

belonging to variants V₁ (average supplemented with 2,5 mg/l BA) values by 0,3 cm above the control V₀, which represents an increase of 23,7%, while the same parameter for explants grown on V₂ (medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D) marked an increase of 0,1 compared to the control, a percentage increase of 7,69% (Fig.5). Results that, statistically, are appreciated as being distinctly significant (Table 1).

Supplementation of the culture medium with 2,5 mg/l BA (V₁) positively influenced the formation of new strains (Fig.4), which recorded the highest values, respectively 2 buds/variant, compared to 0,9 buds/variant in the case of control V₀ (medium without growth regulators) and 1,1 buds/variant (Fig.3) in explants grown on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V₂). These values represent in both cases an increase, by 122,22% (Fig.5) in V₁ explants (supplemented with 2,5 mg/l BA) and by 22,22% in V₂ (supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D). Results which, statistically, are appreciated as being distinctly significant (Table 1)

Table 1

Results of biometric evaluations of vitro seedlings of *Aylostera* (Speg.) *heliosa* performed 90 days after inoculation of explants on basic aseptic culture media with the addition of 2,5 mg/l BA (V₁) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (V₂)

Parametrul	Lungimea medie a tulpinilor principale ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificația		Numărul mediu al neoformatiunilor caulinare ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificația		Lungimea medie a celei mai mari neoformatiuni caulinare ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificația		Numărul mediu de rădăcinițe ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificația		Lungimea medie a celei mai mari rădăcinițe ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificația		Numărul mediu de calusuri ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificația		Diametrul mediu al calusurilor ± abaterea standard		Varianta		Semnificația		
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V0	1,30±0,36	0,1326	**	0,90±0,30	0,0884	**	0,30±0,07	0,0053	**	0	0		0	0		1,00±0,65	0,4211	NS	2,30±1,21	1,4526																							
V1	1,60±0,41	0,1700	**	2,00±0,46	0,2105	**	0,70±0,22	0,0474	**	0	0		0	0		0	0		0	0																							
V2	1,30±0,32	0,1000	**	1,10±0,33	0,1079	**	0,20±0,09	0,0084	*	0	0		0	0		2,60±0,41	0,1684	***	5,20±0,58	0,3368	***																						

Legenda : „***” - foarte semnificativ, „**” - distinct semnificativ, „*” - semnificativ, „NS” - nesemnificativ.

As expected, the average basal diameter of the newly formed buds is larger in explants grown on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l BA (V₁) (Fig.4) and 0,7 cm, respectively (Fig.3), compared to the control group V₀ (Vidican et al, 2014) in which this parameter recorded a value of 0,3 cm and 0,4 cm in explants grown on V₂ (average supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D).

A. The average diameter of the stem formed strains

B. Average number of newly main

C. The average diameter of the largest newly formed stem

D. The average number of calluses

E. The average diameter of the calluses

Fig.3. Graphic presentation of the average values corresponding to the parameters read at the level of in vitro cultures of *Aylostera* (Speg.) *heliosa*, on basic aseptic medium modified by us - (variant V₀) - with the addition of 2,5 mg/l BA (variant V₁) and of 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (variant V₂), data expressed in absolute values; (where: A- average diameter of the main stem; B - average diameter of newly formed strains; C- average diameter of the largest newly formed stem; D- average number of calluses; E-average diameter of calluses).

The results recorded by us are in line with those obtained by Wellens (2003) which shows that of all the cytokines, most cactus species respond favorably to cultivation on a medium supplemented with benzyladenine (BA) in different concentrations 0,1 - 10 mg / l (Fig. 4). Compared to the values recorded in the control group V₀ (average without growth regulators) this parameter expressed in percentage values was higher by 133,33% in variant V₁ and by 33,33% in V₂. (Fig.5)

The phenomenon of rhizogenesis has not manifested itself until this date in any of the experimental variants studied (Fig. 4).

Callus induction was noted both in inoculated and grown explants on culture medium lacking growth regulators (V_0) where an average number of 1,0 calluses/variant was recorded (Fig.3), with an average size of 2,3 cm (Fig.) As well as those grown on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V_2) which with a number of 2,6 calluses / variant that reached an average size of 5,2 cm (Fig.) Exceeded the control by 160% in the first case and by 126,08% (Fig.5) in the second case (Vidican et al, 2011)

Fig.4. Inoculi of *Aylostera* (Speg.) *Heliosa*, 90 days after inoculation of the “in vitro” explant, where: A- basic aseptic medium without growth regulators (V_0); B- Basic medium with the addition of 2.5 mg / l BA (V_1); C- Base medium with the addition of 2.5 mg / l 2.4D (V_2); where: iiv-viable initial inoculum; iin-initial necrotic inoculum; mc-culture medium; nc-young stems; ar-areola; sp-spines; cl-calus; zn-necrotic area.

The callus generated from explants cultivated on a medium lacking growth regulators is located on the surface of the explant but also on the culture medium, it shows signs of early senescence, indicated by its cream or even light brown (Fig.4).

A. The average diameter of the stem formed strains

B. Average number of newly main

C. The average diameter of the formed stem largest newly

D. The average number of calluses

E. The average diameter of the calluses

Fig.5. Graphical presentation of the average values corresponding to the parameters analyzed at the level of vitrocultures of *Aylostera (Speg.) heliosa*, on basic aseptic medium modified by us - (variant V₀) - with the addition of 2,5 mg/l BA (variant V₁) and 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D (variant V₂), data expressed as a percentage, obtained after reporting the analyzed values to the results recorded at the respective parameters read in the control group (V₀), without growth regulators,

In the case of explants inoculated on culture medium supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4-D (V₂), the callus was crumbly, snow-white (Fig. 4), and due to its abundance it covered the entire surface of the culture medium. As can be seen in Figure 4, the buds generated at the level of both experimental variants kept their particular species characteristics, respectively, the size and color of the spines, but especially the specific shape of the comb.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Analyzing the data analyzed on *Aylostera heliosa* explants after 90 days of in vitro culture, we found that it is possible to initiate in vitro

cultures in this cactus, on culture media supplemented with benzyladenine (BA) and 2,4 D

2. Monitoring the beneficial effect on the formation of buds and their average size by the addition in the culture medium of 2,5 mg/l auxin (2,4-D) and cytokinin (BA) we can say that the highest values we have recorded in variant V₁ (average supplemented with 2,5 mg/l BA) with 2 buds/variant respectively an average size of 0,7 cm compared to 1,1 buds/variant in V₂ (average supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4 d) and an average size of 0,4 cm.

3. Rhizogenesis did not occur in any of the experimental variants studied.

4. Regarding the number of calluses formed at V₂ (mean supplemented with 2,5 mg/l 2,4 D) there was an increase of 1,6 calluses/variant compared to the control group V₀, an increase of 126,08% , and an average increase in size by 2,9 cm, respectively an increase of 126,08%

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STUDY ON THE NUTRITIONAL IMPORTANCE OF PEPPER (CAPSICUM ANNUM) CULTIVATED IN THE SOLARIUM UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF THE CULTURE SUBSTRATE AND THE FERTILIZATION REGIME

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Abstract

Research shows that the food requirements of the human body can be met by an average daily food ration consisting of foods of animal origin in the amount of 714 grams and 1225 grams of foods of plant origin, of which 400 grams must be vegetables (Gonțea , 2011).

Pepper occupies a very important place in the assortment of vegetables, being able to be consumed raw, its content being fully used by the human body.

Key words: bell peppers, vitamin C, calcium, phosphorus, iron

INTRODUCTION

The pepper is native to Guatemala, Peru, Brazil and Mexico where it has been cultivated since ancient times. It was first reported by the doctor CHANCA (1494). In Europe it spread first to Spain, then to other countries, including Hungary, where it has been known since 1585 (Somos, 1967).

In Romania, peppers have been cultivated since the 19th century, first in the southern parts and then in the rest of the country (Bălașa, 1980).

The specialized documentations highlight the worldwide trend of increasing the areas occupied by peppers and especially of increasing the production per unit area by improving the culture technology with a special emphasis on fertilization, irrigation and mechanization, by creating high productivity varieties, with superior qualitative qualities and on the extension of some culture methods in order to stagger the culture for a longer period.

Very large areas of land are cultivated with peppers in the USA, France, Italy, Bulgaria, Hungary, Russia.

In our country, peppers with their different varieties are cultivated annually on an area of about 15,000 hectares.

Very favorable areas are the river meadows in the Danube Plain and in the Western Plain, favorable are the Plain and the Transylvanian Plateau, the North of Moldova and the sub-hilly area of the Carpathian Mountains.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The analysis of the pepper fruit content was made for the plants grown in the solarium in bags with organic substrate and in the soil for the varieties Romanesc 69 and Favoritul Pieții.

The variety Romanesc 69 is semi-early with prismatic fruits truncated with 3-4 pronounced ribs, medium in size, lemon yellow at technical maturity and red at physiological maturity.

The variety Favoritul Pieții is also semi-early with prismatic fruits with 3-4 pronounced edges, of medium size and light green color at technical maturity and bright red at physiological maturity.

By combining the factors, eight variants were made as follows:

V₁ - culture in bags with organic substrate with the variety Romanesc 69, with fertilization when N, P, K decrease to critical levels;

V₂ - culture in bags with organic substrate with the variety Romanesc 69, with complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels;

V₃ - bag culture with the Favoritul Pieții variety, with fertilization when N, P and K decrease to critical levels;

V₄ - bag culture with the Favoritul Pieții variety, with complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels;

V₅ - soil cultivation with the variety Romanesc 69, with fertilization when N, P, K decrease to critical levels;

V₆ - soil cultivation with the variety Romanesc 69, with complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels;

V₇ - soil cultivation with the Favoritul Pieții variety, with fertilization when N, P and K decrease to critical levels;

V₈ - soil cultivation with the Favoritul Pieții variety, with complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels;

The surface of the harvestable plot was 30 m², and of the whole experience 240 m². The number of plants harvested from the experimental plot was 90 (3 plants / m²).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The best results in terms of total production were obtained in variant 4 - culture in bags on organic substrate with complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels with the variety Favoritul Pieții of 49.2 t/ha, followed by variant 3 with the variety Romanesc 69 and the other variants cultivated in bags on an organic substrate.

Table 1

The influence of the cultivation system and of the fertilization regime on the pepper production

Variants	Culture system	Fertilization regime	Production obtained t/ha	± D	Significance of the difference
V ₁	Culture in bags on organic substrate with variety Romanesc 69	Fertilization when N, P and K fall to critical levels	45.8	2.2	x
V ₂	Culture in bags on organic substrate with variety Romanesc 69	Complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels	48.7	5.1	xx
V ₃	Culture in bags on organic substrate with variety Favoritul pieții	Fertilization when N, P and K fall to critical levels	46.3	2.7	x
V ₄	Culture in bags on organic substrate with variety Favoritul pieții	Complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels	49.2	5.6	xx
V ₅	Soil cultivation with variety Romanesc 69	Fertilization when N, P and K fall to critical levels	43.6	-	-
V ₆	Soil cultivation with variety Romanesc 69	Complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels	47.2	3.6	xx
V ₇	Soil cultivation with variety Favoritul pieții	Fertilization when N, P and K fall to critical levels	45.3	1.7	x
V ₈	Soil cultivation with variety Favoritul pieții	Complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels	47.9	4.3	xx

LSD 5% - 1.69; LSD 1% - 3.21; LSD 0,1% - 6.10

The soil cultivation system gave yields lower than 47.9 t / ha at variant 8, with complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels with the Favoritul pieții variety, followed by variant 6, with the variety Romanesc 69 and the other variants grown in soil (Table 1). Statistical analysis shows the significant difference between variants 1,3,7 and control and distinctly significant between variants 2,4,6 and control.

These differences are due both to the culture substrate that ensured different conditions of temperature and mineral nutrition at the level of the root system and to the different fertilization with mineral substances.

The chemical analysis of the composition of the pepper fruits (table 2) shows that the culture system and the fertilization regime do not essentially change the content in vitamin C, phosphorus, calcium and iron per 100 grams of fresh product (table 2).

The highest content in vitamin C was the fruits of variant 7, the crop in the soil with the variety. Market favorite with fertilization when N, P and K decrease to critical levels of 180 mg/100 grams of fresh product.

The content of vitamin C is lower in the fruits of the variants on organic substrate, with complete fertilization, a fact that can be attributed to the higher volume of production.

Table 2

The content of vitamin C, phosphorus, calcium and iron in pepper fruits grown in solarium under the influence of the culture substrate and the fertilization regime

Variants	Culture system	Fertilization regime	Vitamin C mg/100g	Phosphorus mg/100g	Calcium mg/100g	Iron mg/100g
V ₁	Culture in bags on organic substrate with variety Romanesc 69	Fertilization when N, P and K fall to critical levels	164	24	8,0	0,3
V ₂	Culture in bags on organic substrate with variety Romanesc 69	Complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels	148	28	9,9	0,6
V ₃	Culture in bags on organic substrate with variety Favoritul pietii	Fertilization when N, P and K fall to critical levels	167	25	8,5	0,3
V ₄	Culture in bags on organic substrate with variety Favoritul pietii	Complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels	151	29	10,1	0,7
V ₅	Soil cultivation with variety Romanesc 69	Fertilization when N, P and K fall to critical levels	175	20	7,4	0,2
V ₆	Soil cultivation with variety Romanesc 69	Complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels	170	25	9,0	0,4
V ₇	Soil cultivation with variety Favoritul pietii	Fertilization when N, P and K fall to critical levels	180	22	7,7	0,2
V ₈	Soil cultivation with variety Favoritul pietii	Complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels	172	27	9,7	0,5

Regarding the phosphorus, calcium and iron content, the highest values are found in the fruits of the variants that have been fertilized by maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels (table 2).

CONCLUSION

1. Pepper is a species with great nutritional and economic value, occupying an important place in the assortment of vegetables.

2. The very pleasant taste and the very varied range of uses, fresh, as a simple salad or with other vegetables, in dishes, sauces, soups, stuffed peppers have determined the continuous increase of pepper consumption in all countries.

3. The nutritional value of pepper is given by the high content of vitamins, sugars, minerals, amino acids and organic acids.

4. The content of fruits in vitamin C is higher in soil culture than in bags in organic substrate. It is also higher in the Favoritul pieții variety than in Romanesc 69 variety.

5. Phosphorus, calcium and iron are found in larger quantities in the fruits of plants grown in bags on organic substrate with complete fertilization, maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels, than those fertilized when N, P and K decrease to critical levels. They are also higher in the Favoritul pieții variety than in the Romanesc 69.

6. Pepper fruits harvested from plants grown in soil with complete fertilization maintaining N, P and K at optimal levels contained higher amounts of phosphorus, calcium and iron than those fertilized when N, P and K decrease to critical levels.

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POSSIBILITIES FOR IMPROVING DEGRADED LAND THROUGH FOREST VEGETATION

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Abstract

The present paper has as major objectives knowledge of the soil's state conditions, soil degradation and the possibility of improving and strengthening them with the help of forest vegetation. The land slip process is a particularly damaging process whose many consequences affect human activity. Schematically, the consequences of this process relate to the degradation of cropland. Thus, the process of stabilizing these forms of degradation is extremely important for the integrity of both the fields of culture, the forest and the integrity of all people, because we know quite well a lot of accidents caused by landslides.

Key words: Improvement, degradation, vegetation, possibility, trees

INTRODUCTION

Against the background of the changes in the nature of the property, in the landscape in Maramures, especially in Baia Mare, there are some empty hills, from the former pastures or even from the old forests that are getting degraded every day and from the different degree of torrential formations that grow more and more amplified with the passage of time. Natural vegetation is becoming more and more impoverished, even though the number of grazing animals has dropped dramatically.

According to the living environment of forest phytogenosias, soil can be defined as a subsystem integrated within the forest and resort as an ecosystem. Within the forest as a land ecosystem, the soil is formed and evolved by pedogenic factors and is constantly influenced by these factors, forming together with the near atmosphere, the biotope or the forest resort, the living environment of the biocenosis.

As a natural system, soil forms in the area of lithosphere interference with the atmosphere, the biosphere and the hydrosphere, thus forming the coating of the earth called the pedosphere. The elements of the four spheres play the role of solidification factors or pedogenetic factors. (Bodog, 2018)

Rock or parental material, along with the relief, climate and living vegetable and animal organisms are the main solidification factors. The external coating of the earth or earth's crust is composed of rocks and minerals, against which the soil is formed by the action of the climatic

elements, the surface and the groundwater and the animal and plant organisms in the biosphere.

The relief represents the space on which the pedogenesis process takes place and influences the formation of the soil both directly, by the nature of the surface store, resulting from the process of disaggregation-alteration and geological erosion and its age, and indirectly through the change of the local climate and vegetation. (Traci, 1985)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Following the study carried out in the vicinity of Firiza Forest District, Maramures County, P.U. Baia Mare, a.u. 43A, soils have been identified that are affected by degradation phenomena, i.e., landslides. Landslides are complex phenomena consisting in the detachment and displacement of sloping earth masses. On the studied territory we find land with fragmented slipped mass. They are represented by earthen masses, moderate to very strongly fragmented. The slid earth mass is consistent, not soaked in water, respectively with excess water, especially during wet periods.

"The land-sliding process is a particularly damaging process whose many consequences are passed on to human activity. Schematically, the consequences of this process relate to the degradation of croplands" (Ciortuz, 1981)

The production unit P.U. I, Baia Mare, within the Firiza Forest District, Maramures County, has an area of 615.20 ha., which is made up of four types of soil.

Fig..1 Location of the case study

In this case, landslides have as their main cause the combined action of gravity and infiltration waters, of meteoric water that leads to large changes in the specific weight of some earth masses, weakening the cohesion of the rocks, thus relishing the formation of displacement surfaces.

Another factor that helps to form the phenomenon of decay is the faulty activity of man through the faulty management of the earth, in this case, the deforestation of the land.

Fig. 2 Landslides in P.U. I, a.u. 43 A

Climatic-meteorological factors are the factors that play a determining role in the onset and evolution of landslides. Thus, a period of heavy rainfall can cause changes in the state of tensions inside the earth massif. The infiltration of precipitation leads to an increase in hydrostatic pressure that causes the earth's consistency to change and thus a reduction in cohesion and the angle of inner friction. Thus, the landslide forces exceed the lump resistance of the land causing the cession.

A factor that conditions the process of landslide is also the geological substrate. In principle, this factor influences the process to which we refer by its petrographic nature and structure. The relief or geomorphological factor also influences the process of displacement, largely determining both the predisposition to displacement, as well as the character of the motion and the plane shape of the lands.

Vegetation is a factor that ensures the stability of land, preventing or limiting the movement of soil and rock masses on slopes. The absence or the totally sporadic presence of lands in the process of slipping into forests is a proof of the important role that vegetation plays, especially woody vegetation, in counteracting the displacement process.

Fig..3 Landslides in P.U. I, a.u. 43 A

In the development unit 43A, we identified, in four situations, the phenomenon of landslides, on an area of about 1.2 ha.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As a result of the sliding processes, a variety of forms of land degradation result, depending on the type of slippage, the extent and intensity of the manifestation of the phenomena. Of these, the most widespread are: the ravine or the detachment surface, the lands slipped into the block with the slipped mass unfragmented or poorly cracked.

It is noted the large share of luvisols that account for 360.60 ha, soils that in favorable climatic conditions, provide good conditions for the development of forest vegetation. This is reflected in the increases in the hoisters which, at the rate of 83%, achieve higher and medium production classes.

Preluvosol - occupies a share of 22%, more precisely 132.03 ha of the entire production unit. The composition and morphological characterization of the profile represents the following sequence of profile horizons: ***Ao-Bt-C***. It has a different profile texture, medium (loamy) in Ao, and at the level of the Bt horizon, fine or medium, but with greater clay content. The structure is in the

relatively well-developed horizon and column-prismatic or prismatic, well developed in Bt. Humus content is 2-3%, the pH has relatively high values: the reaction is weakly acidic in the Ao horizon with pH below 6 and neutral or weakly alkaline towards the base of the profile with a pH of less than 7 superiorly grainy,

The distribution of soil types is shown in the following diagram:

Fig. 4 Distribution of soil types

Luvisoil - occupies the largest share of the entire production unit being spread over 60% of the unit area, namely 360.60 ha. The composition and morphological characterization of the profile: it represents the following sequence of horizons on *the Ao-El-Bt-C* profile. It has a differentiated texture on the profile, medium (loamy-sandy or loamy) in Ao, at the level of the horizon He the clay content decreases (the texture all medium or to coarse), and at the level of the Bt horizon the texture becomes fine or all medium, but with a higher clay content. The structure in the upper horizon is grainy, less developed, the horizon He is unstructured or with polyhedral or lamellar structure and Bt represents prismatic structure, well developed. The humus content is about 2%, and the pH has low values, below 5. It is a soil of middle and superior creditworthiness for oak, oak-beech and beech of hills. Currently, on these soils we find, oak, beech and poor beech and hornbeam mixtures, with good vegetation condition with medium production class.

Districambosoil - occupies 18% of the surface, being found in the entire production unit. The composition and morphological characterization of the profile presents the following sequence of horizons on the profile: *Ao-Bv-C(R)*. It has a medium-coarse to medium-to-middle texture, undifferentiated

on the profile, poorly-moderately developed structure, grainy in Ao and polyhedral in Bv. Other physical, physico-mechanical and aeration properties are generally favorable. The content in humus is 3-4% and consists mainly of fulvic acids but can have a blackberry amount of organic matter up to 20-25%, the degree of saturation in bases low ($V \leq 35\%$). The reaction of the soil is acidic to strongly acidic (pH = 4.5-5.0)

As a result of the research carried out in the case study, we have identified the soil type in the U.P. I Baia Mare, u.a. 43 A as typical *Luvosol-code 2201*.

Fig. 5 Luvosol tipic

The morphological composition of the profile represents the following sequence of profile: **Ao-El-Bt-C**, where the horizon Ao has a thickness of about 10-20 cm having a brown, light brown color. El horizon, partially depleted in clay, organic matter having a thickness between 10 -20 cm, being lighter in color. The Bt horizon is much thicker than in brown soils, having at least 50% of the colors in 10YR and yellow shades.

This type of soil is formed on parental materials represented by loamy, sands, clays, deposits, loessoid and various metamorphic and igneous rocks poorer in calcium minerals. The vegetation under which this type of soil was formed is made up of sessile or beech forests, with a more acidophilic flora.

Mineral trophicity is medium or medium to upper. For forest species, nitrogen trophicity is also satisfactory. The soils located on the ridges or in the upper part of the slope dry up to the state of dryness, especially in the thinned stands. Because the water in horizon B cannot climb into the upper horizons and the saplings of forest species may suffer from dryness. But the shaded slopes have more moist soils and without variations. Therefore, on

these slopes the stands of sessile oak, beech sessile oak and pure beech trees are of higher production classes than those on the ensued slopes.

This type of soil is of medium to upper creditworthiness for oak, oak-berches and pure beechings, but even for the Hungarian Oak and the lindenberry. The average creditworthiness is determined by the middle edaphic volume, because of the loamy and compact Bt horizon in the summer season.

Due to the harsh conditions of vegetation in land suffering from land sliding earthen masses, a serious hindrance to the installation of forest vegetation arises. As a result, the list of species, which can be used for afforestation of these lands, is considerably narrowing. In general, for the afforestation of sliding lands, species are used that bear the heavy texture and moisture variations, and that have a rich and deep root system.

Taking into account on the one hand the characteristics of the land and on the other hand the ecological characteristics and requirements of the species for the consolidation of landslides- affected land, it is recommended to use the following species of trees and shrubs.

- Trees: black pine, Sylvester pine, black amen, white amen, white willow, willow, white poplar, acacia, ash, sycamore, Turkish cherry, forest cherry, salty, Turkestan elm.

- Shrubs: white buckthorn, green amen, dwarf acacia, bloodsucker, dogwood, red ossorish, etc.

Obviously, the specified species are distributed according to the stationary conditions.

The recommended afforestation composition in this situation is 50Ac50As. Crop densely: 5,000 seedlings/ha (1×2), so on the entire improvement area the required number of seedlings is 6,000 pieces.

For the consolidation of degraded lands in the study area, the planting of tree species will be done in pits of 30×30×30.

CONCLUSIONS

Within the complex of measures, which is applied to degraded lands by landslides of earth masses, phyto-ameliorative afforestation works play a decisive role of the first importance.

These works constitute a powerful means of fixing land and capitalizing on such land because:

- the carpet of trees and shrubs retains a large part of the precipitation on the canopy.

- prevents snow from drifting and sudden melting.

- regulates surface runoff by preventing concentrated infiltration and undermining of slopes.
- uniformizes the thermal regime.
- eliminates through sweating an appreciable amount of water.
- bind together the layers of soil and rock thus increasing their cohesion.
- restores and relieves the soil.
- raises the economic and social value of land.

In order to improve the phenomenon of sliding the earthen masses, in the studied arrangement unit, in accordance with, the existing stationary conditions, we chose to use the planting by mixture of *acacia* and *ash* bouquets for the execution of the consolidation works.

Due to the stationary causes generated by the general natural context but also by those of a customized nature at the level of the lands in the studied unit, the reconstruction and stabilization of the lands affected by the slips, is much more difficult compared to other forms of degradation.

One of the problems of carrying out these types of works would be, the small number of forest species capable of coping with these stationary conditions, with the exception of micro-depressions in the areas affected by slips that benefit from a more favorable soil moisture regime.

According to the, the stationary conditions, in order to improve the conditions of degradation, I believe that planting in bouquets of *acacia* and *ash* is the right choice, because, they have land, but at the same time, the ability to stabilize in a short term the phenomenon of acacia slips, brings another benefit, especially for beekeepers, through the melliferous flowers that it produces, thus at the age of 5 it produces flowers in abundance.

Due to the fact that both forest species are able to adapt very well and to unfavorable conditions, due to the degradation of the land, I believe that the area that requires the consolidation of the sliding earth masses will not be a problem for these species. Thus, the stabilization of the degraded lands is carried out without problems.

For the improvement area studied, a number of 5,000 seedlings/ha are required. Thus, for the entire area of 1.2 ha, the number of seedlings needed is 6,000 seedlings.

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NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF THE INDUCTION HEAT TREATMENT OF THE DRILL WITH SPLIT CHISEL PEAK

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Abstract

This paper proposes an analysis of the induction hardening method of the drill with split chisel peak. In the case of the drill with split chisel peak the heating analysis needs solution in the thermal diffusion problems coupled with eddy currents case. The known simulation must be the same with the requirements parameter in practice.

Keywords: Numerical simulation, Electromagnetic field, Electromagnetic field coupled with thermal, drill with split chisel peak.

INTRODUCTION

The drill with split chisel peak is used for digging seedlings.

The drill with split chisel peak used to dig holes for planting seedlings must meet very different conditions, which condition their construction:

The cutting area of the drill with split chisel peak must have optimal linear and angular parameters, depending on the terrain conditions in which it is worked.

The drill with split chisel peak must have such a construction that the dislocated soil should be evacuated freely, and should it remain in the pit, it should not prevent its advance and with drawal.

The construction of the drill must ensure easy sharpening, or if possible self-sharpening of cutting edges is possible

During the work, the drills should not cause the walls of the excavated pits to be pressed, nor the mixing of the detached layers of earth, when this is required

In general the the drill with split chisel peak must be have an homogeneous structure to respond of imposed requirements.

The induction hardening simulation method is used for all kinds of geometry types of metal piece. This method consider the change of both parameters like the electromagnetic and thermal parameters and is according with the temperature.

We must verify that the B-H relation is dependent on temperature, passing from iron-magnetic environment form to air. In this case, we observe that the eddy's current problems and thermal diffusion are strongly coupled in the Curie point zone.

As we know the B-H relation is linear and the magnetic permeability is adjusting according to the highest effective value of the magnetic induction (T. Leuca, M. Arion, G. Cheregi, I. Horge, 2007).

We adopt linear pattern (FLUX 2D – tutorial) and the B-H relation.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

For the simulation we use FLUX 2D software package.

In the analysis of this case we must solve the electromagnetic problem with a parallel – plane structure.

The magnetic field problem can be solved by reduced to the determination of a potential vector with a single component, which verifies an similar equation of the scalar potential.

The coupled of thermal diffusion problems with eddy currents is the main problem of every hardening method.

For a better analysis of the results we need to find the result of eddy currents problem (power density) and temperature (thermal capacity and thermal conductivity) (Leuca, Cranganu-Cretu, Arion, Tarcau, 2002), (Leuca, 1997).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The numerical simulation with FLUX 2D software (FLUX 2D – tutorial) allows to determining accurately the relationship between the used frequencies, the desired treatment depth and also the power density.

Fig. 1. The drill with split chisel peak

The desired treatment depth is very important to make a complete map of the hardening process.

Fig. 2. The position of point A and B where is make the analysis of field temperatures

Fig. 3. The temperature in point A

Fig. 4. The temperature in point B

CONCLUSIONS

The numeric simulation of the hardening process is a complex problem because the non-linear problems of eddy currents is provide from non-linear relation of **B-H**.

The non-linear of thermal problem provide from dependence with temperature of thermal parameters (Leuca, Arion, Cheregi, Horge, 2007).

The thermal transfer to the surface of the workpiece is characterized by a convection coefficient with the value $\alpha = 20 \text{ W/m}^2/\text{°C}$ and by a radiation coefficient (characteristic of the thermal transfer by radiation) $\varepsilon = 0,75$ by which the dependence of the thermal transfer coefficient α_e it's a function of temperature

After the simulation process we observe that the coupled of two problems result from strong dependence of relation **B-H** with temperature. Through proposed heat treatment we get a homogenous structure.

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STUDY ON THE RESTORATION OF A VIENNESE PIANO

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Abstract

Any intervention made on works of historical, artistic and environmental interest, in order to protect it and pass it on in its entirety, without eliminating the traces of the passage of time, is called a restoration intervention. Three different professions operate in restoration: the art historian, who should read the work and determine the choices on which to base the work; the restorer, who must make the restoration possible in the best possible way; the scientific expert, who can give correct answers to any uncertainties.

Key words: restore, piano, wood

INTRODUCTION

An acoustic piano has a protective wooden housing comprising the sounding board and the metal strings, which are strung tensioned in a metal frame. Pressing one of the keyboard keys a lined hammer (usually it is lined with felt) is determined to hit the piano strings. After hitting, the hammer rises from the strings, which continue to vibrate at their own resonant frequency. These vibrations are transmitted through a callus to the resonant plate which amplifies these vibrations more efficiently, transferring this acoustic energy to the nearby air considered physically coupled to it. When the flap is released, a damper stops the strings from vibrating, making the sound stop.

The essential elements for producing the sound in a piano are: the metal strings hit by the wooden hammer with a felt head, the gag on which the strings are fixed by means of strings of metal nails, and which transmits the vibration of the string to the wooden soundboard. has the role of transforming the vibration of the string into sound waves. The string alone produces an almost inaudible sound, due to its very small surface, and the resonant plate, which has a considerably larger surface, transforms the vibration of the string much more efficiently into sound, moving a large volume of air. ([http:// ro.wikipedia.org/Pollens](http://ro.wikipedia.org/Pollens) 1995, [http:// ro.wikipedia.org/Thiollet](http://ro.wikipedia.org/Thiollet), J-P, Derecichei, et al., 2013, Derecichei, 2014)

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Only the material of the work of art is restored, so that the author's message is not altered in any way. In order to protect the artistic authenticity, every possible intervention must be treated critically, being very important the elimination of any operation that is not necessarily necessary, therefore a case study must be made for each object to be restored. (www.descopera.ro). Any intervention made on works of historical, artistic and environmental interest, in order to protect it and pass it on in its entirety, without eliminating the traces of the passage of time, is called a restoration intervention.

The contribution of science, which is considered indispensable by all, is often inaccessible due to lack of funds (or too high costs). For this reason, in some restoration projects the scientific investigations are not fully integrated in the work, but are only an accessory, which only enriches the restoration operation, instead of contributing to the determination of the project. (www.incomemagazine.ro, Derecichei, et al., 2014, Derecichei, et al., 2015).

The restoration of the piano as well as the analysis and repair of the damaged elements to be presented was performed at Zaha Ciprian Nicolae individual enterprise.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Depending on the analysis made, the restoration or reconditioning of the piano begins with the treatment for pests, conservation and isolation of the damage caused by them, in our case the restoration can be done. The piano was cleaned of the finishing materials in several stages. It started with the help of a scraper, with a belt grinding machine with abrasive belts with granules of 40 microns / cm square and made by hand with abrasive materials with granules of 40-60 microns / cm square in the first phase and later with granules of 80- 100 microns / cm square, no strippers were used because they are detached elements that will have to be glued in place and if stripping material enters those places it will need to be removed because the adhesive does not adhere to the strippers. After coarse cleaning, check the degree of damage to the veneer on the piano surfaces. Cleaning of the finishing material is done on all the wooden elements of the piano and is done on the length of the fiber of the material. The areas with detachment and / or impact problems are analyzed, the lack of material is marked and the repair of these areas will start depending on the degree of destruction. (fig.1) (Derecichei et al., 2017, Derecichei et al., 2018, Derecichei et al., 2018, Ganea, et al., 2010).

The restoration of the piano begins with the dismantling of the moving and connecting elements, ie the metal parts such as: hinges, wheels, shield, locks, etc., or used solutions for cleaning and degreasing metal elements.

Fig. 1. Keyboard (own source)

After checking all the parts, note all the defects that need to be remedied and the procedures to be followed depending on the duration and complexity of the work to be done (fig.1). The works are scheduled in a certain order and the next steps are taken. In all cases where a treatment of insect-infested wood is needed in combination with the preventive protection of the wood against insect attack, we apply an insecticide solution suitable for removing insects from the wooden structures of the objectives. Needle syringes were used for surface and deep impregnation of the wood, by spraying and brushing.

Fig.2. The flaps are complete but some damaged - no ivory elements (own source)

All flat surfaces that needed refilling were cleaned with the help of the manual cutter on which a tail mill with a cutting diameter of 6 mm to 18 mm was mounted, and with the help of guides the destroyed veneer was removed from the surfaces. Following the processing steps with hand and electric tools, the processing of surfaces for all piano components began. The piano housing was completely cleaned with abrasive materials with granulations of 120 microns / cm square and we started edging the edge of the piano with veneer following the direction of the fiber before cleaning and positioning it according to the initial shape. (Lucaci et al., 2013, Lucaci, et al., 2014, Lucaci, et al., 2016)

The next step was to clean and repair the keyboard, checking the flaps, hammers and other components. The hammers being numbered and cleaned of dust, the felt was cleaned from them and the felt was completely replaced from the keyboard housing (fig.2 and fig.3). For the damaged flaps, the ivory elements were replaced with others of the same age from another defective piano, these being adapted to the necessary shape and size, they being cleaned, rounded and bleached like the others.

Fig.3. Polishing of elements (own source)

CONCLUSIONS

By prolonging the life of old furniture, you become actively and responsibly involved in protecting the environment and, in addition, you make financial savings. In each old object that you want to bring back to life, case studies and necessarily insecticide treatments must be done, in

order to eliminate their pests. Restoring and reconditioning a variety of old wooden objects from musical instruments, picture frames, mirror frames to tinplate, weaving looms, various objects made over 100 years ago as well as church elements and personal museums I found that the treatment with insecticides leads to considerable prolongation of the life of objects. For large objects, it is recommended to place them in an isolated room and treat them with insecticide until the pests are finally controlled.

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STRUCTURE STANDS EVALUATION USING VERTICAL DIFFERENTIATION INDEX

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Abstract

The use of the vertical differentiation index in terms of establishing the structure of some stands and assessing the correlations between the values of this index and the percentage of wood affected by disturbing factors and variations in land inclination provides practical information for external factors. This paper aimed to determine the vertical differentiation index for stands with different structures and to correlate these values with the percentage of wood in the total volume of stands affected by destabilizing factors, as well as to correlate this index with the slope. The vertical differentiation index shows the structure of the stand in relation to the variations in height of the neighbors of each trees analyzed. When this index is close to the value 1, we have strong stands in front of disturbing factors, while the index is closer to the value 0, the stands are extremely vulnerable to the action of the disturbing factors.

Key words: vertical differentiation index, correlation, stand structure, disturbing factors

INTRODUCTION

The knowledge of the stands structure and their capacity to satisfy the assigned functions established by the technical norms, and the analysis carried out by the forest management in accordance with the realities in the field make the establishment of the structure of the stands acquire a crucial influence. In a sense, the structure of the stands with the functions it must perform and its inclusion in the functional type determines the type of treatment that can be proposed by the forest management and then applied by those who manage the forest (Roibu, C.C., et al., 2007).

In recent decades, there have been clearer signs that mention the danger of environmental degradation by decreasing the areas covered by natural forests with uneven age structures (Duduman G., 2011) and the degradation of their structure mainly composed of spruce but also other forest ecosystems that were traditionally not affected by extreme weather events.

This thinks that stand structures will have to be built in the future taking into account extreme weather events, including their impact on the forest.

The „structure“ of a forest may be defined by the spatial distribution of the tree positions, by the particular mingling patterns of the different tree species and by the spatial arrangement of their dimensions. Several tree species

may occur in a given forest, each with its own diameter distribution. The different species and tree sizes may be found in close proximity to each other and thus exhibit a high degree of “mingling”, or they may be spatially segregated (Gadow et al., 2014).

Structural diversity is often seen as an indicator of ecological diversity (Kint, et. al., 2014). This is a debatable assumption. However, a forest’s spatial structure is one of its characteristic attributes. The problem which presents itself is how to characterize and describe forests with different species compositions and size distributions more accurately, using affordable assessment techniques (Merganic et al., 2014).

The vertical differentiation index shows the structure of the stand in relation to the variations in height of the neighbors of each trees analyzed.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

As a material used, 30 trees were measured from each stand, each of them was determined to be neighboring trees in numbers of three to seven and for them the tree heights were determined. The analyzed trees were statistically randomly distributed so that any tree in the stand had the chance to be part of the analyzed survey. The heights were determined with the hypsometer and the neighbors of the trees chosen in the survey (the thirty) were established based on the smallest distances from the tree chosen in the survey.

The determination of the vertical differentiation index for each analyzed stand was made using the following relation(după Ciubotaru A., Păun M., 2014):

$$DH_n = 1/N * \sum [1/n \sum (1 - X_{ijmin}/X_{ijmax})]$$

in which:

- DH_n is the vertical differentiation index;
- N - number of trees measured;
- n – the number of trees considered neighbors of the analyzed tree i ;
- X_{ijmin} – the lowest height in each group of trees analyzed,
- X_{ijmax} - the highest height in each group of trees analyzed.

For each tree analyzed, regardless of whether it is pure or mixed stand, the determination of the vertical differentiation index was made. For these values, the correlation was determined with the percentage of the volume affected by destabilizing factors, respectively with the slope of the land.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The index of the vertical differentiation have values in the range [0; 1]. Values close to 0 indicate small differences in tree height (even -age

stands, continuous profile), while values close to 1 indicate large differences in tree heights (uneven age stands, wavy, lacy or stepped) (after Ciubotaru, Păun, 2014).

Regarding the results obtained from the statistical processing, the following were found: there is quite marked variability between the values of the index of vertical differentiation in stands of all types of structures which supports the statement that forestry interventions can change in a sense or else these values and on the other hand the correlative type links between this index and the percentage of wood affected by destabilizing factors are quite strong. In this sense, the following representative graph (see figure 1) is presented below:

Fig. 1 Wood volume percent affected by Windthows in correlation with vertical differentiation index

The correlative type links between the vertical differentiation index and the slope of the terrain are not as strong (see figure 2) as in the previous case. Thus the correlation coefficient determined in this case has the value of 0.61 while for the previous correlation it had the value of -0.96. This shows that there is a strong inverse correlation between the percentage of wood affected by destabilizing factors and the values of the vertical differentiation index.

Fig. 2 - Slopes in corelation with vertical differentiation index

CONCLUSIONS

The vertical differentiation index is useful in forestry practice in order to be able to build stable stands in the future due to disturbing factors. When this index is close to the value 1, we have strong stands in front of disturbing factors, while the index is closer to the value 0, the stands are extremely vulnerable to the action of the disturbing factors.

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3D MODELLING ASSISTED BY SOLIDWORKS SOFTWARE TO CREATE THE PRODUCT "SCA CHAIR"

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Abstract

*This paper shows how easy it is to develop a 3D product that we want to launch in production line through the SolidWorks design software, which helps a lot when it comes to strength, functionality, raw material and production costs. It took about ten hours of actual work to make the complete assembly *SCA 3D*, which is very short time, and if the complete assembly is made using SolidWorks software it can be noticed that the assembly can be mounted, has mechanical strength as one can notice in the strength testing results when the chair is put to various forces or tensile tests. There are two very useful aspects in the design process, namely: if a change is made to an object part of an (sub)assembly, the assembly, respectively the subassembly will change, and the related technical drawings will be modified automatically and it will warn us if a mistake is made, and the second feature is that objects are physically assembled while taking constraints into consideration.*

Key words: SCA chair, design, SolidWorks software, functionality, chair testing

INTRODUCTION

SolidWorks is a computer-aided 3D geometric modelling software package for mechanical designers. It is a native, easy to learn and user-friendly Windows application, which allows users to model parts as individual entities, the modelling of part assemblies and to generate 2D documentation. (Vegra, 2019)

Usually, the modelling of a part begins with the drawing of a design and starting from this design the graphic base feature is generated, and then the other construction elements necessary to complete the model are added. Once a 3D model is made, it can be refined by adding, altering or rearranging the building blocks of which it is made. Developing complex models made in SolidWorks software mean using more than two functions or tools on a single model.

The SCA project came into being because the wood raw material became very expensive and certain projects became more expensive. The SCA chair is a concept that is designed in such a way that the wood material used to develop it is very easy to process, and the parts that make up this chair are designed in such a way that if certain dimensions are not respected in the case of certain parts they can be reused to another parts of the same chair.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

SCA is a folding chair designed for both camping and garden, but also for public use. It is easy to transport and takes up very little space. A professional-grade CAD software was used to carry out this project, namely SOLIDWORKS 2010 Professional, which is software that aided a lot in the design, testing and price calculation of this chair, as well as in the calculation of the necessary raw material and the required components to develop it.

In the first phase, the 3D model was created, which was assembled, checked and tested, after which the production and transport costs were also calculated using this software. After making these steps, the chair had to be modified in such a way that it was made at the lowest possible production costs without changing the structure or strength of the chair. By making the changes aforementioned it was possible to check and test the chair once again after the last changes.

In order to have a broader view of the assembly one can apply the “explode function” of the software, in which each component part is displaced in such a way that all the components can be seen.

Fig. 1. Explode SCA

In order to get as close to reality as possible when designing an assembly or a body in SolidWorks, we can make several studies regarding the strength of the body under certain conditions as described below:

- First, we will test the assembly at the force of 120 kg of pressure applied perpendicularly to the chair and backrest and with fixing from the lower end of the front and back chair legs, which comes on a flat surface (e.g. floor);
- In each study, the SolidWorks software helps us with a report for each element on which there were applied forces that generated changes on those elements, shaping the properties of the study within this paper.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the study on the chair pressure testing, the warning sensors provide great assistance when we are limited by the constraint by which an element in the chair body must not exceed certain values. In this case we place a sensor to warn us whenever this weight is exceeded and no matter how many bodies we have in the assembly, or if the bodies are not made of the same material, the sensor warn us whether the value is exceeded.

The tables below present all the conclusions of the study:

Table 1

All the conclusions of the study

Study name	Study 1
Analysis type	Static
Mesh Type:	Solid Mesh
Solver type	FFEPlus
Inplane Effect:	Off
Soft Spring:	Off
Inertial Relief:	Off
Thermal Effect:	Input Temperature
Zero strain temperature	298.000000
Units	Kelvin
Include fluid pressure effects from SolidWorks Flow Simulation	Off
Friction:	Off
Ignore clearance for surface contact	Off

The table below shows the units of measurement that were applied in the study:

Table 2
The units of measurement that were applied in the study

Unit system:	SI
Length/Displacement	mm
Temperature	Kelvin
Angular velocity	rad/s
Stress/Pressure	N/m ²

The properties that were applied to each element in this study are showed in the tables below:

Table 3
The properties that were applied to each in this study

Material name:	[SW]Fag		
Description:	Material fag		
Material Source:			
Material Model Type:	Linear Elastic Isotropic		
Default Failure Criterion:	Unknown		
Application Data:	18.04.2021		
Property Name	Value	Units	Value Type
Elastic modulus	1.9e+012	N/m ²	Constant
Poisson's ratio	0.29	NA	Constant
Shear modulus	3e+008	N/m ²	Constant
Mass density	720	kg/m ³	Constant
Tensile strength	5	N/m ²	Constant
Compressive strength	5	N/m ²	Constant
Yield strength	2e+007	N/m ²	Constant
Thermal expansion coefficient	10	/Kelvin	Constant

The tables below show all the properties that were applied in this study to each element.

Table 4

All the properties that were applied in this study to each element

Material name:	[SW]Fag (2)
Description:	
Material Source:	
Material Model Type:	Linear Elastic Isotropic
Default Failure Criterion:	Unknown

The table below shows how the surfaces were configured and what tolerances were applied.

Table 5

The surfaces were configured and what tolerances were applied

Mesh Type:	Solid Mesh
Mesher Used:	Standard mesh
Automatic Transition:	Off
Smooth Surface:	On
Jacobian Check:	4 Points
Element Size:	11 mm
Tolerance:	0.55 mm
Quality:	High
Number of elements:	42859
Number of nodes:	82028
Time to complete mesh(hh:mm:ss):	00:00:10
Computer name:	DESKTOP-3LM6GFQ

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the design of this chair has successfully passed all the endurance tests performed in SolidWorks software at 120 kgf according to the above test results and is ready to enter series production. The approximate deviation from reality is 10%, since the chair was tested by making use of exact forces and at an exact weight applied on the selected parts. The report results may include small deviations that fall within the tolerated limits due to the quality of the wood and the way it dries.

The optimization of the necessary raw material has been successfully achieved and it is no longer necessary to change the structure of the chair. It results that the technical documentation shows no errors and the parts are combined smoothly, so they can be successfully manufactured in the production workshops. In the series production this *SCA chair* can sustain a tolerance of ± 2 mm per gauge and $\pm 0,5$ in the case of part processing operations.

The *SCA chair* has been designed with SolidWorks software and meets all standards in terms of strength, safety and quality. After testing this

chair at 120 kgf one can state that it is a solid chair, although it is a folding chair that is easy to transport and store. In brief, the *SCA chair* is much more efficient than any other model of folding chair because it has double folding and takes up very little space when folded.

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ANALYTICAL STUDY OF DISPLACEMENTS AND DEFORMATIONS OF WOODEN BEAMS USING THE METHOD OF INITIAL PARAMETERS

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Abstract

The work presented and conceived by the author is intended to be a starting point in all calculations of strength and rigidity. It can be considered as a novelty in the case of these types of problems through the calculation program designed by the author. The paper briefly presents the analytical study of the problem, focusing on numerical analysis. The constructive element considered is made of wood, but can be adapted for any other type of material.

Key words: analytical, numerical, bar, kinetics, parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Practical engineering experience has often confirmed the importance of the behavior and safe operation of the components of mechanical or civil structures. As it is known, the safety of operation is largely related to the calculations of strength and rigidity in execution projects.

The mechanical analysis of the different elements within the different constructive or mechanical structures also implies an approach to the problems related to their rigidity calculation. The present paper wishes to present in detail the practical analytical and numerical application of the method of initial parameters applied to an element of wood material component of a structure. The author considered in the paper an element made of beam-type wood, with a circular section of constant diameter and its length. The initial data of the presented paper are the following:

- l , beam length;
- E , Young's module;
- I , the moment of axial inertia;
- σ_{adm} , the allowable tension of the material;
- ν_{adm} , maximum allowed arrow;
- φ_{adm} , the permissible rotation of the beam sections.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Regarding the admissible arrow, it is chosen depending on the use and the place where the constructive element is located.

In the case of the initial parameter's method, it is sought to determine the general expressions of the kinematic parameters represented by displacements and rotations, as well as of the static parameters represented by the bending moments and the shear forces.

Unlike the direct integration method, the method presented and applied in the paper presents a much simpler calculation algorithm compared to the direct integration method even for a small number of intervals of variation of the bending moment, the need to determine the integration constants by writing is eliminated. boundary and boundary conditions between intervals (Catargiu, Kopenetz, 2001, Ciofoaia, Curtu, 1986)

The case study was performed on the bar element loaded with a system of equilibrium forces composed of a uniformly distributed force, a concentrated force and a bending moment.

The following notations have been adopted

q , intensity of the force evenly distributed;

F , concentrated external force;

The constructive element is considered in the paper as simply supported, it being part of the statically determined systems. The study starts from the mechanical analysis of the original parameters with the prior determination of the connection forces from the supports of the considered constructive element. The kinetics allowable values chosen by the author are:

- $v_{adm} = \frac{1}{600} [\text{mm}]$
- $\varphi_{adm} = 1^\circ$
- $\sigma_{adm} = 120 \left[\frac{\text{N}}{\text{mm}^2} \right]$
- the moment of axial inertia of the section, $I = (\pi \cdot D^4)/64 [\text{m}^4]$;
- the allowable arrow was considered to be, $L/1000 = 2 [\text{mm}]$
- allowable rotation, $\varphi_{adm} = 1^\circ$
- uniformly distributed load having intensity $q = \rho \cdot g \cong 50 [\text{kN} / \text{m}]$.

The study tries to present besides the application of the method of the initial parameters and a way of its numerical application for the case of the considered constructive elements.

Fig. 1 Geometric element loaded with external forces

The practical analytical and numerical study was performed in the XOY plane, considering the constructive element represented only by the bar axis.

Fig. 2 The constructive element represented in the plane by its own longitudinal axis

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The application of the calculation algorithm of the initial parameters method led to the following results (Fetea, 2010), (Goia, 2000), (Ile., 1981)

$$\begin{aligned} \sum M_A &= 0; \\ \sum M_B &= 0; \\ -2V_B + 2.5q + 0.5F &= 0 \\ 2V_A - 0.5q - 1.5F &= 0 \\ V_B &= \frac{(2.5q + 0.5F)}{2} \end{aligned}$$

$$V_A = \frac{(0.5q + 1.5F)}{2}$$

Taking into account the mode of support and loading of the element, the initial parameters identified are the following (Gheorghiu, Hadar, 1998):

$$v_0 = 0;$$

$$\varphi_0 \neq 0;$$

$$M_0 = 0;$$

$$T_0 = V_A = \frac{(0.5q+1.5F)}{2}.$$

Having the initial parameters partially determined the general equation of the arrow becomes (Ivan M. Statica, 1997), (Marțian, 1999):

$$v(x) = \varphi_0 x - \frac{T_0 x^3}{6EI} - \frac{F(x - 0.5)^3}{6EI} + \frac{q(x - 1)^4}{24EI}$$

The rotation of the body axis is non-zero and unknown. To determine it, the author imposed the limit condition (Missir-Vlad, 2002):

$$v(2) = 0 \rightarrow \varphi_0$$

$$v(2) = 0$$

$$\varphi_0 = \frac{\frac{T_0 x^3}{6EI} + \frac{F(x - 0.5)^3}{6EI} - \frac{q(x - 1)^4}{24EI}}{2000}$$

The determined value of the rotation φ_0 is introduced in the general equation of the displacements, obtaining the final expression of their determination. By convenient derivations were obtained the expressions of rotation, respectively of the bending moment and of the shape shear force taking into account the differential equation of the deformed axis Missir-Vlad, Ioana, 2002):

$$\frac{d^2v}{dx^2} = -\frac{M_x}{EI}$$

$$\varphi(x) = \varphi_0 - \frac{T_0 x^2}{2EI} - \frac{F(x - 0.5)^2}{2EI} + \frac{q(x - 1)^3}{6EI}$$

Having the general expressions of the kinematic and static parameters of the cross sections of the considered constructive element, their values can be determined in any element section. For the case studied. a numerical calculation program was designed in Matlab, aiming to determine the same

parameters as in the case of the analytical study of the beam (Muntenu Gh.,1998). The following calculation program designed by the author and named – **The calculation program of the kinematic parameters.**

```

% TITLE - The calculation program of the kinematic parameters
% D, diameter
% E, Young's modulus
% I, axial inertia moment
% F, External force
% L, lenght bar
% q, load intensity
% VA, force reaction in A section
% v, general expression of displacements
% ROT0, initial spin
% ROT, general expression of spin
% v1,v2,v3, displacements by intervals
% rot1,rot2,rot3, spin by intervals
D=400
E=2.1*10^5
I=(pi*D^4)/64
q=50
F=100
L=2000
VA=87.5
ROT0=((87.5*10^3*2^3)*(10^9)/(6*2.1*10^5*1.256*10^9)+(100*(1.5)^3)
*(10^12)/(6*2.1*10^5*1.256*10^9)-
(50*(1)^4)*(10^12)/(24*2.1*10^5*1.256*10^9))/2000
syms x E I
v=((ROT0*x)*10^3)-(((VA*x^3)*10^12)/(6*E*I))-(((F*(x-
0.5)^3)*10^12)/(6*E*I))+(((q*(x-1)^4)*10^12)/(24*E*I))
ROT=diff(v)
M=-(diff(ROT))*(E*I);
T=diff(M);
for x=[0 0.1 0.2 0.3 0.4 0.5 ];
    v1=((ROT0*x).*10^3)-(((87.5*x.^3)*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I))
end
for x=[0.6 .7 .8 .9 1];
    v2=((ROT0*x).*10^3)-(((87.5*x.^3).*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I))-(((100*(x-
0.5).^3).*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I));
end;
for x=[1.1 1.2 1.3 1.4 1.5 1.6 1.7 1.8 1.9 2];

```

```

v3=((ROT0*x).*10^3)-(((87.5*x.^3).*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I))-(((100*(x-
0.5).^3).*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I))+(((50*(x-
1).^4).*10^12)./(24*2.1*10^5*I));
end;

```

```

syms x VA E I
v1=((ROT0*x)*10^3)-(((VA*x^3)*10^12)/(6*E*I))
rot1=diff(v1)
for x=[0 0.1 0.2 0.3 0.4 0.5 ]
    for VA=87.5
        for E=2.1*10^5
            for I=1.256*10^9
                rot1=746729692537419125/2305843009213693952
(500000000000*VA*x.^2)./(E*I)
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

syms x VA E I
v2=((ROT0*x).*10^3)-(((87.5*x.^3).*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I))-(((100*(x-
0.5).^3).*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I))
rot2=diff(v2)
for x=[0.6 .7 .8 .9 1]
    for VA=87.5
        for E=2.1*10^5
            for I=1.256*10^9
                rot2=746729692537419125/2305843009213693952
(11274289152000000000000000*x.^2)./(5411658792960001*I)
(12884901888000000000000000*(x - 1/2).^2)./(5411658792960001*I)
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

syms x VA E I
v3=((ROT0*x).*10^3)-(((87.5*x.^3).*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I))-(((100*(x-
0.5).^3).*10^12)./(6*2.1*10^5*I))+(((50*(x-
1).^4).*10^12)./(24*2.1*10^5*I))
rot3=diff(v3)
for x=[1.1 1.2 1.3 1.4 1.5 1.6 1.7 1.8 1.9 2]

```

```

for VA=87.5
  for E=2.1*10^5
    for I=1.256*10^9
      rot3=(21474836480000000000000000*(x - 1).^3)/(5411658792960001*I) -
(12884901888000000000000000*(x - 1/2).^2)/(5411658792960001*I) -
(11274289152000000000000000*x.^2)/(5411658792960001*I) +
746729692537419125/2305843009213693952
    end
  end
end
end

```

The determined values of the arrows and of the rotations in the body sections are:

Displacements	Rotations	Sections coordinates
v1 = 0	rot1 = 0.3238	for x=0
v1 =0.0323	rot1 = 0.3222	for x=.1
v1 =0.0643	rot1 = 0.3172	for x=.2
v1 =0.0957	rot1 = 0.3089	for x=.3
v1 =0.1260	rot1 = 0.2973	for x=.4
v1 =0.1550	rot1 = 0.2824	for x=.5
v2 =0.1823	rot2 =0.2622	for x=.6
v2 =0.2072	rot2 =0.2350	for x=.7
v2 =0.2291	rot2 =0.2006	for x=.8
v2 =0.2471	rot2 =0.1592	for x=.9
v2 =0.2607	rot2 =0.1106	for x=1
v3 =0.2690	rot3 =0.0549	for x=1.1
v3 =0.2714	rot3 =-0.0076	for x=1.2
v3 =0.2672	rot3 =-0.0769	for x=1.3
v3 = 0.2558	rot3 =-0.1528	for x=1.4
v3 =0.2365	rot3 =-0.2350	for x=1.5
v3 =0.2086	rot3 =-0.3233	for x=1.6
v3 =0.1716	rot3 =-0.4177	for x=1.7
v3 =0.1249	rot3 =-0.5178	for x=1.8
v3 =0.0679	rot3 =-0.6235	for x=1.9
v3 =3.8164e-17	rot3 =-0.7346	for x=2

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions that can be drawn from this study are the following:

1. The elaboration of this program by the author represents an element of novelty, which allows solving any problem of static calculation

of wooden beams, regardless of the external forces acting, the type of wood material, its mechanical-physical characteristics. The problem is easy to solve just by changing the values in the program. This feature will make the work of any engineer easier, being necessary to apply only the calculation program used.

2. The program made by the author allows the exact determination of the kinematic parameters in any of the sections of the constructive element.
3. The program allows the determination of displacements and rotations for any constructive element of bar type, regardless of the type of material, the external forces and the considered supports.
4. The numerical analysis through the conceived program, leads to exact and correct results regarding the displacements and rotations according to the supports of the constructive element.
5. The practical implementation of numerical calculation methods is certainly in the future the only viable methods in quickly and accurately solving computational problems in engineering.

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ANALYSIS OF THE DEGRADATION STAGE OF THE ROAD SYSTEM ON THE FOREST ROADS WITHIN P.U. I CISLA (CISLA-BORȘA COMPOUNDING OFFICE)

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Abstract

The need to analyze the state of forest roads results from the concern for their maintenance in order to ensure a transport network capable of serving all the needs of the forest sector.

In order to determine solutions for the maintenance and rational exploitation of forest roads, in this paper were studied a series of correlative links in order to identify the existence of correlations between declivity, average pit depth, road system thickness, and their total affected area.

The case study was carried out on the forest roads Arineș and Izvorul Ursului, with a length of 1800 m, located in Borșa (Maramureș), in the P.U. I Cislă, Cislă Borșa Composesorate.

In order to obtain a correlative link between all the elements determined and presented in tables 1 and 2, all types of regression equations (logarithmic, polynomial, exponential, linear and power) were tested, so that the interdependence between them can be established.

The testing of the four ranges determined for the above-mentioned elements on the two forest roads revealed the existence of distinctly significant correlations between the declivity and the total area affected.

The regression equations obtained by polynomial correlation, which are distinctly significant, show the existence of close interdependencies between the declivity of longitudinal roads, the total area affected by their operation and climatic factors, the thickness of the road system and the depth of pits formed over time.

From the interpretation of the tests performed it can be seen that in the road sectors with higher declivities the surface of the roadway, respectively the thickness of the road system are much more subject to physical degradation.

Key words: forest roads, geometric elements, exploitation, analyze, correlations;

INTRODUCTION

In forest management, taking into account the complexity of the functions performed by forest roads (Gucinski et al.,2001), the future strategy for the expansion of road networks must aim first of all at the strict observance of forest management in order to ensure a continuous assurance of forest production on the one hand and to exercise the protective role of forests along with a more efficient accessibility of the forest fund. (Ungur et al.,2003; Iovan, 2017).

In order to analyze the stage of degradation of the road system on forest roads within P.U. I Cislă, a series of correlations were sought between the declivity, the average depth of the pits, the thickness of the road system, and their total affected area.

The need to analyze the state of forest roads results from the concern for their maintenance in order to ensure a transport network capable of serving all the needs of the forestry sector in close accordance with current environmental requirements (Lugoa et al., 2000; Lazăr et al., 2008), this is due to the fact that starting the design and execution of new roads involves a difficult and obviously expensive methodology, so that the maintenance of existing ones becomes a major concern (Ungur, 2005; Nevečerel et al., 2007).

In order to determine solutions for the maintenance and rational exploitation of forest roads, in this paper were studied a series of correlative links in order to identify the existence of correlations between declivity, average pit depth, road system thickness, and their total affected area.

For this purpose, two forest roads with a length of 1800 m each were analyzed, fragmented on sections of 100 m, on which certain geometric elements, constructive characteristics and existing degradations were followed, which are presented in table no. 1 and 2.

Ways of communication (forest roads) are the physical support for the opening of forest basins (Klč P.,2005). A rational management of the forest fund must respect the technical, managerial, economic and ecological principles (Murphy, 1985; Crețu, et al.,2006).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The case study was carried out on the forest roads Arineș and Izvorul Ursului, with a length of 1800 m, located in Borșa (Maramureș), in the P.U. I Cisla, Cisla Borșa Composesorate. The roads are located in a mountainous region, the predominant geomorphological unit being the slope, with mostly undulating terrain configuration, altitudes between 800 and 1770 m. The current accessibility of the forest fund is 77%, and the current density of forest transport facilities is 3,1 m / ha (20***). The coordinates of the perimeter that includes these two forest roads are between 47°38' 04" / 40°39' 04" N and respectively 24°50' 33" / 24°52' 01" E.

In order to determine the geometric peculiarities and the existing degradations, a visual inspection of the analyzed roads was performed.

The equipment used was:

- ▶ telemetry (for determining distances, surfaces and depths)
- ▶ clinometer (for determining the slope in longitudinal profile)

Fig. 1. Case study localization – Cisla P.U. I, Borșa Composesorate (Maramureș) (20***)

Declivity (%) shows the degree of inclination of the road in longitudinal profile (Olteanu N.,1996) and was determined with the help of the clinometer, the depth of the pits (cm) was determined with the help of the rangefinder by measuring from the upper level of the roadway, the thickness of the road system (cm) starting from the maximum value (initial 30 cm) and the total area affected was determined in percentages.

All these geometric elements and the degradations formed at the level of the roadway, respectively of the drainage ditches present the current stage of the forest road platform (A.C.F., 2006) analyzed.

Table 1

The value of geometric elements and degradations, on the Arineș forest road

Section	Interval [m]	Declivity %	Average pit depth [cm]	Road system thickness [cm]	Total area affected [%]
1	0-100	9,0	10	13,0	55,0
2	100-200	10,5	5,0	20,0	48,0
3	200-300	10,0	6,0	21,0	50,0
4	300-400	11,0	9,0	16,0	44,0
5	400-500	11,0	5,0	19,0	43,0
6	500-600	10,0	6,0	19,0	48,0
7	600-700	9,5	6,0	20,0	39,0
8	700-800	8,0	5,5	22,0	49,0
9	800-900	9,0	8,0	16,0	48,0
10	900-1000	9,5	8,5	16,0	47,0
11	1000-1100	11,0	6,0	19,0	40,0
12	1100-1200	10,0	5,5	19,0	42,0
13	1200-1300	9,5	8,0	15,0	50,0
14	1300-1400	10,0	8,0	18,0	44,0
15	1400-1500	8,0	10,0	14,0	35,0
16	1500-1600	10,5	6,0	20,0	43,0
17	1600-1700	11,0	5,0	20,0	40,0
18	1700-1800	10,5	6,5	20,0	46,0

Table 2
The value of geometric elements and degradations, on the Izvorul Ursului forest road

Section	Interval [m]	Declivity %	Average pit depth [cm]	Road system thickness [cm]	Total area affected [%]
1	0-100	8,5	9,0	15,0	53,0
2	100-200	9,0	10,0	13,0	54,0
3	200-300	11,0	12,0	13,0	40,0
4	300-400	10,5	6,5	21,0	38,0
5	400-500	11,0	6,5	21,0	41,0
6	500-600	12,0	12,5	15,0	35,0
7	600-700	12,0	13,0	15,0	36,0
8	700-800	10,0	12,0	14,0	41,0
9	800-900	10,0	12,5	12,0	40,0
10	900-1000	9,0	13,0	14,0	38,0
11	1000-1100	10,5	11,0	14,0	41,0
12	1100-1200	10,5	10,0	16,0	37,0
13	1200-1300	11,0	8,0	18,0	39,0
14	1300-1400	12,0	6,0	24,0	38,0
15	1400-1500	11,0	5,0	24,0	40,0
16	1500-1600	10,0	5,0	23,0	39,0
17	1600-1700	9,0	14,0	12,0	46,0
18	1700-1800	9,5	14,5	14,0	45,0

In order to obtain a correlative link between all the elements determined and presented in tables 1 and 2, all types of regression equations (logarithmic, polynomial, exponential, linear and to power) were tested, so that the interdependence between them can be established (Horvat, D. 1994).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The testing of the four ranges of values determined for the above-mentioned elements on the two forest roads resulted in the existence of distinctly significant correlations between the slope and the total affected area, partially presented in figures 2 and 3.

Fig.2. Graphical representation of the polynomial correlation between the declivity and the total affected area resulting on the Arineş forest road

Table 3
The value of the correlation relations obtained between the elements studied on the two forest roads

Forest road / Determined elements	Declivity / Total area affected	Average pit depth / The thickness of the road system
Arineş	R ² =0,7632 R=0,8736	R ² =0,8341 R=0,9132
Izvorul Ursului	R ² =0,6043 R=0,7805	R ² =0,9185 R=0,9583

Fig.3. Graphical representation of the polynomial correlation between the slope and the total affected area resulting on the Izvorul Ursului forest road

The values of the correlation ratios obtained for the value ranges presented in tables 2 and 3, show the existence of a polynomial correlation, with a correlation ratio $R^2=0,7632$ (Figure2), respectively $R^2=0,6043$ (Figure3) therefore distinctly significant (Giurgiu V., 1972) from a statistical point of view, in terms of the interdependence between the slope and the total area affected on the Arineş and Izvorul Ursului forest roads.

At the same time, there were distinctly significant correlations between the average depth of the pits and the thickness of the road system, with $R^2=0,8341$ for the Arineş forest road, respectively $R^2=0,9185$ for the Izvorul Ursului forest road.

These polynomial correlations show that there is a very direct link between the declivity and the total area affected, respectively the average depth of the pits and the thickness of the road system of the analyzed forest roads.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to increase efficiency by ensuring optimal conditions for the practice of sustainable forestry, a pragmatic approach to the design and maintenance of forest roads is needed. In this sense, it is necessary to periodically monitor the evolution of the technical condition of the existing forest roads.

From the results obtained in this study it can be proposed that in the future to use GIS technology, in order to increase the accuracy and quality of forest road design (Crainic G.C.,2017) and subsequently the implementation of practical and efficient decisions regarding the maintenance of these roads (Martínez-Zavala L. et al.,2008; Tamaş Ş. et al., 2006).

The regression equations obtained by polynomial correlation, which are distinctly significant, show the existence of close interdependencies between the declivity of longitudinal roads, the total area affected by their operation and climatic factors, the thickness of the road system and the depth of pits formed over time.

From the interpretation of the tests performed it can be seen that in the road sectors with higher slopes the surface of the roadway, respectively the thickness of the road system are much more subject to physical degradation. These findings can be explained by the fact that in these sectors of forest roads the traction force and the adhesion force of motor vehicles act with an increased intensity on the road system, compared to the sectors with lower declivities.

Another explanation for the degradation of the road system and the road part consists in the different action of climatic factors (precipitation, temperatures) as well as the exposure of the roads. Also a decisive factor in this direction is represented by the hydrological and hydrographic peculiarities of the forest basins in which the forest roads are located. Thus, where there are small permanent watercourses, they take over and ensure a controlled drainage of water, while where temporary or torrential water formations are formed, the water causes a physical aggression on the technical quality of the roads.

By establishing a distinctly significant correlation between the analyzed geometric elements, it can be said that they directly influence the quality of the infrastructure and superstructure of forest roads (Coulter E.D. et al.,2006).

Carrying out repeated and sustained studies over time could significantly contribute to obtaining the most efficient methods for the long-term exploitation and maintenance of forest roads (Zarojanu D. et al., 2006), in line with current and perspective of sustainable forestry.

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SPRUCE FORESTS WITH *SPHAGNUM GIRGENSOHNII* FROM THE WETLANDS OF THE WESTERN CARPHATIANS MOUNTAINS AND SOMEȘUL CALD-SOMEȘUL RECE INTERFLUVE, AND THEIR PHYTOCENOLOGICAL AND ECOPROTECTIVE IMPORTANCE

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Abstract

Spruce cenoses established on sphagnum grow at altitudes ranging between 1,020 m and rising up to 1,601 m, vegetating near springs, streams, shaded valleys and slopes with high humidity rates, at the edge of oligotrophic and eutrophic peatlands, on turbid, acid moist soils, which are poor in mineral substances.

The spectrum of bioforms (see Figure 1) shows that the majority species are hemicryptophytes (55%), followed by phanerophytes (17.5%), cameophytes (15%), geophytes (10%) and terophytes (2.5%).

The floristic elements (see Figure 2) highlight the predominance of circumpolar species (32.5%), followed by Eurasian (25%), European (15%), cosmopolitan and Central European species in the same percentage (i.e. 7.5%), Carpatho-Balkan species (5%), while the lowest share is represented by endemic-Carpathian, Ponto-Pannonian and Artic-Alpine species (2.5% each).

The diagram of ecological indices (see Figure 3) highlights the dominance of mesophilic species (57.5%), followed by mezo-hygrophilous ones (25%), eurihydric (10%), and xeromesophilic species (5%). Considering the temperature factor, microtherms (55%), euritherms (27.5%), micro-mesotherms (12.5%), and cryophiles (5%) are dominant. In relation to the chemical reaction of the soil, the species hierarchy encompasses euriionic (27.5%), acidophilic (25%), acid-neutrophilic (22.5%) strongly acidophilic (17.5%) and weakly acid-neutrophilic (7.5%) species.

The karyotype spectrum (see Figure 4) shows the dominance of polyploids (57.5%), followed by diploids (32.5%), and diplo-polyploids (7.5%), and of species with unknown karyotype (i.e. 2.5%). The diploid index is 0.56.

Key words: phytocenoses, bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, karyotype.

INTRODUCTION

The floristic composition of the association (see Table 1) totals 40 cormophyte species and 10 bryophyte species, which shows a great biodiversity. The tree line is dominated by the indicator and characteristic

species, *Picea abies*, which has a general coverage of 43.5% ADm and maximum value of constant (K=V). In addition to spruce stands, there are several isolated specimens of *Sorbus aucuparia* and *Fagus sylvatica*. The canopy cover is average, starting from a consistency of 0.5 and rising to 0.8. The height of the trees is generally higher in case of older specimens and lower in case of young specimens, and ranging between 15 and 28 m. The diameters of the tree trunks start from 20-38 cm, which shows the presence of some old trees with slow growth. The layer of poorly developed shrubs and subshrubs consists of only a few species (i.e. *Pinus mugo*, *Sambucus racemosa*, *Rubus hirtus*, *Rubus idaeus*). Within the association, the *Vaccinium myrtillus* plants are present in all surveys, with a good general coverage of 13.15% ADm and maximum value of constant (K = V), which negatively influences the participation of other species that form part of the association.

Extrazonal spruce phytocenoses located on sphagnets were described in Romania in the following areas: Parâng Mountains (Borhidi, 1971), Poiana Stampei (Coldea, 1991), Someșul Rece Valley (I. Pop et al., 1984), Bihor Mountains (Coldea, 1991), Iezer-Păpușa Mountains (Alexiu, 1998), Arieșul Mare-Arieșul Mic interstream area (Ursu, 2013), and in the northern part of Bihor Mountains (Togor, 2016).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The surveyed material represents the priority natural ecosystems consisting by dominant spruce forests developed on *Sphagnum girgensohnii* within the Western Carpathians (a.k.a. Apuseni) Mountains, Someșul Cald-Someșul Rece interfluvium. We carried out 10 phytocenological surveys on the most representative phytocenoses. All plant species found, with the assessment of abundance and dominance (AD) for each species according to the Braun-Blanquet scale (Braun-Blanquet et Pavillard 1928), were enclosed in the association table (see Table 1). The *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* association was analysed and characterized ecologically, phytocenologically, cytogenetically based on the association table and histograms with reference to the distribution of bioforms, floristic elements, ecological indices, and genetic karyotypes.

Finding and description of the association was made based on the floristic criterion, with the help of characteristic, indicator, dominant and differential species. The name of the association is in accordance with the provisions established by the International Code of Phytosociological Nomenclature (Weber et al., 2000). Classification of species by corresponding coeno-taxonomic units (i.e. suballiances, alliances, orders, classes) was made in accordance with the ecological-floristic systems

elaborated by Tüxen (Tüxen, 1955), and Braun-Blanquet (Braun-Blanquet, 1964), and on the basis of more recent works (Coldea et al., 1997 and Sanda et al., 2003, 2008).

The ecological and phytocenological characterization of the species within the surveyed territory was made according to dedicated literature (Sanda et al., 2003), (Ciocârlan, 2009), (Sârbu et al., 2013).

The information on the value of ecological indices, bioforms, floristic elements, and number of chromosomes are presented according to synthesis works elaborated by various researchers (Pop, 1977, 1982), (Sanda et al., 2003, 2008), (Cristea et al., 2004), (Ciocârlan, 2009), (Burescu et Toma, 2005), (Doniță et al., 2005).

We carried out the analysis of phytocenoses with regard the influence of ecological factors moisture (M), temperature (T) and soil chemical reaction (R) according to a previous paper works (Sanda et al., 2003), which adapted the ecological indices values for the plants in Central Europe on a 1 to 9 scale (Ellenberg, 1974) to the pedoclimatic conditions specific to Romania, by making use of scale ranging between 1 and 6. We made the classification of the species by the corresponding coenotaxa according to the works of other authors (Borza et Boșcaiu, 1965).

Cytogenetic analysis of species by karyotype thereof was done according to the works of Sanda et al., 2003.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the composition of the association there are present species characteristic to the **Abieti-Piceion** alliance and the ATHYRIO-PICETALIA order (i.e. *Athyrium filix-femina*, *Veratrum album*), and a large number of species belonging to the **VACCINIO-PICEETEA** class (i.e. *Vaccinium myrtillus*, *Deschampsia flexuosa*, *Homogyne alpina*, *Oxalis acetosella*, *Calamagrostis villosa*, *Dryopteris cristata*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Luzula sylvatica*, *Polytrichum strictum*, *Vaccinium vitis-idaea*, *Gymnocarpium driopteris*, *Lycopodium anotinum*, *Blechnum spicant*, *Huperzia selago*, *Pinus mugo*, etc.); in phytocenoses there are also present transgressive species from the **QUERCO-FAGETEA** classes (i.e. *Cystopteris fragilis*, *Polygonatum latifolium*, *Polygonatum verticillatum*, *Senecio nemorensis ssp. jacquinianus*, *Gentiana asclepiadea*, *Fagus sylvatica*, etc.). Among the spruce forests containing *Sphagnum girgensohnii* within the Bihor Mountains, Someșul Cald-Someșul Rece interfluvial stand out two acidophilic, glacial relict species specific for sphagnum belonging to the **OXYCOCCO-SPHAGNETEA** classes (i.e. *Eriophorum vaginatum*, *Vaccinium microcarpum*). The well-developed

bryophyte layer is rich in species, maintaining high level of moisture and acidity of phytocenoses.

With regard the floristic composition, following the review of the association table (see Table 1) and histograms, compared to the work of Togor (Togor, 2016) one can notice that we found in the association 40 cormophyte and 10 bryophytes species while Togor (Togor, 2016) found 53 cormophytes and 11 bryophytes. Comparing the spectrum of bioforms shows that hemicryptophyte species are dominant with a percentage of 55% while in the case of Togor's work (Togor, 2016) hemicryptophytes have a share of 56.61%. The phytogeographic elements consist in circumpolar species i.e. 32.5% while in the case of Togor (Togor, 2016) circumpolar species have a share of 47.17% The diagram of ecological indices shows that in our country mesophiles predominate i.e. 57.5% and at Togor (Togor, 2016) mesohigophiles are dominant with 41.51%; moreover, in our case microtherms' share is 55% and 45.28% in the case of Togor (Togor, 2016); in our research euriionic species percentage is 27.5% while in Togor's research (Togor, 2016) acidophilic species have a 37.75%. The karyological analysis shows that polyploid species have the highest percentage of 57.5%, while in the case of Togor's work (Togor, 2016) their share is only 49.06%.

From the analysis above it results that the some results overlap in some points yet they are not similar since the surveyed areas are not impacted by the same pedoclimatic conditions.

Analysis of the spectrum of bioforms (see Figure 1) shows that the majority species are hemicryptophytes (55%), followed by phanerophytes (17.5%), cameophytes (15%), geophytes (10%), and terophytes (2.5%).

Fig. 1. Spectrum of bioforms in the *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* association
 Legend: MPh = Megaphanerophytes; mPh = Mesophanerophytes; nPh = Nanophanerophytes; Ch = Chamaephytes; H = Hemicryptophytes; G = Geophytes Th = Annual terophytes.

The floristic elements (see Figure 2) shows the predominance of circumpolar species (32.5%), followed by Eurasian (25%), European (15%), cosmopolitan and Central European species in the same percentage (i.e.

7.5%), Carpatho-Balkan species (5%), while the lowest share occurs in the case of endemic-Carpathian, Ponto-Pannonian and Arct-Alpine species (with 2.5% each).

Fig. 2. Spectrum of floristic elements from the *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* association
 Legend: Cp = Circumpolar; Eua = Eurasian; E = European; Ec = Central European; End Carp = Endemite Carpathian; Carp-B = Carpathian-Balkan; Arct-Alp = Arctic-Alpine; Cosm = Cosmopolitan; P-pan = Ponto Pannonian.

The diagram of ecological indices (see Figure 3) highlights the dominance of mesophilic species (57.5%), followed by mesohygrophiles (25%), eurhydres (10%), xeromesophiles (5%). Depending on the temperature, the microtherms (55%), euritherms (27.5%), micro-mesotherms (12.5%), and cryophiles (5%) are dominant. In terms of the chemical reaction of the soil, eurionic (27.5%), acidophilic (25%), acid-neutrophilic (22.5%), strongly acidophilic (17.5%), and weakly acid-neutrophilic (7.5%) species are present.

Fig. 3. Ecological indices diagram for the *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* association

The karyological spectrum (see Figure 4) shows the dominance of polyploids (57.5%), followed by diploids (32.5%), diplo-polyploids (7.5%), and of species with unknown karyotype (2.5%). The diploid index is 0.56.

Fig. 4. The karyological spectrum for the *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* association
 Legend: D = Diploids; P = Polyploids; DP = Dipopoliploids; N = Unknown karyotype.

These very valuable forests are included in the habitat type: R4210 Southeastern Carpathian spruce forests with *Sphagnum sp.* (Doniță et al., 2005). Correspondence: NATURA 2000: 9410 Acidophilous *Picea abies* forests of the montane to alpine levels (**Vaccinio-Piceetea**) PAL.HAB .: 42.2131 Carpathian peat moss spruce forest. Priority habitat, with very high conservation value, including relict species, being included in the list of natural habitats of community interest whose conservation requires the designation of Special Areas of Conservation (AUC) Directive 92/491 EEC, Annex I- in Romania.

Table 1

Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum Kuoch 1954

						Survey No.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		
						Altitude AMSL (mx10)	121	102	130	115	115	160	161	160	122	108		
						Exposure	SV	N	N	N	N	N	-	-	N	N		
						Slope (°)	4	32	12	28	18	2	-	-	12			
						Tree layer consistency	0.8	0.5	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.7	0.7	0.7		
Biof.	Fl. el	M	T	R	G	Tree height (m)	24	26	24	18	20	20	26	28	26	20	K	ADm
						Tree diameter (cm)	28	38	36	20	22	34	34	36	30	24		
						Tree layer coverage (%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	-	-		
						Grass layer coverage (%)	90	80	100	100	10	80	90	80	30	20		
						Moss layer coverage (%)	80	90	50	90	90	70	90	90	100	80		
						Surveyed area (m ²)	80	40	80	120	120	40	40	80	80	80		
MPh	E	0	0	0	D	<i>As. Sphagnum girgensohnii</i>	2	3	3	2	2	3	4	3	2	2		
						<i>As. Picea abies</i>	3	3	3	4	4	2	2	3	4	4	V	42.87
						Abieti-Piceion, Athyrio-Piceetalia												
H	Cosm	4	2.5	0	P	<i>Athyrium filix-femina</i>	+	.	+	I	0.1
G	Eua	4	2.5	4	DP	<i>Veratrum album</i>	+	I	0.02
						Vaccinio-Piceetea												
Ch-nPh	Cp	0	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	2	1	4	+	1	2	+	2	+	1	V	11.87
H	Cp	2	0	1	P	<i>Deschampsia flexuosa</i>	.	+	+	+	1	+	+	.	+	1	V	1.1
H	Alp-E	3.5	2.5	2.5	P	<i>Homogyne alpina</i>	1	.	1	.	.	+	.	.	+	.	IV	1.22
H-G	Cp	4	3	3	D	<i>Oxalis acetosella</i>	1	+	+	+	+	+	.	.	+	+	IV	0.8
H	Eua	4	2.5	1.5	P	<i>Calamagrostis villosa</i>	1	.	+	+	1	+	+	.	+	+	IV	1.3
H	Cp	3.5	2	3	P	<i>Dryopteris cristata</i>	.	+	.	+	+	+	.	+	+	+	IV	0.37
						<i>Polytrichum strictum</i>	.	.	1	1	1	1	.	+	2	1	IV	5.15
MPh-mPh	E	3	2.5	2	D	<i>Sorbus aucuparia</i>	.	.	+	.	+	.	.	+	+	.	III	0.27
H	Ec	3.5	2.5	2	DP	<i>Luzula sylvatica</i>	+	.	+	.	+	.	.	+	+	.	III	0.47
Ch-nPh	Cp	3	2	1	D	<i>Vaccinium vitis-idaea</i>	+	+	+	+	.	.	II	0.17
G	Cp	3	2.5	2	P	<i>Gymnocarpium dryopteris</i>	+	+	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	+	II	0.2
Ch	Cp	4	2.5	2	P	<i>Lycopodium annotinum</i>	+	.	+	+	+	II	0.17
						<i>Dicranum scoparium</i>	1	1	+	.	1	II	2.8
						<i>Sphagnum magellanicum</i>	+	+	+	.	.	II	2.25
H	Cp	3.5	2	1.5	P	<i>Blechnum spicant</i>	+	+	I	0.05
Ch	Cosm	3.5	2	2	P	<i>Huperzia selago</i>	.	.	+	I	0.02

H	Carp-B	3	0	0	D	<i>Hieracium transylvanicum</i>	.	+	.	.	+	.	.	.	+	.	I	0.1	
H	Cp	3.5	0	0	P	<i>Luzula luzuloides</i>	+	.	I	0.07	
H	End	4	2	3	D	<i>Leucantheum waldsteinii</i>	+	I	0.02	
						<i>Polytrichum commune</i>	+	.	I	0.07	
						<i>Polytrichum juniperinum</i>	+	2	I	0.9	
						<i>Hylocomium splendens</i>	+	I	0.07	
Th	Eua	3	0	1.5	D	<i>Melampyrum sylvaticum</i>	+	+	.	.	I	0.1	
MPh	Ec-Alp	0	2	0	D	<i>Pinus mugo</i>	+	+	.	I	0.05	
H	Carp-B	3.5	2	2	P	<i>Campanula abietina</i>	+	I	0.02	
H	Cp	3.5	0	0	P	<i>Dryopteris dilatata</i>	+	I	0.02
H	Cosm	3.5	0	0	P	<i>Cystopteris fragilis</i>	+	I	0.02	
G	P-Pan	3	3.5	4	D	<i>Polygonatum latifolium</i>	+	I	0.02	
H	Eua	3.5	3	3	P	<i>Senecio nemorensis</i> ssp. <i>jacquinianus</i>	+	+	I	0.05	
H	Ec	4	2	4	P	<i>Gentiana asclepiadea</i>	+	I	0.02	
nPh	E	3	2.5	3	P	<i>Rubus hirtus</i>	.	+	I	0.02	
G	Eua	3	2.5	2.5	P	<i>Polygonatum verticillatum</i>	+	I	0.05	
MPh	E	3	2	0	D	<i>Fagus sylvatica</i>	+	+	I	0.05	
H	Eua	3	0	3.5	P	<i>Epilobium montanum</i>	+	I	0.02
						Oxycocco-Sphagnetea													
H	Cp	4.5	0	1.5	D	<i>Eriophorum vaginatum</i>	+	+	1	.	.	II	1.45	
Ch	Arct-Alp	5	0	2	D	<i>Vaccinium microcarpum</i>	+	.	I	0.02	
						<i>Sphagnum fallax</i>	+	.	I	0.07	
						<i>Sphagnum fuscum</i>	+	I	0.02	
						Variae syntaxa													
						<i>Rhytidiadelphus triquetrus</i>	.	1	2	+	+	2	III	5.22
nPh	Cp	3	3	3	DP	<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	.	+	.	.	+	+	II	0.17	
H	Cp	4	1.5	0	P	<i>Epilobium anagalidifolium</i>	.	+	.	.	.	+	II	0.12	
mPh	Eua	3	2	3	P	<i>Sambucus racemosa</i>	.	+	I	0.02	
H	Eua	4	3	0	P	<i>Molinia caerulea</i>	+	I	0.27	
H	Eua	0	0	0	P	<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	I	0.02	
Ch	Eua	2.5	2.5	3	N	<i>Scutellaria supina</i>	.	1	I	0.25	
H	E	3	1	2	P	<i>Festuca nigrescens</i>	+	I	0.05	

Place and date of surveys: 1 Făget, 09.08.2018, GPS 463142.5, 225227.9; 2 Albac-Coșuri Valley, 09.08.2018 GPS 463017.7, 225254.3; 3 Ursoița-Piciocaru, 14.09.2019, GPS 463229.8, 225334.3; 4 Lina 14.09.2018 GPS 463437.2, 225319.8; 5 Beliș Valley, 14.09.2018 GPS 463434, 225213; 6-8 Căpățânei Swamps, 28.07.2019. GPS 462817.5, 230545.9; 462815.8, 230602.3; 432817.7, 230608.6; 9 Cracilor-Dobrușu Valley 11.08.2019 GPS 463603.2, 230149.8; 10 Drăguiaș-Poiana Horea Valley 12.09.2019 GPS 463554.5, 225352.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The association entails a very high scientific importance since it includes four (4) rare, endangered, glacial relict species, included in the Red Lists and a tertiary relic e.g. *Dryopteris cristata*, *Leucanthemum waldstreinii*, *Eriophorum vaginatum*, *Vaccinium microcarpum*, *Blechum spicant*.

2. The phytocenoses of the *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* association are dominated by hemicryptophytes (55%), followed by phanerophytes (17.5%), cameophytes (15%), geophytes (10%), and terophytes (2.5%).

3. The geographical area of the *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* association is dominated by circumpolar species (32.5%), followed by Eurasian (25%), European (15%), cosmopolitan and Central European species with the same share (i.e. 7.5%), Carpatho-Balkan species (5%), while the lowest percentage belong to endemic-Carpathian, Ponto-Pannonian, and Arctic-Alpine species (i.e. 2.5% each).

4. Ecological indices highlight the fact that, in terms of soil moisture, there are dominant the following species: mesophiles (57.5%), followed by mesohygrophiles (25%), eurhydrates (10%), and xeromesophiles (5%). With regard the temperature, the dominant species are microthermic (55%), eurythermic (27.5%), micro-mesothermal (12.5%), and cryophilic species (5%). Regarding the chemical reaction of the soil, the euriionic (27.5%), acidophilic (25%), and acid-neutrophilic (22.5%) are dominant followed by strongly acidophilic (17.5%) and weakly acid-neutrophilic (7.5%) species.

5. In the genetic structure of the phytocenoses of the *Sphagno girgensohnii-Piceetum* association, polyploids (57.5%) are dominant, followed by diploids (32.5%), diplo-polyploids (7.5%) and species with unknown karyotype (2.5 %). The diploid index is 0.56.

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RESEARCH ON 6833 FOREST ECOSYSTEM TYPE *COMMON OAK-TURKEY OAK* MIXED STAND WITH *AGROSTIS-CAREX BRIZOIDES* (REGIONAL VERSION OF A NEW TYPE OF ECOSYSTEM) WITHIN THE SEGMENT OF LANDSCAPE SITUATED ON HIGHT WESTERN PLAIN OF TINCA FOREST DISTRICT

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Abstract

*The identification and description of types of forest ecosystems on smaller geographical units, from the level of landscapes (landschaft), in order to establish the ecological specificity within a certain territorial unit and the establishment of some sustainable management measures, gives the forest typology a strong regional feature (Doniță, 2004). Forest typology evolved from the necessity of differentiating management measures of the forests according to composition, structure, productivity, features of the stands, i.e. after their eco-systemic features (Doniță et al., 1990). In this type of forest ecosystem the nucleus of constant species consists of: *Quercus cerris*, *Q. robur*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Agrostis stolonifera*, *Veronica officinalis*.*

Key words: forest ecosystems, geographical segment landscape, ecological landscape environment, sustainable forestry.

INTRODUCTION

High piedmontal plain situated in the center of the study area, with average altitudes of 100-200 m., with increasing values eastward, is a Pleistocene plain unit, largely folded, resulted from the connection of the alluvial cones of the river flowing from the mountains and hills situated eastward.

The connection between the plain and the hills is marked by a morphological threshold of about 40-60 m.

The proluvial deposits from the plain are consisted of clay and silt deposits. On these materials heavy and alternant hydric soils forms.

The relief is dominantly a plateau, slightly folded and fragmented by some shallow, temporary brooks. The clays (red clays) are the base of stagnic luvisols on the slopes, planic and whitish soils on the plateau, with a well-balanced hydric regime.

The climate is warm, less humid as in the low hill unit (mean average temperatures of 10°C, average rainfall quantities of 614.7 mm).

Within these natural conditions the plateau ecosystem is consisted of turkey oak, pedunculate oak, sessile oak, Hungarian oak, usually the mix of two even three species, with the presence of the common hornbeam along

the small brooks. The soil indicators herbaceous and shrub layer is consisted of *Agrostis-Carex brizoides*, *Genista-Festuca heterophylla* on the plateaus, *Glechoma-Geum* and *Arum-Brachypodium* along the brooks.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The locations of the research are the forests administrated by Tinca Forest District; the study has started in 2020 and continued in 2021.

The establishment of typological units (types of ecosystems) was made using the method of synthetic systemic indicators evaluating phytocoenosis, climate indicator forest plants and edaphic conditions: acidity, humidity, humus content, compactness. The use of phyto indicators is based on the principles of modern ecology according to which the plants, as primary producers and the phytocoenosis which they make up, exactly reflects not only the complex abiotic ecological factors, decisive for forest biocoenosis but also the nature and the functionality of these biocoenosis which finally represents the productivity of the forest ecosystem.

The forest ecosystems were analyzed according to **location** within the study area; **the features of the ecosystem type**: surface area, geographical parameters (average altitude, altitude range); relief forms: types, inclination of the slopes, slope exposition, lithology, soil types and subtypes, ecological limitative factors); the description of the stands, the description of the herbaceous layer; the **correspondence with**: types of forests, types of stations, plant associations, types of habitat, **present state of the stands and management measures (particularities)**: main features, distribution according to age classes, the source of main elements, natural regeneration, productivity classes, management measures, variability and succession tendency (forms of type, successional tendencies and forest facies).

The description of the forest ecosystem was made based on collected field data. In order to analyse the collected data were used different softwares, such as Excel, ArcGis.

After determining the types, they were mapped by researching all the planning units and classifying them into types, taking into account the composition of the trees, the type of grass-subshrub layer, the type of humus. (Moțiu and co., 2011; Moțiu and co., 2012). The delimitation method of the forest ecosystems had as base some typological schemes made for the study area (for ex forest corps) (Moțiu and co., 2011; Moțiu and co., 2012). The landscaping units with non-native species cultures were classified into types based on the type of resort.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TYPE OF ECOSYSTEM: 6833 Medium and poorly productive oak, with moder, on stagnant luvisols and stagnant albic and luvic, oligobasic, quasi-balanced hydric soils and alternating on the surface, cu *Agrostis-Carex brizoides* (the regional variant of a new type of ecosystem)

Subtypes: 68332 highly productive subtype;
68333 poorly productive subtype.

Spreading: this type of ecosystem is widespread on the Piedmont plain and a little on the low hills. It is widespread in U.P.IV - Trup Tinca - Topile.

Characteristics of the type of ecosystem within the researched area:

a. Occupied area: 700.2 ha.

b. Resorts:

- average altitude 181 m (variation difference 131-210 m);
- relief: by shape - plateau, rarely sloping; after inclination - no inclination or moderate slopes; after the exhibition - ground plan;
- rock: red clays;
- types and subtypes of soil: stagnic luvisols, white stagnic, luvic stagnosols;
- ecological limiting factors: vernal excess moisture on the surface and in profile, and moisture deficit in dry summers, reduced trophicity.

c. The composition of the stands: in the dominant floor *Quercus cerris* (in high proportions), accompanied in all cases by *Quercus robur* with coverage of 5% -30% of the surface; disseminated, *Quercus petraea* ssp. *polycarpa* can be found; in the dominant floor sometimes a few specimens of *Carpinus betulus*, *Pyrus pyraster* și *Acer tataricum* may appear.

d. The composition of the shrubs: *Crataegus monogyna*, *Rubus caesius*, *R. sulcatus*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Rosa canina*; rarely maybe found also: *Evonymus europaeus*, *Frangula alnus*, *R. hirtus*.

Acer tataricum and *Pyrus pyraster* may also be present in the sub-tree floor, with a maximum coverage of 5%.

The shrub is generally poorly developed, with a cover of 5% - 10% of the surface.

e. The composition of the herbaceous layer: *Agrostis stolonifera*, *Carex brizoides*, *Lysimachia nummularia*, *Veronica officinalis*, *Festuca heterophylla*, *Polygonum hydropiper*, *Juncus effusus*, *Brachypodium sylvaticum*, *Galium palustre*, *Dactylis glomerata*, *Lychnis flos-cuculi*, *Campanula patula*, *Galeopsis tetrahit*, *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Hypericum perforatum*, *Fragaria vesca*; in some situations

they may still be encountered: *Geranium robertianum*, *Polygonatum latifolium*, *Galium aparine*, *Stellaria holostea*.

The layer of shrubs is well developed, with a coverage of 30% - 70% of the surface, depending on the degree of illumination. *Agrostis stolonifera*, *Carex brizoides* and *Festuca heterophylla* can become abundant, especially in parquet, but also in the case of stronger thinning of the stand

Correspondence with:

- **forest types:** - ;

- **resort types: 6.4.1.1.** – Hilly beech (oak, sky, garnish) Pm, luvisols, including whitish luvisols, epihypostagnic-mesohypostagnic, medium edaphic;

- **plant associations:** - ;

- **habitat type:** - .

The current state of the stands and management measures (particularities):

f. The structure of the trees: is missing - no inventory has been made.

Foto 1: *Common oak-turkey oak mixed stand with Agrostis-Carex brizoides, in u.a. 36, U.P.IV Topile area, (photo - P.T. Moşiu)*

g. Distribution by age range: 6-10 years - 2%; 11-20 years 18%; 21-40 years - 17%; 41-80 years - 53%; over 80 years - 11%.

h. The origin of the main elements of the tree: Turkey oak - natural sowing 33%, sprout 55%, plantation and artificial seeding 12%, common oak - natural sowing 17%, sprout 55%, plantation 28%.

i. Production class of the main tree elements: Turkey oak cl III/IV; Common oak cl IV/III; Sessile oak cl III/IV.

j. Natural regeneration through seeding: turkey oak regenerates well, oak regenerates harder and only in more favorable microstations, on elevations (Doniță and co., 1990); the cause is poor fruiting and soil

understanding by *Agrostis stolonifera*;

k. The indicated target composition: 4Ce 2St 2Go 2Ju,Ar,Pă,Mă.

l. Management measures on age intervals: 0-5 years - decomposition of natural regenerations and/or plantations; 6-10 years - preferential promotion of oak and sessile oak by applying clearings and quercus cerris only where appropriate. It is mandatory to maintain the mixed species (Tartarian maple and wild pear) to create a subfloor; 11-20 years - proportioning the mixture in favor of oak and sessile oak by clearing; 21-40 years - the application of thinning combined with the promotion of sessile oak and valuable cerris quercus specimens; 41-80 years - continuing to promote the oak through combined thinning, keeping the rest of the massif closed; over 80 years - application of hygiene cuts.

m. Other management measures: introduction in the composition of the arboretum of some species of aid - common maple, Tartarian maple and wild pear. Increasing the proportion of oak and sessile oak up to 40-50% in the composition of stands, in more favorable resorts (on slopes). Shrubs from shoots will be converted gradually, as much as possible by natural regeneration (if the tree is at the age of fruiting), or by restoration. In the case of crops with non-native species, ecologically not indicated (acacia), it is recommended to replace them with native species adapted to local seasonal conditions.

Hydrotechnical works, execution of drainage ditches and unclogging of existing ditches, works to improve the conditions of biological drainage are indicated.

n. Variability and successional trends (forms of type, successional tendencies and silvofacies): in the researched territory we describe the geographical variant with oak (sometimes sessile oak). Type of forest ecosystem **7133** presents a form with slightly common oak, up to 10% in the composition of the stand, with *Agrostis stolonifera* and *Festuca heterophylla* dominant within the grass layer (Turkey oak realizes the third class of production and common oak fourth class of production, quality being IV for both species) and a form with more peduncled oak - up to 30% in the composition of the tree, in some cases the oak being even dominant as a proportion of participation (it may appear sessile oak also, disseminated or with a proportion of 10% in the composition of the tree), with mosaic of the grassy-subshrub layer: in the lower places (wetter) with *Agrostis stolonifera* and *Festuca heterophylla* and in higher places (with better edaphic conditions in the upper soil horizon) with *Lamium galeobdolon*, *Geranium robertianum*, *Melica uniflora*, *Mycelis muralis*, *Euphorbia amygdaloides*, *Carex sylvatica*, *uneori Polygonatum latifolium*, *Galium aparine*; productivity and quality is higher than in the previous form, both in the *Quercus cerris* and in the oak (second or third production class for Turkey

oak and third or fourth class for common oak, and third class quality for *Quercus cerris*, and fourth class for oak). This form represents a transition to the type of ecosystem **7833** - Mixed oak stand with *Agrostis-Carex brizoides*.

In conditions of plateau edges, on soils with better drainage, the transition is made to ecosystem **7135** - Turkey oak stand with *Genista-Festuca heterophylla* (terrace shape) or to type **5724** - Turkey oak-Sessil oak with common hornbeam mixed stand with *Glechoma-Geum* (terrace shape); these forms of transition are characterized by mosaicizing the subshrub grassy layer. On the sunny slopes, exposed to stronger insolation and implicitly to stronger drying, the transition is made to type **7135** - Turkey oak stand with *Genista-Festuca heterophylla* (slope shape). **Silvo Facies:** with Hungarian oak (mixture in bouquets or groups with coverage of up to 30-40% in the composition of the stand);

o. Observations: we find in this type of forest ecosystem stands of medium productivity; the cause lies in the average creditworthiness of the resorts (soils with medium edaphic volume and in some places with a more favorable aero-hydric regime). The type of ecosystem has variability on micro resorts: in micro resorts where hydrophilic species dominate in the grassy layer (*Agrostis stolonifera*, *Carex brizoides* and so on), the productivity of the stands is lower, and on micro-elevations, with species from the mull flora, the productivity is higher.

It is the regional version of a new type of ecosystem.

CONCLUSIONS

This priority of this period is to establish types of forests on small geographic units, at the level of landscapes, the typology having thus a strong regional feature.

We tried, within this research, to establish ecosystem-based forest type existing in a territory smaller but representative for the high plain units within Tinca Forest District, to state the current status of types and propose appropriate management measures to bring forest types as close as possible to the natural state.

Regarding the regional particularities of ecosystem type

The existence of oligo loamy and oligo mezo basic soils on plains, on large surfaces, strongly alternating humidity both on the surface and on the soil, which develops edified biocenosis of some species from the *Quercus* genus, with a few mixed species, having in the herbaceous layer many species of swamp (Beldie and Chiriță, 1967; Ciocârlan, 2000).

Under these conditions, the competitiveness of species from *Quercus* genus, being reduced, may form mixtures, in which participate three or more four species from this genus, present in the region: *Quercus robur*, *Quercus petraea*, *Quercus cerris*, *Quercus frainetto*, thus making the transition to the type of 7833 Mixed oak stand with *Agrostis stolonifera*-*Carex brizoides* forest ecosystem.

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CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE EVALUATION OF THE PRODUCTIVITY OF PERMANENT GRASSLANDS FROM THE MEZIAD HILLS (BIHOR COUNTY)

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Abstract

This paper presents a case study on the evaluation of the productivity of permanent grasslands based on the floristic survey. The permanent grasslands on the Meziad Hills consist mainly of 2 associations, Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris Horvat 1951 and Trifolio repenti-Lolietum Krippelová 1967, Resmeriță et Pop 1967. In these 2 associations, a number of 10 phytocoenological relevées were carried out, 5 relevées for each association, in which the assessment of abundance-dominance was made according to the Braun-Blanquet scale.

Following the calculations performed, it was determined for the phytocoenoses of the Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris association a pastoral value (VP) of 60.53, with a green mass production (MV) of 11.18 (t/ha) and an animal load of 0.93 livestock units UVM / ha. For the Trifolio repenti-Lolietum association, a pastoral value (VP) of 55.31 was determined, with a production of green mass production (MV) of 10.66 (t/ha) and an animal load of 0.88 livestock units UVM/ha.

Key words: pastoral value, permanent grasslands, carrying capacity, green mass production

INTRODUCTION

Vegetation studies on permanent grasslands in the country do not refer to their productivity or carrying capacity. Data on grassland productivity are useful in establishing measures to improve their quality and assessing the optimal carrying capacity, which are necessary in the rational management of the pastoral fund.

The elaboration of a method for evaluating the productivity of the grasslands based on the floristic relevées is useful in establishing some economic data of production useful in the realization of the pastoral arrangements. This method is more accurate compared to the old method based on direct determination by mowing on sample surfaces.

Some studies on the assessment of grassland productivity based on floristic relevées have been carried out by Marușca et al. 2019, Marușca et al. 2020, Marușca, 2016, Pășcuț and Marușca, 2020.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The Braun-Blanquet scale was used to assess the abundance-dominance of plant species in the studied grasslands. The notes of appreciation of the abundance-dominance in percentages according to

constancy (K) were made according to the model implemented by Marușca (2019). The botanical nomenclature used for the identified species is in accordance with the works elaborated by Ciocârlan (2009) and Sârbu et al. (2013).

The species in the floristic relevée, after being transformed into participation percentages, are divided into three fodder groups: *Poaceae*, *Fabaceae* and other families. The feed quality indicators are also mentioned in the table (F4-F9), as well as the harmful indicators (F1-F3), together with the indicators of useful (M1-M9) and harmful (M0 for F1-F3) forage phytomass.

The fodder value indices (F) after Păcurar and Rotar (2014), Kovacs (1979) and Marușca (2019) are the following: F1 = toxic to animals and humans; F2 = harmful to animal products; F3 = harmful to the vegetal layer; F4 = weak fodder (ballast species); F5 = mediocre fodder; F6 = medium forage; F7 = good fodder; F8 = very good fodder; F9 = excellent fodder; X = species of unknown feed value.

The percentage share of grassland species with the indication of fodder quality indices (F) and useful phytomass index (M) gives the possibility to calculate the pastoral value (VP) according to the following formula:

$$VP = \Sigma P(\%) \times F/9$$

where: VP - pastoral value indicator (with values of 0-100), for F-with values between 4-9;

P(%) - percentage share of each species, depending on the values of F.

Depending on the values of the indicator on the pastoral value, the grasslands can be classified as follows: 0-5 degraded grassland; 5-15 very weak; 15-25 weak; 25-40 mediocre; 40-60 medium; 60-80 good; 80-100 very good.

The evaluation of the useful fodder production is performed by an indirect method based on the floristic relevées and production indices (M) of the fodder species from the grassy carpet of the grasslands (Marușca, 2019). The determination of the average green mass production index (IM) for permanent grassland phytocoenoses shall be calculated using the following formula:

$$IM = \Sigma P(\%) \times M/100$$

where: IM - the average green mass production index; for F-with values between 4-9;

P(%) - the share of participation in percentage of each species, depending on the values of M (values between 1-9).

The value of the average green fodder index (IM) within the range in Table 1 is multiplied by the green mass production coefficient (CMV),

resulting in the production in tonnes per hectare (MV) and finally the appreciation of this indicator.

Table 1

Production indices for feed species and estimating the useful yield per hectare of permanent unfertilized grasslands (after) Marușca, 2019)

Average production indices green mass forage species (IM)	Coefficients of transformation in green mass production (CMV)	Green mass production estimate (MV) (t/ha)	Appreciation of production value
0.1 – 0.5	x 1.8	0.18 – 0.90	Very weak
0.6 – 1.0	x 1.9	1.14 – 1.90	
1.1 – 1.5	x 2.0	2.20 – 3.00	Weak
1.6 – 2.0	x 2.1	3.36 – 4.20	
2.1 – 2.5	x 2.2	4.62 – 5.50	Weak-Medium
2.6 – 3.0	x 2.3	5.98 – 6.90	
3.1 – 3.5	x 2.4	7.44 – 8.40	Medium
3.6 – 4.0	x 2.5	9.00 – 10.00	
4.1 – 4.5	x 2.6	10.66 – 11.70	Middle-Good
4.6 – 5.0	x 2.7	12.42 – 13.50	
5.1 – 5.5	x 2.8	14.28 – 15.40	Good
5.6 – 6.0	x 2.9	16.24 – 17.40	
6.1 – 6.5	x 3.0	18.30 – 19.50	Good-Very good
6.6 – 7.0	x 3.1	20.46 – 21.70	
7.1 – 7.5	x 3.2	22.72 – 24.00	Very good
7.6 – 8.0	x 3.3	25.08 – 26.40	
8.1 – 8.5	x 3.4	27.54 – 28.90	Excellent
8.6 – 9.0	x 3.5	30.10 – 31.50	

The following formula is used to determine the carrying capacity (CP) expressed in livestock units (UVM) per hectare (Table 2).

$$CP(UVM/ha) = \frac{MV(t/ha)}{Nz \times Zp}$$

where: MV - represents green mass production (t/ha)

Nz - the daily requirement of grass for 1 livestock unit (UVM), 65kg (50kg+30%(15kg) seasonal climate fluctuations and unconsumed debris)

Zp - number of grazing days (season)

Table 2

Appreciation of carrying capacity of grasslands is done this way:

Units of livestock UVM/ha value	Grassland appreciation
0.01 - 0.20	Degraded (Degr.)
0.21 - 0.40	Very weak (FS)
0.41 - 0.60	Weak (S)
0.61 - 0.80	Mediocre (Med.)
0.81 - 1.20	Middle (Mijl.)
1.21 - 1.60	Good (B)
1.61 - 2.00	Very good (FB)
Over 2.00	Excellent (Ext.)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study of permanent grasslands of the Meziad Hills highlights the existence of two plant associations *Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris* Horvat 1951 and *Trifolio repenti-Lolietum* Krippelová 1967, Resmeriță et Pop 1967. The study was conducted in August 2020 resulting in a number of 10 phytocoenes relevées, 5 relevées for each association.

From a cenotic point of view, the two associations are framed in *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* R. Tüxen 1937 class, *Arrhenatheretalia* R. Tüxen 1931 order, *Cynosurion* R. Tüxen 1947 alliance.

The *Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris* association is found at altitudes of 235-300 m, on generally shaded exposures (N, NW) with a slope of 5-12° (Table 3). The floristic composition is rich and varied, totaling 96 species.

The grasslands belonging to this association have a pastoral value (VP) of 60.53, a fodder green mass production (MV) estimated at 11.18 (t/ha), which supports an animal load of 0.93 livestock units UVM/ha, calculated for an average grazing season of 185 days.

Table 3

The floristic composition of the *Festuco rubrae-Agrostetum capillaris* Horvat 1951 association from the Meziad Hills (Bihor County)

No. relevées	1	2	3	4	5	K	Participation P (%)	Indices		
Altitude (m.s.m.)	300	240	260	240	235					
The coverage of vegetation layer (%)	100	100	100	100	100					
Exposition	N	NV	S	NV, V	NV					
Slope (°)	18	5	12	10	10					
Area	100	100	100	100	100					
GPS	Lat. N	46.72686	46.71821	46.71074	46.70857	46.71959				
coordinates	Long. E	22.42470	22.36428	22.38382	22.35676	22.31812		F	M	
	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Poaceae										
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	3	2	3	4	4	V	40	7	6	
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	2	3	2	1	1	V	21,3	7	5	
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	7	4	
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	6	6	
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	5	3	
<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	4	3	
<i>Calamagrostis epigeios</i>	+	+	1	+	+	V	2,8	3	0	
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	+	+	.	+	+	IV	0,4	9	8	
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	+	1	.	+	+	IV	2	9	8	
<i>Festuca arundinacea</i>	+	+	.	+	+	IV	0,4	8	9	
<i>Festuca valesiaca</i>	+	+	+	+	.	IV	0,4	5	3	
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	+	+	+	+	.	IV	0,4	3	0	
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	.	+	.	+	+	III	0,3	8	6	
<i>Molinia caerulea</i>	+	+	.	+	.	III	0,3	3	0	

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	+	+	·	·	·	II	0,2	9	8
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	·	+	·	·	+	II	0,2	9	8
<i>Arrhenatherum elatius</i>	·	·	·	+	+	II	0,2	8	8
<i>Festuca rupicola</i>	+	·	+	·	·	II	0,2	5	5
Fabaceae									
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	8	6
<i>Trifolium hybridum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	8	6
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	1	1	+	1	+	V	2,8	8	5
<i>Trifolium pretense</i>	+	+	+	·	+	IV	0,4	8	7
<i>Trifolium medium</i>	·	+	+	+	·	III	0,3	6	4
<i>Dorycnium pentaphyllum</i>	+	·	·	+	+	III	0,3	3	0
<i>Medicago lupulina</i>	·	·	+	·	+	II	0,2	8	3
<i>Trifolium campestre</i>	·	+	·	·	+	II	0,2	7	2
<i>Coronilla varia</i>	·	+	·	·	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Ononis spinosa</i>	+	·	·	·	+	II	0,2	3	0
Other families									
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	6	4
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	6	1
<i>Leontodon hispidus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	5	3
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	5	2
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	4	1
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	4	2
<i>Prunella laciniata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	4	2
<i>Thymus glabrescens</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	4	2
<i>Erigeron annuus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	3	0
<i>Juncus effusus</i>	+	1	1	+	+	V	2,8	3	0
<i>Polygala vulgaris</i>	+	+	+	·	+	IV	0,4	4	1
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i>	+	+	+	+	·	IV	0,4	3	0
<i>Carex hirta</i>	+	+	+	+	·	IV	0,4	3	0
<i>Filago germanica</i>	+	+	·	+	+	IV	0,4	3	0
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	2	1	2	1	·	IV	7,9	3	0
<i>Viola tricolor</i>	+	+	+	+	·	IV	0,4	3	0
<i>Carlina vulgaris</i>	+	+	+	·	+	IV	0,4	2	0
<i>Galium verum</i>	·	+	+	·	+	III	0,3	5	4
<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	+	·	+	·	+	III	0,3	4	6
<i>Rumex acetosa</i>	+	+	·	·	+	III	0,3	4	5
<i>Cerastium holosteoides</i>	+	·	·	+	+	III	0,3	3	0
<i>Epilobium roseum</i>	+	+	·	·	+	III	0,3	3	0
<i>Eryngium campestre</i>	+	·	·	+	+	III	0,3	3	0
<i>Euphrasia stricta</i>	+	+	+	·	·	III	0,3	3	0
<i>Juncus tenuis</i>	·	+	·	+	+	III	0,3	3	0
<i>Lysimachia nummularia</i>	·	+	+	+	·	III	0,3	3	0
<i>Hypericum perforatum</i>	+	·	·	+	+	III	0,3	2	0
<i>Ranunculus polyanthemus</i>	+	+	·	·	+	III	0,3	1	0
<i>Bellis perennis</i>	·	·	·	+	+	II	0,2	5	1
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	+	·	·	·	+	II	0,2	5	6
<i>Fragaria vesca</i>	·	+	·	·	+	II	0,2	5	1
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i>	+	+	·	·	·	II	0,2	5	5
<i>Lythrum salicaria</i>	+	·	·	·	+	II	0,2	4	7
<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	·	·	·	+	+	II	0,2	4	6
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	·	+	+	·	·	II	0,2	4	4

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Campanula patula</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Centaurium erythraea</i>	+	.	.	+	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Cruciata glabra</i>	+	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Dianthus carthusianorum</i>	+	.	.	.	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Filipendula hexapetala</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Galium mollugo</i>	.	+	.	.	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Juncus inflexus</i>	.	.	.	+	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Lycopus europaeus</i>	+	.	.	.	+	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Matricaria perforata</i>	.	+	.	+	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Potentilla reptans</i>	+	.	.	.	+	II	0,2	3	0

Other species (K I; P 0.1%; F 1.2.3.):
Gnaphalium sylvaticum, Knautia arvensis, Convolvulus arvensis, Juncus conglomeratus, Potentilla argentea, Anthemis arvensis, Scrophularia umbrosa, Polygonum hydropiper, Rumex conglomeratus, Euphorbia cyparissias, Dipsacus laciniatus, Urtica dioica, Lysimachia vulgaris, Stellaria graminea, Ranunculus repens, Clinopodium vulgare, Rubus sulcatus, Rosa canina, Prunus spinosa, Crataegus monogyna, Juniperus communis.

where: F - fodder quality indices; M - production indices; K - constancy;

The phytocenoses belonging to the *Trifolio repenti-Lolietum* association colonize the flat lands (slope 5-8°), with V, NV exposures, at altitudes of 200-275 m. (Table 4). The floristic composition totals a number of 70 species. The pastoral value (VP) of these meadows is 55.31, with a green mass production (MV) of 10.66 (t/ha) and an animal load of 0.88 livestock units UVM/ha, calculated for a duration of the grazing season in an average of 185 days.

Table 4

The floristic composition of the *Trifolio repenti-Lolietum* Krippelová 1967, Resmerița et Pop 1967 association from the Meziad Hills (Bihor County)

No. relevées	1	2	3	4	5	K	Participation P (%)	Indices	
Altitude (m.s.m.)	275	210	200	230	225				
The coverage of vegetation layer (%)	100	100	100	100	100				
Exposition	NV	-	V	-	-				
Slope (°)	8	-	5	-	-				
Area	100	100	100	100	100				
GPS	Lat. N	46.73142	46.73442	46.73887	46.73853	46.73211			
coordonates	Long. E	22.43307	22.37059	22.30894	22.32494	22.32460			
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Poaceae									
<i>Lolium perenne</i>	3	3	3	3	2	V	27,5	9	8
<i>Festuca pratensis</i>	1	1	1	+	1	V	2,8	9	8
<i>Agrostis capillaris</i>	1	1	1	1	1	V	5	7	5
<i>Festuca rubra</i>	+	1	1	+	1	V	2,8	7	6
<i>Agropyron repens</i>	+	+	.	1	+	IV	2	6	7

0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
<i>Holcus lanatus</i>	1	.	+	1	1	IV	2	6	6
<i>Anthoxanthum odoratum</i>	+	.	+	+	1	IV	2	5	3
<i>Phleum pratense</i>	+	+	.	+	.	III	0,3	9	8
<i>Festuca arundinacea</i>	+	+	.	.	+	III	0,3	8	9
<i>Cynosurus cristatus</i>	+	.	+	.	+	III	0,3	7	4
<i>Danthonia decumbens</i>	+	.	+	.	+	III	0,3	4	3
<i>Nardus stricta</i>	+	+	.	.	+	III	0,3	3	0
<i>Dactylis glomerata</i>	+	.	.	+	.	II	0,2	9	8
<i>Poa pratensis</i>	.	.	1	1	.	II	1,5	8	6
<i>Calamagrostis epigeios</i>	.	.	+	+	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Molinia caerulea</i>	.	.	+	.	+	II	0,2	3	0
Fabaceae									
<i>Lotus corniculatus</i>	1	+	1	1	+	V	2,8	8	6
<i>Trifolium hybridum</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	8	6
<i>Trifolium repens</i>	1	1	1	1	1	V	5	8	5
<i>Trifolium pratense</i>	+	.	1	1	+	IV	2	8	7
<i>Medicago lupulina</i>	.	.	+	+	.	II	0,2	8	3
<i>Trifolium medium</i>	+	.	.	+	.	II	0,2	6	4
Other families									
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	6	4
<i>Plantago lanceolata</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	6	1
<i>Leontodon hispidus</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	5	3
<i>Polygala vulgaris</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	4	1
<i>Prunella vulgaris</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	4	2
<i>Cerastium holosteoides</i>	+	+	+	+	+	V	0,5	3	0
<i>Juncus effusus</i>	1	2	+	1	2	V	9	3	0
<i>Potentilla erecta</i>	+	+	.	+	+	IV	0,4	5	2
<i>Rumex acetosa</i>	+	+	.	+	+	IV	0,4	4	5
<i>Thymus glabrescens</i>	+	+	+	+	.	IV	0,4	4	2
<i>Agrimonia eupatoria</i>	.	+	+	+	+	IV	0,4	3	0
<i>Carduus acanthoides</i>	+	+	+	.	+	IV	0,4	3	0
<i>Eryngium campestre</i>	.	1	1	+	1	IV	2	3	0
<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	2	+	.	+	1	IV	6,3	3	0
<i>Euphorbia cyparissias</i>	.	1	1	1	1	IV	3,5	1	0
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	+	+	.	+	.	III	0,3	5	6
<i>Centaurea phrygia</i>	+	.	.	+	+	III	0,3	4	6
<i>Hieracium pilosella</i>	+	.	+	.	1	III	1,4	4	1
<i>Leucanthemum vulgare</i>	.	.	+	+	.	II	0,2	5	5
<i>Prunella laciniata</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II	0,2	4	2
<i>Veronica officinalis</i>	+	+	.	.	.	II	0,2	4	4
<i>Campanula patula</i>	+	.	.	+	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Centaurium erythraea</i>	+	.	.	+	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Galium mollugo</i>	.	.	+	+	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Matricaria perforata</i>	+	.	+	.	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Potentilla reptans</i>	+	.	+	.	.	II	0,2	3	0
<i>Potentilla anserina</i>	+	.	+	.	.	II	0,2	3	0
Other species 1937 (K I; P 0.1%; F 1.2.3.): <i>Polygonum hydropiper, Ambrosia artemisiifolia, Rumex conglomeratus, Xanthium strumarium, Verbena officinalis, Dipsacus laciniatus, Urtica dioica, Filago germanica, Erigeron annuus, Mentha pulegium, Lythrum salicaria, Hypericum perforatum, Lycopodium europaeus, Juncus tenuis, Juncus inflexus, Carex hirta, Rubus sulcatus, Rosa canina, Frangula alnus, Prunus spinosa, Crataegus monogyna.</i>									

where: F - fodder quality indices; M - production indices; K - constancy;

CONCLUSIONS

The permanent mesophilic grasslands of the Meziad Hills have a great floristic diversity, colonizing the slightly to moderately sloping slopes, with generally shady exposures and acidic brown and humic brown soils, that are rich in humus with different degrees of saturation in bases, district-soil type.

The pastoral value of these grasslands is medium-good, with a production of green mass between 10.66 and 11.18, which allows an optimal load of animals of 0.88-0.93 livestock units UVM/ha in 185 days of grazing.

These studies on the productivity and grazing capacity of permanent grasslands can be compared with those of the past in order to establish their dynamically economic evolution.

Determining the productivity of grasslands through this new method of evaluation based on floristic relevées serves to prepare pastoral arrangements and the evolution over time of this indicator.

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PHILATELIC CONCERNS FOR SOIL PROTECTION: 2015, INTERNATIONAL YEAR OF SOILS

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Abstract

The concerns about soil protection have existed for a long time, but until 2015 they did not materialize visibly internationally. In 2015, the United Nations decided that it must take a stand in this regard, so 2015 was designated the International Year of Soils. This initiative has grown, so that even some of the postal administrations have decided to participate actively, issuing a series of philatelic effects following United Nations policy. The present study proposes an analysis of the respective parts, in an attempt to illustrate another perspective on soil protection. The indexing, processing, analysis, description, and dissemination of philatelic material were done through the prism of the postal administration sites, and through the sites with dedicated philatelic content (such as Colnect[®], Delcampe[®], PicClick[®], StampWorld[®], etc.). The results obtained as a philographic summum show that there were special concerns aimed at promoting soil protection and the International Year of Soils. Moreover, these concerns have materialized both as stamps and FDCs, and as circulations, with thematic philately supporting the humanitarian cause of soil protection, in particular, and sustainable agriculture in general.

Key words: soil protection timeline, International Year of Soils, philately, sustainable agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

The 68th General Assembly of the United Nations, by the resolution adopted on December 20, 2013, announced and proclaimed the year 2015 to be the International Year of Light and Light-based Technologies, as well as the International Year of Soils - IYS 2015 (UN, 2013).

As a sequel to the Decade on Biodiversity (2011-2020) and the Post-2015 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the last thematic concern has been initiated to alert humans to the direct relationship between soil fertility, food security, essential ecosystem functions and prosperous societies (UN, 2015; FAO, 2015).

In this sense, the many initiatives organised within the scope of these celebrations aim to help raise society's awareness to the need for sustainable land management, as a key factor for producing food and obtaining fuels, natural fibres and clean water, as well as ensuring essential ecosystem functions and helping present and future generations to adapt to climate change. In this context, the Food and Agriculture Organization has been

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nominated to implement the IYS 2015, within the framework of the Global Soil Partnership and in collaboration with Governments (FAO, 2015).

In addition, some of the postal administrations also contributed to the promotion of the event, which began to gain momentum internationally. Adopting the policy of international entities (such as UNEP, FAO, etc.), they decided to actively participate in promoting the International Year of Soils, achieving and issuing a series of philatelic effects.

In this sense, the present study proposes an analysis of the respective pieces, in an attempt to illustrate another perspective on soil protection, namely that of thematic philately. Thus, from the indexing of the pieces to the analysis, description, and dissemination of philatelic material, we have constantly tried to emphasize the concerns for soil protection.

These concerns have known the most diverse forms of representation, which have either gone along the path of presenting the soil as a living organism (able in turn to support life forms) or have tried to achieve other functions of the soil. In this sense, the soil is seen both as a resource-support of the community, in parallel with the importance of light (in some cases the date of issuance of parts for the International Year of Soils overlaps with the issue of parts specific to the International Year of Light), but also as a fragile organism that deserves, more than ever, all our care and attention.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The identification, indexing, analysis, and description of the particularities of the exhibited philatelic pieces were made through the information provided by the postal administration sites, and through the sites with dedicated philatelic content (Colnect[®], Delcampe[®], PicClick[®], StampWorld[®], etc.). An important step in the description of the philatelic material was made by *in situ* analysis (if we can call it that) of the philatelic pieces, ie directly at their source of issuance (postal administrations around the world). In this way, official information was obtained, which certifies the real implications of the postal administrations in Moldova, Slovenia, Spain, Kyrgyzstan, Iceland, Portugal, Tunisia, Uruguay, Russia, etc.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first philatelic issue dedicated to the International Year of Soils appeared in Moldova, on February 21, 2015, being indexed MP #0922, Mi MD#895 and Sg MD#877 (Moldova P.O., 2015a, b). The commemorative issue is based on a single multicolored postage stamp made by offset lithography, with a face value of 1.75 L (Moldovan lei), in 34 x 34 mm format, issued in 200,000 copies.

In Fig. 1 are exposed a series of philatelic materials related to the issue; we find the postage stamp described above (Fig. 1a), an unencrypted sheet of 8 postage stamps (Fig. 1b) and the First Day Cover - FDC (Fig. 1c).

Fig. 1. Various philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", 21.02.2015, Moldova

The presented pieces were made after a model by Vitaliu Pogolşa, and printed by Nova Imprim, Chişinău. Of the circulated parts that we managed to identify and analyze (see Fig. 2), we expose only two, which are in fact locally circulated FDCs (Moldova P.O., 2015c, d).

Fig. 2. Circulated philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", 21.02.2015, Moldova

With the opening of a soil profile in the background, the multicolored stamp illustrating two hands holding a seedling plant (see Fig. 3a), issued by the Slovenian postal administration on May 29, 2015, harmoniously complements the commemorative souvenir package and the FDC (Fig. 3b).

Indexed by Mi SL#BL81, Yt SL#BF80, and Sg SL#MS1196, the package includes the postage stamp in 60 x 70 mm format, laced 13¼ (Slovenia P.O., 2015a, b). The stamp with a face value of 0.46 Euro was printed using the offset lithography technique in a small print run (50,000 pieces), after a model bearing the Villa Creativa imprint. As can be seen, the entire package is part of the FDC franking (Slovenia P.O., 2015c).

(a) postage stamp (b) official FDC, an uncirculated version
 Fig. 3. Various philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", May 29, 2015, Slovenia

To commemorate and promote the "International Year of Soils", the Spanish postal administration issued a special stamp illustrating petunia seeds that can be planted, along with the slogan "Renew the soil - Plant me". The image on the postage stamp shows the contrast of the fertile soil with the food produced from it, and a forest, along with the cracked and barren soil resulting from the deterioration of the ecosystem (Spain P.O., 2015a, b).

To show that healthy soils play a major role in preventing droughts, the mosaic postage stamp (see Fig. 4a) published on June 26, 2015, in 35 x 24.5 mm format, laced 13¼ x 13, extends both as a four-piece block (see Fig. 4b), as well as FDC (see Fig. 4c) (Spain PO, 2015c).

Indexed by Mi ES#4986, Yt ES#4691, Sg ES#4967, Edi ES#4976, and WAD ES#056.15 (Spain PO, 2015a), the stamp with a face value of 0.90 Euro, was printed by offset lithography in 250,000 copies.

Fig. 4. Various philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", 26.06.2015, Spain

On September 2, 2015, Kyrgyz Express Post issues a series of multicolored stamps dedicated to UN promotion events. Therefore, the series includes two miniature postcards - as a setter (see Fig. 5a), one for the International Year of Light and one for the International Year of Soils.

The latter is a flowering cotton plant. In the background of the postage stamp - reproduced both as a mini-sheet (Fig. 5b, c) and as a franking of the FDC (Fig. 5d), is represented a typical mountain landscape of Kyrgyzstan, while in the upper left corner of the postage stamp the official logo of the International Year of Soils (Kyrgyzstan PO, 2015a-c) is presented.

Fig. 5. Various philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", 02.09.2015, Kyrgyzstan

The postage stamp bears the signature of the artists Oleg and Aliona Cojocari, while the printing on gummed paper (105 g/m^2) of the reduced circulation (10,000 copies) is the work of the Nova Imprim institution (Kyrgyzstan P.O., 2015d).

Published on September 10, 2015, the commemorative philatelic issue in Iceland is presented in the form of a multicolored package that includes both postage stamps issued (Fig. 6a). They are in $28 \times 33 \text{ mm}$ format, $13\frac{3}{4}$ lace, being printed in a small circulation (30,000 copies) by the offset lithography technique, according to the models made by the designer Örn Smári Gíslason (Iceland P.O., 2015a, b).

The nominal values of the pieces are identical - 500 Gr. (Gram), these being indexed by Mi IS#1474, Sn IS#1386a and AFA IS#1448 (Iceland P.O. 2015a). As for the FDC of the issue, it is crossed with the entire souvenir package (see Fig. 6b) and has in the semi-illustration a leaf arrangement that roughly outlines the profile of the country's borders (Iceland P.O. 2015c).

(a) postage stamp (b) official FDC, an uncirculated version
 Fig. 6. Various philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", 10.09.2015, Iceland

As in the case of the pieces issued by the postal administration of Moldova and in the package above we find the official logo dedicated to the International Year of Soils, which is positioned in the lower-left corner.

Two other interesting philatelic pieces in terms of design, which complement each other harmoniously in the form of an hourglass (as shown in Fig. 7a,b), saw the light of day in Portugal, starting October 14, 2015.

Indexed by Mi PT#4094, Sn PT#3758a, Yt PT#4073, Un PT#4073, AFA PT#4118, and Afi PT#4637, the two multicolored postage stamps in 32 x 40 mm format, lacy 13, were printed by offset lithography after a model made by Pedro Ferreira (Portugal PO, 2015a,b). They also have a single face value - 0.45 Euro.

The FDC of the issue (as presented in Fig. 7c), identified only as a circulating piece, is also completed with the other two postage stamps targeting the International Year of Light, which have a similar face value (Portugal P.O., 2015c).

Fig. 7. Various philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", 14.10.2015, Portugal

A piece highlighting the soil profile, along with a hand holding a plant tightly (see Fig. 8a), was issued by the Tunisian postal administration on October 16, 2015.

The multicolored postage stamp with a face value of 250 LSd (Tunisian millims), indexed by Mi TN#1864, Yv TN#1770, and Sg TN#1841, is presented in 37 x 52 mm format, laced 13 (see Fig. 8a and 8b). It was printed by offset lithography, after a model made by Souhir Charfi, in a generous circulation - 500,000 pieces (Tunisia P.O., 2015a, b).

(a) postage stamp (b) FDC cancelled with the postage stamp
Fig. 8. Various philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", 16.10.2015, Tunisia

Another surprising piece by the illustration he proposes is the one indexed by Mi UY#3460, Sn UY#2534, and Yt UY#2767 (see Fig. 9a), issued on December 3, 2015, by the postal administration of Uruguay. The multicolored postage stamp, which is in 42 x 30 mm format, with 12 comb lace, was printed by offset lithography by Sanfer Srl after a model made by Daniel Pereyra. The nominal value of the limited edition (15,000 pieces) is 60 Uruguayan pesos (Uruguay P.O., 2015a, b).

The peculiarity and beauty of this piece also affect the FDC (Fig. 9b), which is obliterated with the special stamp illustrating a cuboid soil profile (Uruguay P.O., 2015c).

(a) postage stamp (b) FDC cancelled with the postage stamp
 Fig. 9. Various philatelic pieces - "International Year of Soils", 03.12.2015, Uruguay

An interesting piece to study is the one shown in Fig. 10, illustrating an entire cover (envelope) with a fixed mark, zone A, code 106/29.07.2015 (Russia P.O., 2015). Along with the official logo of the International Year of Soils, there is also a cultivated field, as a sign of appreciation of the fruits that the soil offers, seen as a living organism from the perspective of the pedological school.

Fig. 10. Another philatelic piece - "International Year of Soils", July 29, 2015, Russia

This last material concludes the series of philatelic pieces with reference to the International Year of Soils, which we have managed to review so far. This is also the end of our approach, which has managed to capture the concerns of soil protection in the postal administrations of Moldova, Slovenia, Spain, Kyrgyzstan, Iceland, Portugal, Tunisia, Uruguay and Russia.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study started from a series of questions, which arise from each other, of which we mention a part - Were there philatelic concerns regarding the International Year of Soils?, In which postal administrations were these concerns visible?, What philatelic materials were made in this regard? and so on.

As the official websites of postal administrations around the world were consulted, about the various philatelic materials identified in piles (mixed), sometimes chaotically indexed, on Colnect®, Delcampe®, PicClick®, StampWorld® platforms, etc., the study gained outline.

As such, the results obtained in the form of a philographic summum show that there were special concerns aimed at promoting soil protection and implicitly the International Year of Soils. These concerns have materialized both as stamps and FDCs, and in terms of circulation, with thematic philately supporting the noble cause of soil protection, in particular, and sustainable agriculture in general.

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CREATION OF 3D MODELS WITH VIRTUAL REALITY MODELING LANGUAGE

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Abstract

Static and dynamic descriptions of 3D models, multimedia content and a variety of hyperlinks can be represented with VRML files. The information scenes in the VRML file are organized in a scene graph. It contains nodes that describe objects and their properties, organized as a tree family. Interpretation, execution and presentation of VRML files are performed by the browser, which displays shapes and sounds from the scene graph. The 3D model is constructed using multiple Shape nodes with fields to describe the geometry and appearance of the shape.

Key words: 3D models, virtual reality, VRML, programming language

INTRODUCTION

A professional computer graphics community has expanded the concepts of 3D models to include their interactivity. Static and dynamic descriptions of 3D models, multimedia content and a variety of hyperlinks can be represented with VRML files, with the extension *.wrl, where wrl is the abbreviation for world. VRML initials stand for Virtual Reality Modeling Language. As a text language, VRML allows the rapid construction of the virtual world containing 3D shapes, light sources, fog, animation and even sound effects.

A VRML browser is required for the virtual world described by VRML files to appear. A VRML browser reads files, interprets their syntax, builds a 3D virtual world, and then draws it in a graphical window. Both VRML browsers and competent file creation tools are widely available.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

VRML file structure

A VRML file consists of the following components: header, scene graph, prototypes, and event routing.

The information scenes in the VRML file are organized in a scene graph. It contains nodes that describe objects and their properties, organized as a tree family. Parent scene graphs lead groups of children, which may

include other parents. When groups contain groups and they in turn contain groups, the scene graph grows into a hierarchically grouped tree. Children can be members of more than one group, creating a complex of hierarchical scenes called graphs.

Each of the children and parents in the scene graph are VRML nodes, which create the virtual world. VRML nodes position user observation points, set the background, build 3D shapes, group shapes together, define animation paths, track light sources, add ambient fog, position sounds, and so on.

The coordinate system in which the root nodes are displayed is called the virtual world coordinate system (the default coordinate system). VRML includes the notion of local coordinate systems, defined relative to ancestral coordinate systems, using Transform nodes.

Interpretation, execution and presentation of VRML files are performed by the browser, which displays shapes and sounds from the scene graph. This presentation is the virtual world, which can be navigated through the browser by the user.

Construction of forms

In VRML a shape is constructed using the Shape node with fields to describe the geometry and appearance of the shape. Geometry defines the structure of the shape, and the appearance determines the color and transparency of the shape.

Defining the geometry of the shape

A virtual world is constructed using a lot of Shape nodes, which have the geometry field completed with a geometric node to define the surfaces to be drawn. For this purpose, the following predefined geometric nodes are used, associated with some fundamental geometric shapes: Box, Cylinder, Cone, Sphere.

Defining the appearance of shapes

To determine how the shape appears, the appearance field of the Shape node is completed with an Appearance node. This node has a material field that is completed with a Material node to describe the color and transparency of the shape. Material node fields define the color of the shape, including the diffusion, emissivity, brightness, and transparency of the shape.

The shape can be covered with a texture, completing the texture field of the Appearance node with one of three types of texture nodes: ImageTexture, MovieTexture, or PixelTexture. An ImageTexture node is used to load a textured image from a JPEG, PNG, or GIF file. The

MovieTexture node is used to scroll an MPEG movie file over the 3D form. You can include a small texture directly from the VRML file using a PixelTexture node. In each case, a texture determines the color of the shape, ignoring the diffuseColor field in the Material node of the shape.

Transforming groups of shapes

The shapes corresponding to the root nodes in the scene graph are implicitly constructed in the coordinate system of the virtual world. The Transform node creates a new coordinate system that can be translated, rotated, and / or scaled relative to its parent in the scene graph. The shapes defined in the children field of the Transform node are built in the new coordinate system, allowing the establishment of the position, orientation and resizing of these objects.

Setting the background

The background of the VRML world is by default black. With the help of the Background node you can define particular backgrounds. This node has fields that allow the creation of the color gradient along an infinite radius spherical sky and along an infinite radius hemispherical ground located inside the sky sphere, at the bottom to the equator, which surrounds the virtual world. The skyColor and groundColor fields define the concentric circles of color located on the sky sphere and the ground hemisphere, respectively, at the angles to the vertical defined in the skyAngle and groundAngle fields. Between the portions between these angles there is a linear interpolation of the colors on the color circles that delimit them.

3D model created with VRML

According to the notions described about the Virtual Reality Modeling Language, we built a 3D model, which represents the airplane shown in figure 1, using this programming language. For this purpose, Cylinder-type nodes are mainly used to obtain a better definition of the shapes of the component elements of which it is composed.

Figure 1. Airplane

The tube body is made of a cylinder without bases, turned horizontally, as in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. The body of the airplane

The cockpit, front, and rear of the airplane are made of ellipsoids placed in front and rear, respectively, so as to cover the ends of the tube. The ellipsoids from which the cockpit is made and the rear of the airplane are inclined, and the one from which the front is obtained is smaller, not inclined and protrudes slightly outwards, as seen in figure 3.

Fig. 3. The rear, cockpit and front

The tail and wings of the airplane, shown in Figure 4, are obtained from cylinders strongly compressed in the direction perpendicular to their plane, inclined by corresponding rotations and overturned horizontally in the case of the wings. The exhaust pipe is made of a cylinder overturned horizontally and placed behind the body of the airplane.

Fig. 4. The tail and wings

The engine is constructed of a cone and a cylinder turned horizontally and placed in the rear or front, respectively, according to figure 5. It is fixed under the wing by a support obtained from a sphere flattened by compression and inclined by rotation.

Fig. 5. The engine

The elliptical windows, shown in Figure 6, are made of flattened spheres by strong compression in the direction perpendicular to their plane.

Fig. 6. The windows

to seal the ends of the tube that forms the body of the airplane. The front of the airplane is made by instantiating the object "cockpit", rotated in the opposite direction of rotation within its definition in order to cancel the inclination of the ellipsoid, scaled by 80% on the X, Y and Z axes to reduce its size and translated to the front position so as to it comes out a little.

Defining the "wings" object constructs the right and left wing by the corresponding translation and rotation of the "wing" object definition by 90° , respectively of its instantiation by -90° with respect to the X axis. The "wing" object creates a wing by scaling the object definition "cylinder" by 17% on the Z axis in order to flatten it in the plane of the wing and rotate it around the Z axis to obtain its inclination. The wings of the tail are made by instantiating the object "wings", translated into the rear position and scaled by 50% on the X and Y axes and by 40% on the Z axis to reduce its size. The tail of the airplane is obtained by scaling the instantiation of the "cylinder" object by 50% on the X and Y axes and by 10% on the Z axis to flatten the cylinder in its plane, the rotation around the Z axis to obtain its inclination and its translation at the rear. The exhaust pipe located behind the airplane is created by instantiating the "cylinder" object, translated into the appropriate position, rotated 90° around the Z axis and scaled by 40% on the X and Z axes and by 10% on the Y axis.

The airplane engines are made by defining, respectively instantiating the "engine" object. It rotates the cone by 90° around the Z axis and instantiates the "cylinder" object, translated relative to the cone and scaled by 30% on the X and Z axes and by 10% on the Y axis, in order to build the engine. The support that fixes the engine under the wing of the airplane is obtained by scaling the instantiation of the object "sphere" by 60% on the X axis, 20% on the Y axis and 8% on the Z axis and its rotation around the Z axis to obtain its inclination.

Defining and instantiating the "windows" object determines the creation of the windows on the right side, respectively on the left one. Their rotation around the X-axis allows their location on the surface of the airplane body. The "window" object, defined within the "windows" object, achieves the central window by scaling the sphere by 60% on the X axis and by 30% on the Z axis. The six windows located towards the back, respectively towards the front, are obtained by instantiating the "window" object, translated into the corresponding positions relative to the previous positions.

CONCLUSIONS

The abundance and importance of 3D models, the permission of interactive 3D display, the simplicity of this programming language, give a wide utility to VRML. It quickly became a standard file format for 3D virtual worlds. 3D models remain the main representation used in industrial design, architecture, geographic information systems and entertainment industries.

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THE LEVEL OF AIR POLLUTION WITH SEDIMENT PARTICLES IN SĂLAJ COUNTY IN 2020

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Abstract

This paper presents the study conducted on the evolution of sediment particles in Sălaj county in 2020. The data were provided by the Sălaj County Environmental Protection Agency. This institution monitors the level of pollution with sediment particles through 16 sampling points located in various parts of Sălaj county.

These sampling points are: 7 in Zalău (at the A.P.M. office, Parcului St. no.2, Weather Station, Meteorologiei St. no. 93, 22 decembrie 1989 St. no.175, Vânătorilor St. no.3 A, Sărmaș St. no. 1, CFR Station commodities Zalău North, M. Viteazu Bd. no. 100 and Cascadei St. no. 2 B), two in Jibou (Waters District, Morii St. no.1 and SC Someș Water Company SA, FN – Sewage treatment plant), Șimleul - Transilvaniei, Cehei St. no. 244, Cehu - Silvaniei, SC Someș Water Company SA, FN - Sewage treatment plant, Prodănești, Principală St. no.161, Șarmășag Waters District Gării St. no. 122, Panic, Crasna and Grișeni.

Analysis of the evolution of sediment particles for 2020 shows that the maximum permissible concentration was exceeded once, in October, when the concentration was 19.48 g/m³.

Key words: maximum permissible concentration, monitoring, sampling points, sediment particles

INTRODUCTION

Among the main sources of pollution with sediment particles we can mention power plants, which produce thermal energy and electricity using coal, clandestine burning of household waste, which has increased significantly in recent years, the huge increase in the number of cars (Măhăra, 1969, 1976, 2003; Vancea et al., 1992; Petrea, 2001; Ciulache, 2004; Dumiter, 2005; Köteles, 2011, 2016).

Sediment particles can be solid or liquid and have chemical substances in their composition. They can occur in various forms (dust, smoke, soot, nitrates, asbestos, pesticides, bioaerosols) (Mănescu, et al., 1994; Surpățeanu, 2004; Köteles, Pereș, 2010, 2015; Moza, 2009; Peres, 2009, 2010, 2011).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In order to study the pollution of air with sediment particles in the area of Sălaj county data provided by the Sălaj County Environmental Protection Agency, located in Zalău, were used. The data were processed mathematically and presented in charts in order to show as clearly as possible the level of pollution with sediment particles.

In the area of Sălaj county the air is monitored through observation points located in strategic zones of the county. There are 16 monitoring points, out of which 7 in Zalău (at the A.P.M. office, the weather station, 22 Decembrie 1989 St., Vânătorilor st. no.3 A, Sărmaș St. no. 1, CFR Station Commodities Zalău North, M. Viteazu Bd. no. 100 and Cascadei St. no. 2 B), two in Jibou (Waters District, Morii St. no.1 and SC Someș Water Company SA, FN – Sewage Treatment Plant), Șimleul - Transilvaniei, Cehu - Silvaniei, Prodănești, Șarmășag, Panic, Crasna and Grișeni) (www.apmsj.anpm.ro).

Due to some technical problems, monitoring of the pollutant could not be done in March and April.

The maximum permissible concentration of sediment particles is 17 g/m²/month.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Annual evolution of sediment particles

In 2020 the highest concentration of sediment particles was recorded at the Prodănești sampling point, 8.51 g/m², the maximum permissible concentration was not exceeded. A value close to this one was recorded at one of the monitoring points in Zalău (22 Decembrie 1989 St.), 6.58 g/m². The lowest values were recorded at the following sampling points: Cascadei St. no. 2 B (2.40 g/m²), the Weather Station (2.50 g/m²) and Grișeni (2.75g/m²) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Evolution of sediment particles average concentrations in Sălaj county, over the year 2020

2. Monthly average evolution of sediment particles at the 16 monitoring points

The highest average concentration of the 16 monitoring points was obtained in July, 7.95 g/m^2 , followed by 6.47 g/m^2 in August and 5.88 g/m^2 in June. The lowest pollution value was obtained in January (1.47 g/m^2). The maximum permissible concentration was not exceeded (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Monthly pattern of sediment particles in Sălaj county, over the year 2020

3. Monthly evolution of sediment particles at A.P.M. Zalău

It can be seen that the highest values at the A.P.M. Zalău office sampling point were recorded in August (7.60 g/m^2), July (7.06 g/m^2) and May (6.01 g/m^2). Low values were recorded in January, 1.00 g/m^2 , and November, 1.11 g/m^2 (Fig. 3).

The maximum permissible concentration of $17 \text{ g/m}^2/\text{month}$ was not exceeded.

Fig. 3. Monthly pattern of sediment particles at the APM Zalău sampling point

4. Monthly evolution of sediment particles at the Prodănești sampling point

At the Prodănești sampling point the maximum permissible concentration was exceeded once, in October, when the value recorded was 19.48 g/m^2 , and that was followed by two other high values in September and July, 15.21 g/m^2 and 15.16 g/m^2 respectively (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Monthly pattern of sediment particles at the Prodănești sampling point

CONCLUSIONS

Analysis of the air pollution level with sediment particles for the year 2020 shows that the highest concentration in the county was recorded in Prodănești, 8.71 g/m^2 . The lowest value was recorded at Cascadei St. in Zalău (2.40 g/m^2).

The most affected area in respect of pollution with sediment particles is Prodănești, where the maximum permissible concentration (17 g/m^2) was exceeded in October (19.48 g/m^2).

Higher concentrations of sediment particles were recorded in the summer and autumn months, and lower concentrations in the winter months.

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THE MONTHLY AND ANNUAL AIR TEMPERATURE REGIMES IN THE AREA OF ORADEA, BIHOR COUNTY

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Abstract

The study of air temperature in the area of Oradea is based on data recorded at the Oradea weather station. The data were obtained from the Archives of the National Meteorological Administration (ANM). The analysis of the thermal regime covered a period of 51 years.

The multiannual average of this climatic parameter in the city of Oradea is 10.8°C.

The highest annual average air temperature value for the period included in the study was recorded in 2014 and 2019, a value of 12.8°C, followed by 12.6°C in 2018. The lowest annual average temperature was 9.0°C, and it was recorded in 1985. According to these data, on the entire area of Oradea the fluctuation of the annual average temperatures is relatively small, 3.8°C.

Over the year, the lowest monthly average is recorded in January, -0.7°C, and the highest in July, 21.4°C, which gives a monthly amplitude of 22.1°C.

Over the 51 years included in the study, negative deviations were recorded in 58.8% of the cases, while positive deviations were reported in 39.2% of the years.

Key words: air temperature, negative deviation, positive deviation

INTRODUCTION

Located only 13 km away from the western border of Romania, the municipality of Oradea is the administrative centre of Bihor county. Within the county, Oradea is located in its central-western part, on the Crișul Repede river (Berindei, et al., 1977).

A northern latitude of 47° 03' and an eastern longitude of 21° 55' places Oradea on the course of the Crișul Repede river within a hilly area that is an extension of the Western Carpathians and opens widely, along the valley of the Crișul Repede river, towards the plains (Dragotă, Gaceu, 2002; Ciulache, 2002; Cristea, 2003; Dumiter, 2007; Köteles, Pereș, 2010).

Within the Western Plain, the city of Oradea is located in its central-northern part, in the Crișurilor Plain (Posea, 1977; Pereș, et al., 2019).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Analysis of the air temperature regimes in the area of Oradea was conducted using data recorded in meteorological observation tables at Oradea weather station. The air temperature data were recorded from 1970 to 2020 (51 years) during instrumental observations performed at the weather station with.

The weather station of Oradea was set up in 1881, it is located at an altitude of 136 m and its geographical coordinates are 47° 02' northern latitude and 21° 54' eastern longitude.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Annual average air temperature

The thermal regime of air in the area of Oradea is determined by the particularities of air circulation, of the radiative factors and of the subjacent surface (Pereş A. C., Köteles N., 2011, 2013, 2015). The multiannual average of this climatic parameter in Oradea is 10.8°C.

In Oradea, the highest annual average air temperature value for the period included in the study was recorded in 2014 and 2019, 12.8°C, followed by 12.6°C in 2018. Values close to those mentioned were recorded in 2015, 12.3°C, in 2000 and 2007, 12.0°C. The lowest annual average temperature was 9.0°C and it was recorded in 1985 (Fig. 1). According to these data, on the entire area of Oradea the fluctuation of annual average temperatures is relatively small, 3.8°C, a value obtained as the difference between the highest annual average temperature (12.8°C in 2014 and in 2019) and the lowest annual average temperature (9.0°C in 1985).

Fig. 1. Evolution of annual average temperature in Oradea, 1970-2020

Deviations of annual average temperatures from the multiannual average

The annual average temperatures for the 1970-2020 period represent the „normal” or the multiannual middleness of temperature at the Oradea weather station, against which it is possible to show the direction and the value of deviations from one year to another. In order to highlight that, the deviations of annual values against the multiannual average were calculated for the 1970-2020 period.

In Oradea, values higher than the multiannual average (10.8°C) were recorded in 39.2% of the years included in the study, the deviation values varied between 0.1°C and 2.0°C, the highest positive deviation being recorded 2014 and 2019, while the lowest in 1999 (Fig. 2).

There were more years with negative thermal deviations, 58.8% of the cases, and the value of the negative deviations varied between -0.1°C and -1.8°C. The highest negative deviation was recorded in 1985 (the annual average was 9.0°C), and the lowest in 1972 and 1975 (years with an annual average of 10.7°C). There was only one year with no positive and negative deviations, the year 2001, when the annual average was 10.8°C (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Variation of annual average temperature deviations against the multiannual average in Oradea, 1970 – 2020

Monthly average air temperature

The monthly average temperature follows a natural yearly pattern, it increases beginning with January, when the lowest monthly thermal average is recorded, until July, a month with the highest monthly average temperature, after which the monthly average air temperature pattern is a decreasing one until the end of the year. So, the lowest monthly air temperature value in Oradea is recorded in January, a value of -0.7°C, and the highest in July, when it reaches 21.4°C, which gives a monthly amplitude of 22.1°C.

The analysis of the monthly average thermal values in Oradea shows that after reaching the lowest average value in January, the temperatures start to increase beginning with February, when they become positive, then they reach the maximum in July, after which they will decrease until December. (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Variation of monthly average temperature in Oradea, 1970 – 2020

In winter, the average temperature is negative only in January, while in December and February as compared to January the temperatures are higher by approximately 1°C, which is due to an intense cyclonic circulation. In January the cyclonic circulation is less active, while the anticyclonic circulation from north-east becomes stronger and the invasion of arctic or polar cold air leads to the lowest monthly average temperature.

The winters in the area of Oradea are usually moderate, without strong frosts, due to the western circulation and due to the fact that it is more protected from the invasions of polar – continental air from east and north-east (Gaceu O., 2005; Pereş A. C., et al., 2020).

In autumn, beginning with September, the temperature decreases sharply, the annual averages of these months vary between 16.3°C in September and 5.4°C in November. This cooling of the air temperature is due to the intensification of air cooling through radiative processes and to the increase of cold air advection as a result of the influence of the Siberian anticyclone (Dragotă, 1995; Măhăra, 2001, 2006; Moza, 2009; Pereş, 2012).

The analysis of the thermal differences between the months of the year shows that the changes of average air temperature values from one month to another happen slowly in the summer and winter months (1-2°C), more obvious thermal contrasts occur in the months of the transition seasons (5-6°C).

The highest positive difference (+ $\Delta t^{\circ}\text{C}$) between two months occurs in spring, between March and April, when the thermal increase is 5.5°C.

The highest negative difference ($-\Delta t^{\circ}\text{C}$) between two months occurs during autumn, between September and October, when it is 5.5°C .

CONCLUSIONS

In Oradea, the multiannual average temperature for the period included in the study is 10.8°C . The highest annual average air temperature value for the period included in the study was recorded in 2014 and 2019, a value of 12.8°C , while the lowest was 9.0°C and it was recorded in 1985.

Values higher than the multiannual average (10.8°C) were recorded in 39.2% of the years included in the study, while the negative thermal deviations made up 58.8% of the cases.

The lowest monthly air temperature is recorded in *January*, with an average of -0.7°C , and the highest in *July*, when it reaches 21.4°C , which gives a monthly amplitude of 22.1°C .

The winters in the area of Oradea are usually moderate, without strong frosts, due to the western circulation and due to the fact that it is more protected from the invasions of polar – continental air from east and north-east.

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ADJUSTMENT OF NUMERICAL DATA FOLLOWING SOME MEASUREMENTS

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Abstract

In this paper, we will present a mathematical estimate based on numerical measured temperature and humidity data, from an established area, on consecutive days, in the current year. The method used is called the adjustment of numerical data stability by measurements (x_i, y_i) , i takes values from 1 to n , which can be done with minimal error. The phenomena in various fields of activity can be represented by a link, which can be determined. This is given by a function between an independent variable x and a dependent variable y , $f: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, this is $y = f(x)$. Determining the legitimacy or the trend of variation, is this function f .

It is possible to research phenomena of human activity, which propose the determination of this function, using values observed and measured by the researcher, be they x_i and y_i , distinct points. There are two steps in adjusting the numerical data. The first stage refers to determining the type of trend, as a graphical representation in the plan of the measured numerical values. The second stage consists in determining the parameters a_i , i from 1 to p , by the least squares method, which is the most frequently used.

Key words: function, temperature, humidity, numerical data

INTRODUCTION

We collected numerical data measured, from a metropolitan area, in five consecutive days of October 2021, characterized by temperature, humidity and other characteristics that we will not talk about in this paper. The processing we will do refers only to the two quantities, which we denote by $x = T$ (outside temperature measured in degrees Celsius), $y = H$ (outside humidity determined as a percentage %). We adjust these numerical data using the two steps listed above, which can be various mathematical descriptions. There are several types of trends, for example exponential, logarithmic, linear, parabolic, e.t.c., which are characterized by functions with real coefficients or parameters $y = f(x; a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_p)$. In the case of the linear trend we have the representative function: $y = f(x; a, b) = ax + b$ where a, b are real unknowns, for the parabolic trend: $y = f(x; a, b, c)$, where a, b, c are real unknowns, for the exponential trend $y = f(x; a, b) = ab^x$, where $b > 0$, $b \neq 1$, a are real unknowns.

In this case, for the graphical representation of the 5 points in the plan that determines the type of trend, we will use the Microsoft Excel program, and then we start the mathematical processing.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The measured data are represented in the following table 1.

Table 1

Measured data					
T (° C)	15	17	19	18	18
U	39%	50%	53%	58%	61%

After drawing the graph, a linear trend is obtained, which can be studied mathematically. The axis of the abscissa OX, is represented by the temperature in degrees Celsius, and the axis of the ordinate OY, is the axis of humidity, as in figure 1:

Figure 1. The study of trend

The representative function is $U = f(T; a, b) = aT + b$, a, b unknown real, U is the dependent quantity, and T is the independent quantity. We want to determine the adjustment function starting from this amount which must be minimum.

$$S(a, b) = \sum_{i=1}^5 [(a \cdot T_i + b) - U_i]^2 \quad (1)$$

This method consists in determining the coefficients a and b , solving the system of partial differential equations:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial S}{\partial a} = 0 \\ \frac{\partial S}{\partial b} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2).$$

The system thus replaced becomes:

$$\begin{cases} 2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^5 (a \cdot T_i + b - U_i) \cdot T_i = 0 \\ 2 \cdot \sum_{i=1}^5 (a \cdot T_i + b - U_i) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (3).$$

According to elementary calculations, the form results:

$$\begin{cases} \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 T_i^2 \right) \cdot a + \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 T_i \right) \cdot b = \sum_{i=1}^5 T_i \cdot U_i \\ \left(\sum_{i=1}^5 T_i \right) \cdot a + 5 \cdot b = \sum_{i=1}^5 U_i \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Replacing the data in the following table 2,

Table 2

Data to use

T_i	U_i	$(T_i)^2$	$T_i \cdot U_i$
15	0,39	225	5,85
17	0,5	289	8,5
19	0,53	361	10,07
18	0,58	324	10,44
18	0,61	324	10,98
TOTAL	87	1523	45,84

we get:

$$\begin{cases} 1523 \cdot a + 87 \cdot b = 45,84 \\ 87 \cdot a + 5 \cdot b = 2,61 \end{cases} \quad (5).$$

After solving this elementary system by a correct mathematical method, we obtain:

$$a \cong 0,046304 \dots, \quad b \cong -0,2836896 \dots \quad (6)$$

Therefore the adjustment line has the equation:

$$f(T) = a \cdot T + b \quad (7),$$

which becomes by the method applied:

$$f(T) = 0,046304 \cdot T - 0,28369 = U, \quad (8).$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result obtained is an adjustment of the source function of the measured data. In this case, the linear adjustment function has two unknown a , b , real numbers, which by the least squares method approximated the values mentioned above. For a closer evaluation of the approximate results, we can check the estimate for our values. For example, when T is 15°C , using the determined linear adjustment function and substituting the temperature in it, we obtain the value of humidity $U = 0.41$.

The more accurate the numerical data and this refers to the minimization of measurement errors and the more numerous they are, the more accurate the estimation of the adjustment function.

CONCLUSIONS

If we used this adjustment function for a humidity value from another day in October, in the same metropolitan area, we would get the estimated temperature value from that day. For example, if the measured humidity is $U = 0.61$, it will correspond, after the adjustment function, to a temperature value of $T = 19.3^{\circ}\text{C}$. Obviously, these results can also be used for more laborious and estimated forecasts, with respect to temperature and humidity for other dates, months and years.

This mathematical method can be used for phenomena in any field of human activity, as a research method, which can be used for subsequent estimates.

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FOREST ECONOMICS, FROM THEORY TO SUSTAINABLE APPLICATIONS

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Abstract

The present paradigm regarding the forests, from an economic point of view, has to swift drastically in order to keep the sustainability of it. The existing forest economic models, rooted in sustained yield timber management systems and neo-classical [economic framework](#), are subject to many limitations. Social, economic, and ecological features of sustainable forest management (SFM) are different than that of sustained yield timber management. Hence, the economics of SFM will be based on different economic principles. The two main requirements of the economics of SFM are the economics of multiple equilibria, and a consumer choice theory that incorporates heterogeneity of agents, context specific and dynamics of preferences, distinction between needs and wants, and the subordination of needs. These requirements will need the extension of the boundaries of forest economics. Five basic principles—principles of ‘both-and’, ‘existence’, ‘relativity’, ‘uncertainty’, and ‘complementarity’ will work as a foundation, and the economic principles, developed by evolutionary, institutional, ecological economists and economists from other new streams of economics, will be the useful tools to extend these boundaries.

Key words: Pollution, forest economics, health, sustainability, theories, change of paradigms

INTRODUCTION

Deforestation process represents a major negative impact of land all over the world. These changes are often presented as a battle between economic, social and environmental forces. "Forest Economics" shows that economics has a crucial role in forestry. The author tries to explain by examining the influence of profit-maximizing on the way in which foresters take decisions on harvesting timber, planting forests and the management of crops. Another part of this paper considers silvicultural decision-making. It proceeds from optimal rotation determination, via selection of spacing and thinning regimes, to crop improvement and protection decisions, and choice between silvicultural systems. Although is concerned largely with the rationale and applications of cost-benefit analysis. It considers in detail both the evaluation of the social benefits and costs of forestry, and the pricing of factors of production in developing economies. The paper concluding section discusses the role of forestry in the generation of national and

regional employment, in state involvement in forestry, in world timber prices and the interpretation of forestry policy at local level.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Forest economic models based on the neo-classical framework are subject to serious limitations. The emergence of a new forest management paradigm in the last two decades has further amplified these limitations (Toman et al., 1996).

The new forest management paradigm has transformed forest management from timber management to forest ecosystem management, from sustained timber yield management to sustainable forest management (SFM), and from forest management by exclusion to management by inclusion of user groups, and is commonly known as SFM.

The limitations of forest economic models have resulted in the severance of links between these models and social perceptions and practices of forest management.

The gap between theoretical models and practices has roots in mainstream economics itself. Many economists have observed multi-dimensional limitations of the neo-classical paradigm resulting in low 'evidence theory ratio' (Holmstrom and Tirole, 1989). However, the economics profession, as a whole, has been re-examining and challenging almost every basis of the neo-classical thought to reduce this gap. For example, experimental economists, such as Camerer(1997), Rabin(1998) and Camerer and Thaler (1995), have been working to get a clear picture of decision making by 'Homo-sapiens' as against 'Homo-economicus' agents. Many economists have proposed alternative economic frameworks that overcome some of the limitations of the neo-classical paradigm and incorporate some features of behavioral patterns of 'Homo-sapiens' observed by experimental economists. Evolutionary economics has challenged the concepts of maximization in an uncertain environment and a single competitive equilibrium; institutional economics has incorporated institutions in economic analysis; many branches of economics, such as ecological economics, socio-economics and post-Keynesian economics, have challenged the concept of mono-utility, static preferences, and a maximizing rational agent. Game-theoretic models have been developed to understand and explain co-operative, non-cooperative and strategic behaviors of people in diverse settings, and agent-based models have incorporated heterogeneous agents, changing preferences, and non-maximizing behaviors in economic models. However, no significant attempt has been made in the field of forest economics to incorporate the concepts

and principles emerging from these new economic thoughts. Thus, it is now the turn of forest economists to respond to new challenges of forest management by extending the boundaries of forest economics beyond neo-classical economics. This paper has two main objectives: 1. to demonstrate basic limitations of the models, dominant in forest economics, and usefulness of emerging economic thoughts to overcome these limitations; 2. to establish the relevance of emerging economic thoughts to the economics of SFM, and to provide some basic principles for the economics of SFM.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper tries to make an awareness about the classic way of viewing the forestry sector. The concept of SFM is the reflection of social, economic, and environmental conditions of the late twentieth and early twenty-first century, which are quite different from the conditions of nineteenth and early twentieth century. Management principles and silviculture of SFM are quite different than the management principles and silviculture of forest management based on timber-yield regulation. Similarly, the economic principles of SFM need to be reflective of social, economic, and environmental conditions of twenty-first century and management principles and silviculture of SFM. The silviculture of the Faustmann formula continues to have a direct application for plantation forestry, but not to the SFM. As demonstrated in this paper, existing forest economic models, including Faustmann's formulation, must be refined, and some new economic theories and models must be developed to incorporate the features of SFM. The two dominant requirements of the economics of SFM are the economics of multiple equilibria, and a consumer choice theory that incorporates context specific and dynamic preferences, heterogeneous agents, distinction between needs and wants, and subordination of needs. These two requirements are beyond the boundaries of neo-classical economics. The boundaries of forest economics will have to be extended

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FOREST GOVERNANCE FOR THE FUTURE HEALTH OF THE PLANET

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Abstract

Forest governance is that management branch that deals with the administrative, economic, legal, social and technical measures involved in the conservation and use of natural forests and forest plantations. It also involves various degrees of human intervention to safeguard the forest ecosystem, its functions and its resources for the sustained production of goods and the provision of environmental services.

Key words: conservation of the natural forest, ecosystem, participatory management, sustainable governance

INTRODUCTION

Although the old forestry continues to be widely practised, specially in the developing countries, there is an increasing trend in EU countries and specially in USA towards the forest management as ecological systems with multiple economic benefits and environmental values, and with broad public participation in the decision-making process. This new concept is named 'sustainable forest management'.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The aims to ensure that the benefits - both material and intangible - derived from the forest meet present needs, while at the same time ensuring their continued availability and contribution to long-term social and economic development. General acceptance of, and political commitment to, the principles of sustainable forest management have continued to grow, reinforced by the increased focus on forestry since UNCED. Chapter 11 ('Combating Deforestation') of UNCED's Agenda 21 and the 'Forest Principles' emphasized strongly the need to reconcile the productive functions of forests with their protective, environmental and social functions. Substantial effort has been made over the last two years to develop common criteria at national, regional and eco-regional levels by which sustainable forest management can be defined, and to specify indicators that can be used to monitor and evaluate it. The trend towards sustainable forest management is bringing considerable change in how

forests are perceived and used. Forest management for production of non-wood forest products is receiving more attention. Protective functions of forests are being given more emphasis, resulting in modified management practices. The needs of local, forest-dependent people are being given greater attention. The strict distinctions formerly drawn between production forests, protection forests and (nature) conservation areas have become more important today. For example: many rural development and conservation projects are focusing on increasing production of wood and non-wood forest products in 'buffer zones' as a means of taking pressure off conservation areas; the maintenance of protective functions is being given greater attention in production forests; and the role of forests outside protected areas in the conservation of biological diversity is being studied more intently. Trends in forest policies and institutional arrangements are having direct impacts on forest management. Following the general trend towards decentralization, government forestry administrations in many countries, developed and developing, are making efforts to decentralize control over forest resource management. This involves the gradual devolution of responsibility within the line agencies, from the central to the provincial or district level. Local officers are being given greater decision-making authority on local management issues. This implies changes in management practices to those which have a closer relation to local conditions. A second significant trend is in privatization, either of land or of forestry operations. This trend has obvious implications for forest management in terms of an increased profit motive driving management decisions and, in the case of leases and concessions, the need for government to monitor operations to ensure that agreed conditions related to management are met. A third trend is that of ensuring greater participation by a wide range of interest groups in the planning process. This requires that forest departments develop the institutional capacity and the capability to work with various groups (implying far more effort than in the past in communication, extension and mediation) and are able to modify management plans and practices effectively to meet the agreed objectives. Finally, there is a trend towards encouraging greater involvement of local communities in the management of forest resources. Participatory management of forest resources is not only seen as a means to encourage sustainable forest management, but is also a pragmatic response to the constraints imposed on forest departments by their shrinking financial and human resources. The development of participatory management systems, in which local communities play an important role in the day-to-day management and protection of forest resources, has been rapid in many developing countries, resulting in a wide variety of management arrangements fashioned as appropriate to local conditions. These include:

joint forest management; community forestry programmes; integrated conservation and development programmes used mainly in conjunction with nature conservation efforts; and village land management (referred to as 'aménagement des terroirs' in French), which is developing rapidly in West Africa. Joint forest management (JFM), a collaborative management approach that has been adopted in a number of states in India and in some Southeast Asian countries, has had some major successes. It is based on the principle that local communities become directly involved in the management of public forests and, in doing so, benefit directly from the use of the forests. The forest products industrial sector in most countries continues to adapt to current trends and to anticipate future developments. Recent advances in achieving higher recovery rates have led to a significant reduction in the amount of wood harvested from the forests. Increased consumption of forest products, demand for higher quality products, changes in the availability of raw materials, and public pressure towards environmental aspects of forest management, production and processing, will continue to be major factors affecting technology and product development. Major trends in supply and demand of forest products are having a significant impact on marketing at both the industrial and community enterprise levels. Industrialized and developing countries, and countries in transition, are facing different challenges related to marketing of forest products. Industrialized countries are responding to the emergence of a range of new products (including those filling a small market niche for products from sustainably-managed forests and for speciality non-wood 'natural' forest products, and those resulting from new processing technologies) and an increasing number of products made from residues, recycled materials and plantation-grown timber. Decreasing availability of well-known, quality tropical hardwoods is directing them to high-value end uses. Marketing such wood products requires specialized information and capabilities in order to compete effectively with other materials. Changes in the developing countries are due to more fundamental trends, both within and outside of the forestry sector, including: banning of exports of logs and a rapid move to manufacturing of value-added products in an increasing number of tropical and non-tropical countries; reduced availability of industrial wood from virgin forests with an increased supply of wood coming from plantations, woodlots and agroforestry systems; and a rapid rate of urbanization in many countries, which is changing, quite dramatically, the demand for forest products and the ways in which the products are provided to customers. Countries in transition, as Romania, are facing a dramatically different marketing environment than in the past. Captive domestic markets are being replaced by competitive domestic and export markets. Parastatal organizations, previously responsible for

marketing products in centrally-planned countries, have been replaced by privatized industries and their emerging marketing organizations.

All these changes have focused more attention on marketing issues, and various actions are being taken in many parts of the world to enable marketing to function more efficiently:

- marketing information systems are being invigorated or set up (e.g., the SIMSTRAT of the Fundación Chile);
- forest products marketing education and training programmes are being initiated and strengthened in many universities and training schools throughout the world (e.g., the College of Forestry at the University of the Philippines in Los Baños); and
- a number of international and regional workshops on marketing have been organized to facilitate exchange of information (e.g., sawnwood marketing in countries in transition).

CONCLUSIONS

As community forestry, agroforestry and local production systems for non-wood forest products have gained in importance, increased attention has been paid to marketing as an essential component of these activities. The emergence of these new sources of wood and other forest-derived products is resulting in the development of new, locally-based marketing structures. This trend is also reflected in increased attention being paid to marketing in community forestry and agroforestry education and training programmes (e.g., the Regional Community Forestry Training Centre, RECOFTC, at Kasetsart University, Thailand), and in efforts to build local capacities in marketing.

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